

RED GIANTS IN ECLIPSING BINARIES AS A BENCHMARK
FOR ASTEROSEISMOLOGY

BY

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“Red Giants in Eclipsing Binaries as a Benchmark for Asteroseismology,” a dissertation prepared by Meredith L. Rawls in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Philosophy, has been approved and accepted by the following:

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DEDICATION

To my mother, Kathryn Linwood Rawls (1950–2004)

who dreamed, with some trepidation,
of living to see me travel into space.

These stars are for you.

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¹<https://github.com/sczesla/PyAstronomy>

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ABSTRACT

RED GIANTS IN ECLIPSING BINARIES AS A BENCHMARK FOR ASTEROSEISMOLOGY

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Red giants with solar-like oscillations are astrophysical laboratories for probing the Milky Way. The *Kepler* Space Telescope revolutionized asteroseismology by consistently monitoring thousands of targets, including several red giants in eclipsing binaries. Binarity allows us to directly measure stellar properties independently of asteroseismology. In this dissertation, we study a subset of eight red giant eclipsing binaries observed by *Kepler* with a range of orbital periods, oscillation behavior, and stellar activity. Two of the systems do not show solar-like oscillations at all. We use a suite of modeling tools to combine photometry and spectroscopy into a comprehensive picture of each star's life. One noteworthy case is a double red giant binary. The two stars are nearly twins, but have one main

set of solar-like oscillations with unusually low-amplitude, wide modes, likely due to stellar activity and modest tidal forces acting over the 171 day eccentric orbit. Mixed modes indicate the main oscillating star is on the secondary red clump (a core-He-burning star), and stellar evolution modeling supports this with a coeval history for a pair of red clump stars. The other seven systems are all red giant branch stars (shell-H-burning) with main sequence companions. The two non-oscillators have the strongest magnetic signatures and some of the strongest lifetime tidal forces with nearly-circular 20–34 day orbits. One system defies this trend with oscillations and a 19 day orbit. The four long-period systems (> 100 days) have oscillations, more eccentric orbits, and less stellar activity. They are all detached binaries consistent with coevolution. We find the asteroseismic scaling laws are approximately correct, but fail the most for stars that are least like the Sun by systematically overestimating both mass and radius. Strong magnetic activity and tidal effects often occur in tandem and act to suppress solar-like oscillations. These red giant binaries offer an unprecedented opportunity to test stellar physics and are important benchmarks for ensemble asteroseismology. Future asteroseismic studies should know they are excluding magnetically active stars and close binaries and be aware that asteroseismic masses and radii are both overestimated.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The Utility of Eclipsing Binary Stars

Binary and multiple stars are ubiquitous in the Milky Way. As stars in these systems orbit one another, a distant observer may see periodic dips in brightness as one star appears to pass in front of another. Observing these eclipses yields a wealth of information about the constituent stars including relative sizes and luminosities. If information about the stars' motion is also available, it is possible to deduce the scale of the system and measure absolute properties for each star. Dynamic modeling combines information from radial velocity motion and eclipses to fully characterize the orbital parameters of the system and measure each star's mass, radius, and other physical parameters.

The crucial role of binaries in measuring physical properties of stars is difficult to overstate. While some stellar parameters can be inferred from spectroscopy, population studies, evolutionary modeling, or even asteroseismology, the physics of gravity when one thing orbits another thing is a uniquely direct astrophysical measuring tool. In this case, of course, the "things" are both stars; bright enough to see with telescopes from Earth, yet far enough away that the best images only resolve a single point source when there are really two.

Why is it important to measure stellar properties in the first place? Simply put, stars are the source of nearly all light in the Universe. Because light is the fundamental tool used by astronomers, understanding how stars form, live, and die informs everything from exoplanets to extragalactic studies. A star's mass determines its fate, and orbital dynamics is the only direct method for measuring stellar mass.

In order to turn a distant point of light into a physical pair of stars, at minimum we require several measurements of one star's radial velocity. Such a system is called a single-lined spectroscopic binary (SB1), because one star's movements are observed in a single set of Doppler-shifted absorption lines. If the motion of both stars can be measured, then the system is a double-lined spectroscopic binary (SB2). Each star's radial velocity is given by

$$V = K[\cos(\theta + \omega) + e \cos \omega] + \gamma, \quad (1.1)$$

where θ is the true anomaly, an angular coordinate which describes the location of the star in its orbit, ω is the argument of periastron, or orientation of the orbit on the sky, e is the orbital eccentricity, and γ is the systemic velocity of the binary relative to our Solar System. The amplitude of the radial velocity curve is

$$K = \frac{2\pi a \sin i}{P_{\text{orb}} \sqrt{1 - e^2}}, \quad (1.2)$$

where a is the semi-major axis of the orbit, i is the orbital inclination, and P_{orb} is the orbital period. The radial velocity is therefore a function of $(K, e, \omega, T_0, P_{\text{orb}}, \gamma)$, noting that P_{orb} and the zeropoint T_0 enter the equation via the true anomaly, θ . For a full derivation, see Chapters 2 and 3 in Hilditch (2001).

We can combine the information from a single radial velocity curve with Kepler's Third Law to yield the binary mass function,

$$f(m) = \frac{4\pi^2}{G} \frac{(a \sin i)^3}{P_{\text{orb}}^2} = \frac{K_1^3 P_{\text{orb}} (1 - e^2)^{3/2}}{2\pi G}, \quad (1.3)$$

where G is the gravitational constant. This can be rewritten using Newton's laws of gravity and the fact that $M_1/M_2 \propto K_2/K_1$ to yield

$$f(m) = \frac{(M_2 \sin i)^3}{(M_1 + M_2)^2} = M_1 \frac{q^3}{(1 + q)^2} \sin^3 i, \quad (1.4)$$

where M_1 and M_2 represent the mass of each star in the binary (with corresponding radial velocity curve amplitudes K_1 and K_2) and the mass ratio $q = M_2/M_1$. However, it is impossible to determine the component masses of an SB1 without additional information. An SB2 yields a pair of mass functions from each radial velocity curve, which can then be combined to determine component masses; however, the inclination must be inferred in some other way. This is the best-case scenario.

Eclipsing binaries can be SB1 or SB2, but in either case, observing a light curve that contains primary and secondary eclipses greatly constrains the problem. In this dissertation, we define the primary eclipse as the deepest eclipse. Eclipse timing contains information about the shape and orientation of the binary orbit (e and ω), while eclipse depth and duration give relative stellar radii (R_1/a and R_2/a) and a luminosity ratio. Stellar radii may be estimated from eclipse durations by considering four times: start of eclipse ingress, start of total eclipse, end of total eclipse, and end of eclipse egress. In units of fractional phases, these are ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 , ϕ_3 , and ϕ_4 , respectively. For a circular orbit, we can then write

$$(\phi_2 - \phi_1) = (\phi_4 - \phi_3) = \frac{2R_2}{2\pi a} \quad (1.5)$$

and

$$(\phi_3 - \phi_1) = (\phi_4 - \phi_2) = \frac{2R_1}{2\pi a} \quad (1.6)$$

to directly measure fractional radii (Hilditch 2001). When only partial (grazing) eclipses occur, or no eclipses at all, this procedure cannot be used. If the orbit is eccentric, the orbital speeds of the two stars change as a function of orbital phase, and the durations of the two eclipses will generally differ. In addition, the location in phase of the secondary eclipse relative to the primary eclipse will be shifted by

an amount that depends on e and ω . As a result, the inclination, fractional radii, and eclipse depths are then related by

$$\cos^2 i + \sin^2 i \sin^2 \phi_{1,4} = (R_2/a)^2 (1 + R_1/R_2) \quad (1.7)$$

and

$$\cos^2 i + \sin^2 i \sin^2 \phi_{2,3} = (R_2/a)^2 (1 - R_1/R_2). \quad (1.8)$$

In order for eclipses to appear at all, i must be near 90° , which serves as an additional constraint on the system geometry. Taken together, all the orbital parameters of a SB2 binary as well as component masses and radii may be measured by fitting both an eclipsing light curve model and a pair of radial velocity curve models to observations. This makes binary stars one of nature's most convenient laboratories.

1.2. Asteroseismology With Solar-like Oscillations

Until this point, we have implicitly assumed that the brightness of a star does not appear to change unless another star gets in the way. In fact, numerous physical processes can cause stars to vary on a wide range of timescales, from nuclear to thermal to dynamical. One such process is stochastically-driven surface oscillations. These oscillations have periods on the order of minutes to days and are shorter than a star's dynamical timescale,

$$t_{\text{dyn}} = \left(\frac{R^3}{GM} \right)^{1/2} \propto \bar{\rho}^{-1/2}, \quad (1.9)$$

where $\bar{\rho}$ is the mean density of the star, because they do not propagate all the way from the surface to the center (Aerts et al. 2010). They are called solar-like oscillations because they exist in the Sun and other stars with outer convection

zones. Solar-like oscillation modes are intrinsically stable, and manifest themselves as small fluctuations in a light curve. Stars with solar-like oscillations ring like bells, with ringing oscillation modes excited by the turbulence of convection. There is not enough energy to drive the oscillations, but rather a star resonates in some of its natural oscillation frequencies. Using these and other stellar pulsation mechanisms to study stars from the inside out is called asteroseismology.

The three-dimensional equations of motion for oscillations in stars are functions of spherical harmonics, and there are two main sets of solutions which lead to two types of oscillation modes: pressure modes (p modes), which propagate in the convection zone, and gravity modes (g modes), which propagate in the radiative zone. The modes are named according to the restoring force (pressure or buoyancy, which is driven by gravity) for a star perturbed from equilibrium. As illustrated in Figure 1.1, p modes propagate in the outer regions of a Sun-like star and are directly observable as brightness fluctuations, while g modes are sensitive to conditions deep inside the star. As a Sun-like main sequence star evolves, its central regions contract, and the g modes are occasionally able to interact with p modes in the stellar envelope. The g mode interaction with p modes may then be observed as “mixed modes.” See Section 2.6.1.2 for an example of measuring mixed modes in practice.

Because solar-like oscillations originate as natural resonances, they carry information about the interior structure of a star. Figure 1.2 shows power spectra of solar-like oscillations for stars of approximately $1 M_{\odot}$ that range from main sequence stars up to evolved giants. As stars get larger and less dense, the location of the characteristic “comb” of oscillation modes decreases in frequency and becomes more tightly spaced. From power spectra like the ones in Figure 1.2, it is

Fig. 1.1.— Propagation of pressure and gravity waves in a cross-section of a stellar interior. The p waves in panel (a) are bent as the sound speed increases with depth until they reach an inner turning point where they refract (dotted circles). At the surface, these waves are reflected by a rapid decrease in density. The g waves in panel (b) are trapped in the stellar interior. Figure 5 from Cunha et al. (2007).

possible to measure two observable quantities: the large frequency separation between modes of consecutive spherical order, $\Delta\nu$, and the frequency of maximum oscillation power, ν_{\max} . The large frequency separation is related to the sound speed, and therefore the average density of the star, while ν_{\max} is related to the acoustic cutoff frequency which is determined by the near-surface properties. This suggests scaling relations of the form

$$\Delta\nu \propto \bar{\rho}^{-1/2} \quad (1.10)$$

and

$$\nu_{\max} \propto g T_{\text{eff}}^{-1/2}, \quad (1.11)$$

where $g = GM/R^2$ is the stellar surface gravity and T_{eff} is the effective temperature. For a full derivation of these relations and a discussion of the asymptotic development (Tassoul 1980), see Chaplin & Miglio (2013) and references therein.

Fig. 1.2.— Power spectra of solar-like oscillators observed by the *Kepler* space telescope. Redder colors indicate later evolutionary phases, and thus lower surface gravity. All the stars have masses $\sim 1 M_{\odot}$. The upper right panels are main sequence stars, the lower right panels are subgiants, and the left panels are evolved giant stars. Adapted from Figures 3 and 4 in Chaplin & Miglio (2013).

In practice, solar-like oscillations have become a relatively new way to measure the mass and radius of oscillating stars that is independent of the dynamic binary modeling technique described in Section 1.1. This is achieved by combining Equations (1.10) and (1.11) into scaling relations which use the Sun as a reference:

$$\left(\frac{R}{R_{\odot}}\right) \simeq \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\odot}}\right) \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\odot}}\right)^{-2} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}}\right)^{0.5} \quad (1.12)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}}\right) \simeq \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\odot}}\right)^3 \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\odot}}\right)^{-4} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}}\right)^{1.5}. \quad (1.13)$$

It is important to note that these scaling relations require careful measurements of not only ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$, but also an accurate determination of T_{eff} . In addition, due to the functional form, asteroseismically estimated masses will be inherently

more uncertain than radii for a given measurement of $(\nu_{\max}, \Delta\nu, T_{\text{eff}})$ and their associated uncertainties.

Asteroseismology is a powerful tool for studying evolved stars in particular. Because evolved red giants are larger and less dense than solar-type stars, they oscillate more slowly, which means that a light curve time series may have a correspondingly longer cadence and still contain information about the oscillation modes. This is analogous to recording a movie with a slow frame rate: sufficiently slow movements would appear fine, but faster motion would be poorly-resolved or missed entirely. As it turns out, observations from the *Kepler* space telescope taken every 29.4 minutes (long-cadence) over many 90 day quarters are ideal for asteroseismic studies of red giant stars. The primary goal of the *Kepler* mission (Borucki et al. 2010) was to identify Earth-like exoplanets orbiting Sun-like stars by searching for regular transit events in a single region of the sky. *Kepler* was a resounding success, discovering hundreds of exoplanets and amassing four years of nearly-continuous observations in both long-cadence and short-cadence (1 minute) mode. After two of its reaction wheels failed, it was repurposed as *K2*¹ to continue precision photometry for a variety of science cases in different regions of the sky.

As *Kepler* ushered in a new era of exoplanet discovery, it simultaneously revolutionized stellar astrophysics. Binary stars are regular “false positives” in the eyes of exoplanet hunters, and *Kepler* opened a new window into stellar interiors via asteroseismology with the sheer number of stars observed. While *Kepler* short-cadence observations are good for finding solar-like oscillations in Sun-like stars, long-cadence observations are available for more targets and led to the discovery of

¹For more on the *Kepler* mission and *K2*, see <http://keplerscience.arc.nasa.gov>

numerous oscillating red giants. Figure 1.3 illustrates how many new evolved oscillators have been discovered and characterized using *Kepler* long-cadence data. Together with data from the CoRoT mission (Baglin et al. 2006), characterizing large numbers of stars quickly with the scaling relations became possible for the first time. This method of ensemble asteroseismology does not require detailed modeling of individual oscillation frequencies, and can in principle be done automatically and without dependencies on stellar models.

Fig. 1.3.— Stochastically oscillating stars discovered with different observing campaigns. Colors illustrate detections by ground-based observations (black), CoRoT (blue), and *Kepler* (red). Grey lines are solar-metallicity evolutionary tracks to guide the eye. The majority of the oscillating stars are evolved red giants from *Kepler* long-cadence data. Adapted from Figure 3 in Huber (2014).

While the scaling relations are powerful for characterizing large numbers of stars quickly, they remain relatively untested. This is why binary stars can play a key role as benchmarks for ensemble asteroseismology. Along the way, evolved stars that can be studied independently from two perspectives—as a binary and

as a red giant with solar-like oscillations—are packed with information about the physical conditions necessary for solar-like oscillations to persist.

1.3. Identifying Oscillating Red Giants in Eclipsing Binaries

Gaulme et al. (2013) realized the opportunity presented by two *Kepler* catalogs: one containing over 14,000 red giants² and the other with more than 2,500 eclipsing binaries (Prša et al. 2011; Slawson et al. 2011). Both were curated from the larger Kepler Input Catalog (KIC, Brown et al. 2011), and more recently, the eclipsing binary catalog has been updated (Kirk et al. 2016). When Gaulme et al. (2013) cross-correlated the two catalogs and identified and eliminated false positives, 13 strong candidate red giants in eclipsing binaries remained, of which 12 were previously unknown. Gaulme et al. (2014) updated this list to 19, completed a preliminary asteroseismic analysis of the oscillating systems by measuring $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{\max} , and explored why four of them do not exhibit solar-like oscillations. They found evidence that oscillation modes may be damped in the presence of dark features (i.e., star spots) on the surface of tidally-locked red giants. This agrees with Chaplin et al. (2011), a statistical survey of solar-type *Kepler* stars which found that the number of stars with detected solar-like oscillations decreases with increasing levels of stellar activity.

To investigate further, it is necessary to study some red giants in eclipsing binaries (hereafter RG/EBs) in greater detail. By adding high-resolution spectra to the light curves, we can thoroughly characterize RG/EB orbital dynamics, measure component masses and radii, scrutinize their atmospheres, and model their

²http://archive.stsci.edu/kepler/red_giant_release.html

evolutionary histories. All of this can be done independently of asteroseismology for binaries containing both oscillating and non-oscillating red giants. In the end, we have one of the best-studied samples of stars which can begin to address the connections among magnetic activity, tidal synchronization timescales, stellar evolution histories in the context of binarity, and the presence or lack of solar-like oscillations.

1.4. Observations and Analysis

1.4.1. Sample Selection

The eight RG/EBs studied in this dissertation are selected from those in Gaulme et al. (2013) and Gaulme et al. (2014) to span a range of properties: short and long orbital periods, with and without solar-like oscillations, and differing levels of magnetic activity based on light curve variability. They are, in order of shortest to longest orbital period: KICs 8702921, 9291629, 3955867, 10001167, 5786154, 7037405, 9246715, and 9970396. The double red giant KIC 9246715 is worthy of special attention, because it is the only system with two evolved components. We find a single clear signature of solar-like oscillations attributable to one star for this system even though it contains two stars which are nearly twins. The rest of the RG/EB subset is composed of evolved red giant branch stars with main sequence companions. They are roughly divided into three with shorter orbital periods, two of which lack solar-like oscillations, and four with longer orbital periods, which all have solar-like oscillations. All of the binaries are in the *Kepler* field of view, with apparent *Kepler* magnitudes ranging from 9–14 mag. All but one are SB2. While SB1 systems cannot be used as a direct test of asteroseismology, they are still useful probes of what physical properties can

affect oscillation behavior, especially given that all known RG/EB SB1 systems do exhibit solar-like oscillations.

1.4.2. *Stellar Light Curves and Spectra*

Two general types of observations are used here: light curves, which measure how a star’s brightness varies with time, and spectra, which measure how much light is being emitted as a function of wavelength, or color. Stellar variability in light curves reveals many stellar secrets, from eclipses and transits to star spots and pulsations. The light curve time series used are primarily *Kepler* space telescope long-cadence (29.4 minute) data. Supplementary light curve points taken in the Johnson *BVRI* filters come from the robotically controlled 1 m telescope at Apache Point Observatory (APO), and are potentially useful for constraining the variability of RG/EBs as a function of wavelength. The *Kepler* data span 2009–2013 and the *BVRI* points were taken in 2014–2015.

The spectra in this dissertation are used for several purposes: radial velocities, stellar atmosphere modeling, and investigating magnetic activity. Most of the optical spectra are from the Astrophysical Research Consortium Echelle Spectrograph (ARCES) instrument on the APO 3.5 m telescope. A few optical spectra of KIC 9246715 are from the Tillinghast Reflector Echelle Spectrograph (TRES) on the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory (FLWO) 1.5 m telescope, and several near-infrared spectra of KIC 7037405 are from the APO Galactic Evolution Experiment (APOGEE) survey. The ARCES spectra were collected in 2012–2015, the TRES spectra in 2012–2013, and the APOGEE survey ran from 2011–2014 (Alam et al. 2015). To extract radial velocities from spectra, we use the broadening func-

tion technique described in Appendix A, and to disentangle two individual stellar spectra from a set of observed composite spectra we use a Fourier decomposition technique called FDBinary (fd3), which is reviewed in Appendix B.

1.4.3. Modeling Techniques

Once the light curves and spectra have been appropriately reduced and processed (see Sections 2.2 and 3.2), we use three primary methods to model the observations and gain insights about stellar physics. The first is dynamical modeling with the Eclipsing Light Curve (ELC Orosz & Hauschildt 2000) program. ELC takes a set of input observations of a binary star system, typically light curves and radial velocities, and uses one of several optimizers to iteratively reduce a χ^2 function and find the best global solution. A thorough description of ELC, its optimization techniques, and the resulting 16 fit parameters used to model an eccentric binary is in Section 2.5.

The second is stellar atmosphere modeling with MOOG (Snedden 1973), which compares an observed high-resolution stellar spectrum to a grid of models in order to measure a star’s effective temperature T_{eff} , surface gravity $\log g$, and chemical composition or metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. A fourth parameter, microturbulence, must be fit simultaneously as well. This procedure is reviewed in Section 2.4.2.

The final type of model is a stellar evolution model with Models for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics (MESA, Paxton et al. 2011, 2013, 2015), which is introduced in Section 4.2. This is a one-dimensional model of a star that evolves over time given an initial stellar mass and metal mass fraction. It uses adaptive mesh refinement and a suite of tunable physics modules to first form a star on

the pre-main sequence, evolve it onto the main sequence, and continue up the red giant branch and beyond. Snapshots of the interior stellar profile are taken at various points in time, and an evolved star’s age can be estimated by determining when the MESA model star reaches its present-day radius.

1.5. Thesis Goals and Format

The aim of this dissertation is to use the observations and methods above to address three main science Questions:

1. What is the relationship between stellar activity and solar-like oscillations, and what causes red giants to oscillate with low amplitude or not at all?
2. How does a star’s evolutionary history in the context of a binary affect present-day oscillation activity?
3. Do masses and radii from RG/EB orbital solutions agree with those derived from asteroseismology?

This Chapter has reviewed how binary stars are excellent tools for directly measuring stellar properties and discussed how ensemble asteroseismology can use light curves alone to characterize large numbers of oscillating stars quickly. It has also motivated the need for detailed studies of RG/EBs to both test the asteroseismic scaling relations and investigate what physical situations can affect the presence of solar-like oscillations.

In Chapter 2, we take a close look at a double red giant eclipsing binary, KIC 9246715, which is a representative future state for RG/EBs with a main sequence component. This system is especially worthy of study because the stars

are nearly twins, yet we see only one main set of solar-like oscillations, and the modes are wider and weaker than typical. Chapter 2 also appears in *The Astrophysical Journal* as Rawls et al. (2016), and it encompasses work contributed by several co-authors but ultimately synthesized and written by the lead author. In Chapter 2, we identify signatures of magnetic activity, use a stellar evolution model to calculate tidal forces in KIC 9246715, and begin to address Questions 1 and 2 above. Because the two stars in this binary are so similar and KIC 9246715 is a single data point, it is difficult to use it to precisely address Question 3.

In Chapters 3 and 4, we use the methods established in Chapter 2 to study seven additional RG/EBs. Each of these has a main sequence companion and together they are a representative subset of the full RG/EB sample presented in Gaulme et al. (2013, 2014). Chapter 3 presents dynamic binary models of each system and uses the oscillating giants to test the asteroseismic scaling relations. This directly addresses Question 3. Chapter 4 uses the results from Chapter 3 to search for magnetic activity and explore stellar evolution models. Together, the full subset of well-characterized RG/EBs addresses all three questions much more thoroughly than a single star can. Finally, Chapter 5 discusses the context of these binaries in the Milky Way Galaxy, proposes future directions, and summarizes the main results of this dissertation.

2. KIC 9246715: THE DOUBLE RED GIANT ECLIPSING BINARY WITH ODD OSCILLATIONS

2.1. Introduction

Mass and radius are often-elusive stellar properties that are critical to understanding a star’s past, present, and future. Eclipsing binaries are the only astrophysical laboratories that allow for a direct measurement of these and other fundamental physical parameters. Recently, however, observing solar-like oscillations in stars with convective envelopes has opened a window to stellar interiors and provided a new way to measure global stellar properties. A pair of asteroseismic scaling relations use the Sun as a benchmark between these oscillations and a star’s effective temperature to yield mass and radius (Kjeldsen & Bedding 1995; Huber et al. 2010; Mosser et al. 2013).

While both the mass and radius scaling relations are useful, it is important to test their validity. Recent work has investigated the radius relation by comparing the asteroseismic large-frequency separation $\Delta\nu$ and stellar radius between models and simulated data (e.g., Stello et al. 2009; White et al. 2011; Miglio et al. 2013), and by comparing asteroseismic radii with independent radius measurements such as interferometry or binary star modeling (e.g., Huber et al. 2011; Huber et al. 2012; Silva Aguirre et al. 2012). All of these find that radius estimates from asteroseismology are precise within a few percent, with greater scatter for red giants than main sequence stars. The mass scaling relation remains relatively untested. Most studies test the $\Delta\nu$ scaling with average stellar density and not the scaling of ν_{\max} (the asteroseismic frequency of maximum oscillation power) with stellar surface gravity, because the latter has a less-secure theoretical basis (Belkacem et al. 2011). It is not yet possible to reliably predict oscillation mode amplitudes

as a function of frequency (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2012). One study by Frandsen et al. (2013) did test both scaling laws with the red giant eclipsing binary KIC 8410637. They found good agreement between Keplerian and asteroseismic mass and radius, but a more recent analysis from Huber (2014) indicates that the asteroseismic density of KIC 8410637 is underestimated by $\sim 7\%$ (1.8σ , accounting for the density uncertainties), which results in an overestimate of the radius by $\sim 9\%$ (2.7σ) and mass by $\sim 17\%$ (1.9σ). Additional benchmarks for the asteroseismic scaling relations are clearly needed.

Evolved red giants are straightforward to characterize through pressure-mode solar-like oscillations in their convective zones, and red giant asteroseismology is quickly becoming an important tool to study stellar populations throughout the Milky Way (for a review of this topic, see Chaplin & Miglio 2013). Compared to main-sequence stars, red giants oscillate with larger amplitudes and longer periods—several hours to days instead of minutes. Oscillations appear as spikes in the amplitude spectrum of a light curve that is sampled both frequently enough and for a sufficiently long duration. Therefore, observations from the *Kepler* space telescope taken every 29.4 minutes (long-cadence) over many 90 day quarters are ideal for asteroseismic studies of red giant stars.

Kepler's primary science goal is to find Earth-like exoplanets orbiting sun-like stars (Borucki et al. 2010). However, in addition to successes in planet-hunting and suitability for red giant asteroseismology, *Kepler* is also incredibly useful for studies of eclipsing binary stars. *Kepler* has discovered numerous long-period eclipsing systems from consistent target monitoring over several years (Prša et al. 2011; Slawson et al. 2011). Eclipsing binaries are important tools for understanding fundamental stellar properties, testing stellar evolutionary models, and

determining distances. When radial velocity curves exist for both stars in an eclipsing binary, along with a well-sampled light curve, the inclination is precisely constrained and a full orbital solution with masses and radii can be found. Kepler’s third law applied in this way is the *only* direct method for measuring stellar masses.

Taken together, red giants in eclipsing binaries (hereafter RG/EBs) that exhibit solar-like oscillations are ideal testbeds for asteroseismology. There are presently 18 known RG/EBs that show solar-like oscillations (Hekker et al. 2010; Gaulme et al. 2013, 2014; Beck et al. 2014; Beck et al. 2015) with orbital periods ranging from 19 to 1058 days, all in the *Kepler* field of view.

In this Chapter, we present physical parameters for the unique RG/EB KIC 9246715 with a combination of dynamical modeling, stellar atmosphere modeling, and asteroseismology. KIC 9246715 contains two nearly-identical red giants in a 171 day eccentric orbit with a single main set of solar-like oscillations. A second set of oscillations, potentially attributable to the other star, is marginally detected. The system’s derived physical parameters are in agreement with Helminiak et al. (2015), which was prepared simultaneously and independently. In Section 2.2, we describe how we acquire and process photometric and spectroscopic data, and Section 2.3 explains our radial velocity extraction process. In Section 2.4, we disentangle each star’s contribution to the spectra to perform stellar atmosphere modeling. We then present our final orbital solution and physical parameters for KIC 9246715 in Section 2.5. Finally, Section 2.6 compares our results with global asteroseismology and discusses the connection among solar-like oscillations, stellar evolution, and effects such as star spots and tidal forces, as well as implications for future RG/EB studies.

2.2. Observations

2.2.1. Kepler Light Curves

Our light curves are from the *Kepler* Space Telescope in long-cadence mode (one data point every 29.4 minutes), and span 17 quarters—roughly four years—with only occasional gaps. These light curves are well-suited for red giant asteroseismology, as main sequence stars with convective envelopes oscillate too rapidly to be measured with *Kepler* long-cadence data.

When studying long-period eclipsing binaries, it is important to remove instrumental effects in the light curve while preserving the astrophysically interesting signal. In this work, we prioritize preserving eclipses. Our detrending algorithm uses the simple aperture photometry (SAP) long-cadence *Kepler* data for quarters 0–17. First, any observations with NaNs are removed, and observations from different quarters are put onto the same median level so that the eclipses line up. The out-of-eclipse portions of the light curve are flattened, which removes any out-of-eclipse variability. For eclipse modeling, we use only the portions of the light curve that lie within one eclipse duration of the start and end of each eclipse. This differs from the light curve processing needed for asteroseismology, which typically “fills” the eclipses to minimize their effect on the power spectrum (Gaulme et al. 2014).

The processed light curve is presented in Figure 2.1. The top panel shows the entire detrended light curve, while the middle and bottom panels indicate the regions near each eclipse used in this work. We adopt the convention that the “primary” eclipse is the deeper of the two, when Star 1 is eclipsing Star 2. The geometry of the system creates partial eclipses with different depths due to

similarly-sized stars in an eccentric orbit viewed with an inclination less than 90° . For comparison, we present the detrended light curve with eclipses removed in Figure 2.2. The system shows out-of-eclipse photometric modulations on the order of 2%.

2.2.2. *Ground-based Spectroscopy*

We have a total of 25 high-resolution spectra from three spectrographs. At many orbital phases, prominent absorption lines show a clear double-lined signature when inspected by eye. We find that KIC 9246715 is an excellent target for obtaining radial velocity curves for both stars in the binary as the stellar flux ratio is close to unity. A long time span of observations was necessary due to the 171.277 day orbital period and visibility of the *Kepler* field from the observing sites.

2.2.2.1. TRES Echelle From FLWO We obtained 13 high-resolution optical spectra from the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory (FLWO) 1.5-m telescope in Arizona using the Tillinghast Reflector Echelle Spectrograph (TRES) from 2012 March through 2013 April. The wavelength range for TRES is 3900–9100 Å, and the resolution for the medium fiber used is 44,000. The spectra were extracted and blaze-corrected with the pipeline developed by Buchhave et al. (2010).

2.2.2.2. ARCES Echelle From APO We also obtained 10 high-resolution optical spectra from the Apache Point Observatory (APO) 3.5-m telescope in New Mexico using the Astrophysical Research Consortium Echelle Spectrograph (ARCES) from 2012 June through 2013 September. The wavelength range for

Fig. 2.1.— *Kepler* light curve of the eclipsing binary KIC 9246715 with out-of-eclipse points flattened. Top: Detrended SAP flux over 17 quarters. The detrending process is described in Section 2.2.1. Middle: Folded version of the above over one orbit. The dotted lines indicate the portion of the light curve used in subsequent modeling. Bottom: A zoomed view of secondary and primary eclipses corresponding to the dotted lines above. To avoid overlaps, each observed eclipse is offset in magnitude from the previous one. The colored disks illustrate the eclipse configuration, with the red disk representing Star 1 and the yellow disk representing Star 2. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

Fig. 2.2.— *Kepler* light curve of the eclipsing binary KIC 9246715 with eclipses removed, but retaining out-of-eclipse variability. The times of eclipses are indicated with dotted lines. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

ARCES is 3200–10000 Å with no gaps, and the average resolution is 31,000. We reduced the data using standard echelle reduction techniques and Karen Kinemuchi’s ARCES cookbook (private communication).¹

2.2.2.3. APOGEE Spectra From APO We finally obtained two near-IR spectra of KIC 9246715 from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey-III (SDSS-III) Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment (APOGEE) survey (Alam et al. 2015). The wavelength range for APOGEE is 1.5–1.7 μm , with a nominal resolution of 22,500. The pair of spectra were reduced with the standard APOGEE pipeline, but not combined.

2.2.2.4. Global Wavelength Solution Because the observations come from three different spectrographs at two different observatory sites, it is critical to apply a consistent wavelength solution that yields the same radial velocity (RV) zeropoint for all observations. This zeropoint is a function of the atmospheric

¹<http://astronomy.nmsu.edu:8000/apo-wiki/wiki/ARCES> - ARCES Data Reduction Cookbook.

conditions at the observatory and the instrument being used. Typically such a correction can be done with RV standard stars after a wavelength solution has been applied based on ThAr lamp observations. However, we lacked RV standard star observations, and some of the earlier ARCES observations had insufficiently frequent ThAr calibration images to arrive at a reliable wavelength solution. (We subsequently took ThAr images more frequently to address the latter issue.) To arrive at a consistent velocity zeropoint for all spectra, we use TelFit (Gullikson et al. 2014) to generate a telluric line model of the O2 A-band (7595–7638 Å) with $R = 31,000$ at standard temperature and pressure (STP). We then shift the ARCES and TRES spectra in velocity space using the broadening function (BF) technique (see Section 2.3.1) so they all line up with the TelFit model. The shifts range from -0.88 to 2.18 km s^{-1} , with the majority having a magnitude $< 0.3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

2.3. Radial Velocities

2.3.1. The Broadening Function

To extract radial velocities from the spectra, we use the broadening function (BF) technique as outlined by Rucinski (2002). In the simplest terms, the BF is a function that transforms any sharp-line spectrum into a Doppler-broadened spectrum. The BF technique involves solving a convolution equation for the Doppler broadening kernel B , $P(x) = \int B(x')T(x - x')dx'$, where P is an observed spectrum of a binary and T is a spectral template spanning the same wavelength window (Rucinski 2015). In practice, the BF can be used to characterize any deviation of an observed spectrum from an idealized sharp-line spectrum: various forms of line broadening, shifted lines due to Doppler radial velocity shifts, two

sets of lines in the case of a spectroscopic binary, etc. The BF deconvolution is solved with singular value decomposition. This technique is generally preferred over the more familiar cross-correlation function (CCF), because the BF is a true linear deconvolution while the CCF is a non-linear proxy and is less suitable for double-lined spectra. The BF technique normalizes the result so that the velocity integral $\int B(v)dv = 1$ for an exact spectral match of the observed and template spectra. For this analysis, we adapt the IDL routines provided by Rucinski² into python.³

We use a PHOENIX BT-Settl model atmosphere spectrum as a BF template (Allard et al. 2003). This particular model uses Asplund et al. (2009) solar abundance values for a star with $T_{\text{eff}} = 4800$ K, $\log g = 2.5$, and solar metallicity, selected based on revised KIC values for KIC 9246715⁴ (Huber et al. 2014). Since the BF handles line broadening between template and target robustly, we do not adjust the resolution of the template.

Using a model template avoids inconsistencies between the optical and IR regime, additional barycentric corrections, spurious telluric line peaks, and uncertainties from a template star’s systemic RV. In comparison, we test the BF with an observation of Arcturus as a template, and find that using a real star template gives BF peaks that are narrower and have larger amplitudes. These qualities may be essential to measure RVs in the situation where a companion star is extremely faint, because the signal from a faint companion may not appear above the noise

²<http://www.astro.utoronto.ca/~rucinski/SVDcookbook.html>

³<https://github.com/mrawls/BF-rvplotter>

⁴We later confirm that the RV results are indistinguishable from those measured with a more accurate BF model template ($T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ K, $\log g = 3.0$; see Table 2.3).

if the BF peaks are weaker and broader. However, each star contributes roughly equally to the overall spectrum here, so we choose a model atmosphere template for simplicity. The advantages of using a real star spectrum as a BF template instead of a model will likely be crucial for future work, as most other RG/EBs are composed of a bright RG and relatively faint main sequence companion.

For the optical spectra, we consider the wavelength range 5400–6700 Å. This region is chosen because it has a high signal-to-noise ratio and minimal telluric features. For the near-IR APOGEE spectra, we consider the wavelength range 15150–16950 Å. We smooth the BF with a Gaussian to remove un-correlated, small-scale noise below the size of the spectrograph slit, and then fit Gaussian profiles with a least-squares technique to measure the location of the BF peaks in velocity space. The geocentric (uncorrected) results from the BF technique are shown for the optical spectra in Figure 2.3. The results look similar for the near-IR spectra. The final derived radial velocity points with barycentric corrections are presented in Table 2.1 and Figure 2.4. The radial velocities vary from about -50 to 40 km s^{-1} , with uncertainties on the order of 0.2 km s^{-1} . Uncertainties are assigned based on the error in position from the least-squares best-fit Gaussian to each BF peak.

2.3.2. Comparison With TODCOR

To confirm that the BF-extracted radial velocities are accurate, we also use TODCOR (Zucker & Mazeh 1994) to extract radial velocities for the TRES spectra. TODCOR, which stands for two-dimensional cross-correlation, uses a template spectrum from a library with a narrow spectral range (5050–5350 Å) to

Fig. 2.3.— Radial velocities extracted for 23 ARCES and TRES observations of KIC 9246715 with the broadening function (BF) technique. Each panel represents one spectral observation, ordered chronologically, for which the BF convolution of the target star with a template PHOENIX model spectrum is shown in black. To identify the location of each BF in radial velocity space, we fit a pair of Gaussians, which are plotted in red. The date of observation, orbital phase, and instrument used are printed in the upper corners of each panel. Barycentric corrections have not yet been applied to these velocities. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

Table 2.1. Radial velocities for KIC 9246715 extracted from spectra with the broadening function technique

UTC Date	Midpoint ^a	Phase	v_1 (km s ⁻¹)	v_2 (km s ⁻¹)	Inst ^b
2012 Mar 01	5988.047280	0.773	20.72(14)	-29.88(14)	T
2012 Mar 11	5998.009344	0.831	34.91(14)	-44.26(14)	T
2012 Apr 02	6020.026793	0.960	20.25(15)	-29.77(15)	T
2012 May 08	6055.977358	0.170	-22.49(14)	13.69(14)	T
2012 May 26	6073.937068	0.275	-26.35(14)	17.53(14)	T
2012 Jun 02	6080.976302	0.316	-26.37(14)	17.64(14)	T
2012 Jun 12	6090.904683	0.374	-25.55(15)	16.67(15)	A
2012 Jun 27	6105.752943	0.460	-22.83(15)	12.51(15)	A
2012 Jun 30	6108.894850	0.479	-21.01(14)	12.20(14)	T
2012 Jul 24	6132.758456	0.618	-8.72(31)	-0.55(32)	T
2012 Aug 26	6165.786902	0.811	29.96(15)	-39.77(15)	A
2012 Aug 26	6165.947831	0.812	28.86(15)	-41.26(15)	A
2012 Aug 27	6166.889910	0.817	33.01(15)	-39.84(15)	A
2012 Sep 04	6174.917425	0.864	40.45(15)	-48.07(15)	A
2012 Sep 05	6175.777945	0.869	39.85(14)	-49.22(14)	T
2012 Sep 30	6200.689766	0.015	2.35(18)	-11.53(20)	T
2012 Oct 24	6224.736100	0.155	-21.22(14)	12.80(14)	T
2012 Nov 21	6252.572982	0.318	-26.39(14)	17.67(14)	T
2013 Apr 02	6384.991673	0.091	-14.11(15)	5.13(14)	T
2013 Apr 20	6402.975545	0.196	-23.98(15)	15.28(15)	A
2013 Jun 13	6456.959033	0.511	-17.91(14)	11.00(15)	A
2013 Sep 02	6537.599166	0.982	12.23(15)	-22.55(15)	A
2013 Sep 09	6544.591214	0.022	-0.18(25)	-9.94(26)	A
2014 Apr 23	6770.897695	0.344	-25.70(15)	17.52(15)	E
2014 May 17	6794.863326	0.484	-20.44(15)	11.92(15)	E

^aExposure midpoint timestamp, (BJD-2450000)

^bT = TRES, A = ARCES, E = APOGEE

Fig. 2.4.— Radial velocity curves for both stars in KIC 9246715. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time, with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curve over one orbit. Symbol shape indicates which spectrograph took each observation. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

make a two-component radial velocity curve for spectroscopic binaries. It is commonly used with TRES spectra for eclipsing binary studies. From the radial velocity curve, TODCOR subsequently calculates an orbital solution. We use the full TODCOR RV extractor + orbital solution calculator for the TRES spectra, and compare this with the TODCOR orbital solution calculator for the combined ARCES, TRES, and APOGEE RV points which were extracted with the BF technique. We find that the two orbital solutions are in excellent agreement. The TODCOR RVs (available for TRES spectra only) are on average $0.22 \pm 0.25 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ systematically lower than the BF RVs, which we attribute to a physically unimportant difference in RV zeropoint.

2.4. Stellar Atmosphere Model

2.4.1. Spectral Disentangling

Before the two stars' atmospheres can be modeled, it is necessary to extract each star's spectrum from the observed binary spectra. While the location of a set of absorption lines in wavelength space is the only requirement for radial velocity studies, using an atmosphere model to measure T_{eff} , $\log g$, and metallicity [Fe/H] for each star requires precise equivalent widths of particular absorption lines.

To this end, we use the FDBinary tool (Ilijć et al. 2004) on the spectral window 4900–7130 Å to perform spectral decomposition. Following the approach in Beck et al. (2014), we break the window into 222 pieces that each span about 10 Å. FDBinary does not require a template, and instead uses the orbital parameters of a binary to separate a set of double-lined spectral observations in Fourier space. We test FDBinary's capabilities by creating a set of simulated double-lined spectra

from a weighted sum of two identical spectra of Arcturus. When the orbital solution and flux ratio is correctly specified, the program returns a pair of single-lined spectra that are indistinguishable from the original.

FDBinary requires a set of double-lined spectral observations re-sampled evenly in $\ln \lambda$. For each input spectrum, it is important to apply barycentric corrections and subtract the binary’s systemic velocity (-4.48 km s^{-1} in this case, see Section 2.5 and Table 2.2). FDBinary further requires six parameters to define the shape of the radial velocity curve: orbital period, time of periastron passage (zeropoint), eccentricity, longitude of periastron, and amplitudes of each star’s radial velocity curve. We set these to 171.277 days, 319.7 days, 0.35, 17.3° , 33.1 km s^{-1} , and 33.4 km s^{-1} , respectively. While FDBinary does include an optimization algorithm for any subset of these parameters, we use more robust fixed values from a preliminary dynamical model similar to the ones in Section 2.5. Finally, FDBinary requires a light ratio for each observation. Because the two stars are so similar, and none of our spectra were taken during eclipse, we set all light ratios to 1. This is further justified by the nearly-equal amplitude of each star’s broadening function (see Figure 2.3). We tried adjusting the light ratio and found that the result is qualitatively similar, but systematically increases the strength of all features in one spectrum while systematically decreasing the strength of all features in the other.

All 23 optical spectra of KIC 9246715 are processed together in FDBinary, and the result is a pair of disentangled spectra with zero radial velocity. A portion of the resulting individual spectra are shown in Figure 2.5 with a characteristic ARCES spectrum containing signals from both stars for comparison.

Fig. 2.5.— Disentangled spectra from FDBinary for the two stars in KIC 9246715. The y -axis is offset by an arbitrary amount for clarity. For comparison, a typical observation from the ARCES spectrograph taken close to primary eclipse ($\phi = 0.982$) on 2013 September 02 is in black. The zoom panel is a clearer view of individual spectral features, including $H\alpha$, and clearly shows that the observed double-lined spectrum has been decomposed into two single-lined components. The full decomposed spectra span 4900–7130 Å; only a portion is shown here. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

2.4.2. Parameters From Atmosphere Modeling

We use the radiative transfer code MOOG (Snedden 1973) to estimate T_{eff} , $\log g$, and metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for the disentangled spectrum of each star in KIC 9246715. First, we use ARES (Automatic Routine for line Equivalent widths in stellar Spectra, Sousa et al. 2007) with a modified FeI and FeII linelist from Tsantaki et al. (2013). ARES automatically measures equivalent widths for spectral lines which can then be used by MOOG. An excellent outline of the process is given by Sousa (2014). We use ARES to identify 66 FeI and 9 FeII lines in the spectrum of Star 1, and 74 FeI and 10 FeII lines in the spectrum of Star 2, all in the 4900–7130 Å region. To arrive at a best-fit plane-parallel stellar atmosphere

model with MOOG, we follow the approach of Magrini et al. (2013). Error bars are determined based on the standard deviation of the derived abundances and the range spanned in excitation potential or equivalent width. For Star 1, we find $T_{\text{eff}} = 4990 \pm 90$ K, $\log g = 3.21 \pm 0.45$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.22 \pm 0.12$, with a microturbulence velocity of 1.86 ± 0.09 km s⁻¹. For Star 2, we find $T_{\text{eff}} = 5030 \pm 80$ K, $\log g = 3.33 \pm 0.37$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.10 \pm 0.09$, with a microturbulence velocity of 1.44 ± 0.09 km s⁻¹.

Projected rotational velocities can also be measured from stellar spectra. To estimate this, we compare the disentangled spectra to a grid of rotationally broadened spectra. We find both stars have $v_{\text{broad}} \simeq 8$ km s⁻¹. It is important to consider that this observed broadening is a combination of each star’s rotational velocity and macroturbulence: $v_{\text{broad}} = v_{\text{rot}} \sin i + \zeta_{\text{RT}}$, where ζ_{RT} is the radial-tangential macroturbulence dispersion (Gray 1978). We note that rotational broadening is Gaussian while broadening due to macroturbulence is cuspier, but these subtle line profile differences are not distinguishable here. Carney et al. (2008) find a large range of macroturbulence dispersions for giant stars which may vary as a function of luminosity, gravity, and temperature, and introduce a non-physically-motivated empirical relation $v_{\text{broad}} = [(v_{\text{rot}} \sin i)^2 + 0.95 \zeta_{\text{RT}}^2]^{1/2}$, while Tayar et al. (2015) estimate the macroturbulence for giant stars to be on order 10% of the observed broadening. In any case, at least some of the observed line broadening is attributable to macroturbulence, and we conclude neither star in KIC 9246715 is a particularly fast rotator.

2.5. Physical Parameters From Light Curve and Radial Velocities

To derive physical and orbital parameters for KIC 9246715, we use the Eclipsing Light Curve (ELC) code (Orosz & Hauschildt 2000). ELC computes model light and velocity curves and uses a Differential Evolution Markov Chain Monte Carlo optimizing algorithm (Ter Braak 2006) to simultaneously solve for a suite of stellar parameters. It is able to consider any set of input constraints simultaneously, i.e., a combination of light curves and radial velocities, and can use a full treatment of Roche geometry (Kopal 1969; Avni & Bahcall 1975). ELC uses a grid of NextGen model atmospheres integrated over the *Kepler* bandpass to assign an intensity at the surface normal of each star. Intensities for the other portions of each star’s visible surface are then computed with a quadratic limb darkening law. By including the temperature of Star 1 as a fit parameter, ELC will try different model atmospheres, thereby indirectly computing stellar temperature. ELC uses χ^2 as a measure of fitness to refine a best-fit model:

$$\begin{aligned} \chi^2 &= \sum_i \frac{(f_{\text{mod}}(\phi_i; \mathbf{a}) - f_{\text{obs}}(\textit{Kepler}))^2}{\sigma_i^2(\textit{Kepler})} \\ &+ \sum_i \frac{(f_{\text{mod}}(\phi_i; \mathbf{a}) - f_{\text{obs}}(\text{RV}_1))^2}{\sigma_i^2(\text{RV}_1)} \\ &+ \sum_i \frac{(f_{\text{mod}}(\phi_i; \mathbf{a}) - f_{\text{obs}}(\text{RV}_2))^2}{\sigma_i^2(\text{RV}_2)}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

where $f_{\text{mod}}(\phi_i; \mathbf{a})$ is the ELC model flux at a given phase ϕ_i for a set of parameters \mathbf{a} , f_{obs} is the observed value at the same phase, and σ_i is the associated uncertainty.

We compute two sets of ELC models: the first uses all eclipses from the light curve together with all radial velocity points, and the second breaks the light

curves into segments to investigate how photometric variations from one orbit to another affect the results. Both sets of models employ ELC’s “fast analytic mode.” This uses the equations in Mandel & Agol (2002) to treat both stars as spheres, which is reasonable for a well-detached binary like KIC 9246715 ($R/a < 0.04$ for both stars). The results from both sets of models are presented in Table 2.2. We adopt the “All-eclipse model” as the accepted solution, for reasons described below.

2.5.1. All-eclipse ELC Model

We use ELC to compute more than 2 million models which fit 16 parameters: orbital period P_{orb} , zeropoint T_{conj} (this sets the primary eclipse to orbital phase $\phi_{ELC} = 0.5$ instead of $\phi = 0$), orbital inclination i , $e \sin \omega$ and $e \cos \omega$ (where e is eccentricity and ω is the longitude of periastron), the temperature of the primary star T_1 , the mass of the primary star M_1 , the amplitude of the primary star’s radial velocity curve K_1 , the fractional radii of each star R_1/a and R_2/a , the temperature ratio T_2/T_1 , the *Kepler* contamination factor, and stellar limb darkening parameters for the triangular limb darkening law (Kipping 2013). The scale of the system (and hence the component masses and radii) is uniquely determined given the primary star mass, the amplitude of its radial velocity curve, and the orbital period. Error bars are determined from the cumulative distribution frequency of each fit parameter after the first 10,000 models are excluded to allow for an appropriate MCMC burn-in period. Quoted values are 50% of the cumulative distribution function with the one-sigma upper error at 84.25% and one-sigma lower error at 15.75%. The results are in Figure 2.6 and Table 2.2.

Fig. 2.6.— ELC model for all eclipses of KIC 9246715 taken together. The top two panels show the folded radial velocities, while the middle two panels show the folded light curve. A single full orbit is shown. The bottom four panels are a zoom of each eclipse. Residuals are indicated by a Δ symbol. Red and yellow points are observations and the black line is the all-eclipse ELC model fit. The primary and secondary eclipses are the same configurations as illustrated in Figure 2.1. While one primary eclipse epoch suffers from increased contamination due to a nearby star (see Section 2.5.2), the overall scatter in the eclipse residuals is greater during primary eclipse than during secondary eclipse. This suggests Star 1 is more active than Star 2, and is discussed further in Section 2.6.3. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

Table 2.2. Physical parameters of KIC 9246715 from ELC modeling

Parameter	All-eclipse Model	LC segment rms	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	171.27688 ± 0.00001	171.276 ± 0.001	
T_{conj} [day]	337.51644 ± 0.00005	337.519 ± 0.002	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$87.051^{+0.009}_{-0.003}$	87.08 ± 0.03	
e	$0.3559^{+0.0002}_{-0.0003}$	0.355 ± 0.001	
ω [deg]	$18.4^{+0.1}_{-0.2}$	17.7 ± 0.7	
$e \cos \omega$	$0.33773^{+0.00005}_{-0.00003}$	0.3379 ± 0.0001	
$e \sin \omega$	$0.1123^{+0.0007}_{-0.0012}$	0.108 ± 0.004	
T_2/T_1	$1.001^{+0.001}_{-0.002}$	0.993 ± 0.008	
a [R_{\odot}]	$211.3^{+0.2}_{-0.3}$	211.0 ± 0.3	
contam	$0.002^{+0.004}_{-0.001}$	0.02 ± 0.01	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s $^{-1}$]	-4.4779 ± 0.002	-4.4797 ± 0.0007	systemic velocity ^a
Star 1			
M [M_{\odot}]	$2.171^{+0.006}_{-0.008}$	2.162 ± 0.008	
R [R_{\odot}]	$8.37^{+0.03}_{-0.07}$	8.27 ± 0.09	
R/a	$0.0396^{+0.0001}_{-0.0003}$	0.0392 ± 0.0004	
T [K]	4930^{+140}_{-230}	...	
K [km s $^{-1}$]	$33.19^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$	33.13 ± 0.06	
$\log g$ [cgs]	$2.929^{+0.007}_{-0.003}$	2.938 ± 0.008	
q_1	$0.66^{+0.02}_{-0.04}$	0.72 ± 0.02	triangular limb darkening ^b
q_2	$0.25^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	0.31 ± 0.02	triangular limb darkening ^b
Star 2			
M [M_{\odot}]	$2.149^{+0.006}_{-0.008}$	2.140 ± 0.008	
R [R_{\odot}]	$8.30^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	8.29 ± 0.01	
R/a	0.0393 ± 0.0001	0.03928 ± 0.00002	
T [K]	4930^{+140}_{-230}	...	
K [km s $^{-1}$]	$33.53^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$	33.47 ± 0.06	
$\log g$ [cgs]	$2.932^{+0.003}_{-0.004}$	2.9315 ± 0.0005	
q_1	$0.55^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$	0.52 ± 0.05	triangular limb darkening ^b
q_2	0.33 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.02	triangular limb darkening ^b

^aThe uncertainties reported for γ_{vel} are based on the internal consistency of the model using relative velocities. The true error is on the order of 0.2–0.3 km s $^{-1}$ (Section 2.3.2).

^bThe triangular limb darkening law (Kipping 2013) re-parameterizes the quadratic limb darkening law, $I(\mu)/I(1) = 1 - u_1(1 - \mu) - u_2(1 - \mu)^2$, with new coefficients $q_1 \equiv (u_1 + u_2)^2$ and $q_2 \equiv 0.5u_1(u_1 + u_2)^{-1}$.

2.5.2. Light Curve Segment ELC Models

To investigate secular changes in KIC 9246715, we split the *Kepler* light curve into seven segments such that each contains one primary and one secondary eclipse. This is particularly motivated by the photometric variability seen in Figure 2.2 and the residuals of the primary eclipse in the all-eclipse model, as shown in Figure 2.6. Of all the observed primary eclipses, the one in the seventh light curve segment is slightly shallower than the others by about 0.004 magnitudes. To learn why, we examine the *Kepler* Target Pixel Files, which reveal the aperture used for KIC 9246715 includes a larger portion of a nearby contaminating star every fourth quarter. This higher contamination is coincident with the secondary eclipse in the fifth light curve segment and both eclipses in the seventh light curve segment. Higher contamination results in shallower eclipses because there is an overall increase in flux, and we conclude that the shallower primary eclipse is a result of this contamination rather than a star spot or other astrophysical signal.

We therefore calculate a second set of parameters based on the root-mean-square (rms) of six ELC models, one for each light curve segment, excluding the seventh segment which has significantly higher contamination in both eclipses. Each segment still includes the full set of radial velocity data. The values reported are the rms of these seven models, $a_{\text{rms}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i^2)}$, plus or minus the rms error, $\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - a_{\text{rms}})^2}$. These are reported in Table 2.2. Temperature is not reported because the white-light *Kepler* bandpass is not well-suited to constrain stellar temperatures, and the rms errors among the light curve segments are artificially small.

For all parameters, the all-eclipse model and the LC segment model agree within 2σ . We note that ω , the *Kepler* contamination, and R_1 all have significantly larger uncertainties in the LC segment results than the all-eclipse results. This reflects an inherent degeneracy between viewing angle and stellar radius in a binary with grazing eclipses, which is exacerbated by uncertainties in limb darkening and temperature, as well as varying contamination between quarters. When we hold both stars' limb darkening coefficients fixed with theoretical values $q_1 = 0.49$ and $q_2 = 0.37$ (Claret et al. 2013), we find an ELC solution that gives $R_1 \simeq 7.9 R_\odot$, $R_2 \simeq 8.2 R_\odot$, $\omega \simeq 17.4^\circ$, and contamination as high as 5%. However, this solution has a higher χ^2 than the models which allow triangularly sampled quadratic limb darkening coefficients (Kipping 2013) to be free parameters, and it is important to consider that theoretical limb darkening values are poorly constrained for both giant stars and wide bandpasses. We therefore adopt the all-eclipse ELC solution in this work because it has the lowest χ^2 and uses all available data to constrain the system.

2.6. Discussion

2.6.1. Comparison With Asteroseismology

We expect both evolved giants in KIC 9246715 to exhibit solar-like oscillations. These should be observable as pure p-modes for radial oscillations ($\ell = 0$), mixed p- and g- modes for dipolar oscillations ($\ell = 1$), and p-dominated modes for quadrupolar oscillations ($\ell = 2$) in *Kepler* long-cadence data. For solar-like oscillators, the average large frequency separation between consecutive p-modes of the same spherical degree ℓ , $\Delta\nu$, has been shown to scale with the square root of the mean density of the star. The frequency of maximum oscillation power, ν_{\max} ,

carries information about the physical conditions near the stellar surface and is a function of surface gravity and effective temperature (Kjeldsen & Bedding 1995). These scaling relations may be used to estimate a star’s mean density and surface gravity:

$$\frac{\bar{\rho}}{\bar{\rho}_{\odot}} \simeq \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\odot}} \right)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$\frac{g}{g_{\odot}} \simeq \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\odot}} \right) \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff},\odot}} \right)^{-1/2}. \quad (2.3)$$

Equation (2.2) is valid only for oscillation modes of large radial order n , where pressure modes can be mathematically described in the frame of the asymptotic development (Tassoul 1980). Even though red giants do not perfectly match these conditions, because the observed oscillation modes have small radial orders on the order of $n \sim 10$, the scaling relations do appear to work. Quantifying how well they work and in what conditions is more challenging. This is why measuring oscillating stars’ masses and radii independently from seismology is so important.

Surprisingly, when Gaulme et al. (2013, 2014) analyzed the oscillation modes of KIC 9246715 to estimate global asteroseismic parameters, only one set of modes corresponding to a single oscillating star was found. Of the 18 oscillating RG/EBs in the *Kepler* field, KIC 9246715 is the only one with a pair of giant stars (the rest are composed of a giant star and a main sequence star).

In addition, the light curve displays photometric variability as large as 2% peak-to-peak, as shown in Figure 2.2, which is typical of the signal created by

spots on stellar surfaces. The pseudo-period of this variability was observed to be about half the orbital period, which suggests resonances in the system. Gaulme et al. (2014) speculated that star spots may be responsible for inhibiting oscillations on the smaller star, and a similar behavior was observed in other RG/EB systems. In this section, we reestimate the global seismic parameters of the oscillation spectrum that was previously identified (Section 2.6.1.1), analyze the mixed oscillation modes to determine the oscillating star’s evolutionary state (Section 2.6.1.2), investigate which star is more likely to be exhibiting oscillations (Section 2.6.1.3), and address the discrepancy between different surface gravity measurements (Section 2.6.1.4).

2.6.1.1. Global Asteroseismic Parameters of the Oscillating Star We now re-estimate ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ for the oscillation spectrum in the same way as Gaulme et al. (2014), but by using the whole *Kepler* dataset (Q0–Q17). The frequency at maximum amplitude of solar-like oscillations ν_{\max} is measured by fitting the mode envelope with a Gaussian function and the background stellar activity with a sum of two semi-Lorentzians. The large frequency separation $\Delta\nu$ is obtained from the filtered autocorrelation of the time series (Mosser & Apourchaux 2009). Differences with respect to previous estimates are negligible, as we find $\nu_{\max} = 106.4 \pm 0.8$ and $\Delta\nu = 8.31 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{Hz}$. Because the ELC results yield $T_2/T_1 = 0.989$ (Table 2.2) and the stellar atmosphere analysis gives $T_1 = 4990 \pm 90$ K and $T_2 = 5030 \pm 80$ K (Section 2.4.2), we use an effective temperature of $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000 \pm 100$ K in the asteroseismic scaling equations. Assuming a single oscillating star, the mode amplitudes are only $\sim 60\%$ as high as expected ($A_{\max}(\ell = 0) \simeq 15$ ppm, and not 6.6 ppm as erroneously reported by Gaulme et al.

2014) when compared to the ~ 24 ppm predicted from mode amplitude scaling relations (Corsaro et al. 2013). The modes are four times wider than expected as well, with $\ell = 0$ linewidths $\simeq 0.4 \mu\text{Hz}$ near ν_{max} rather than a value closer to $0.1 \mu\text{Hz}$ as predicted for stars with similar ν_{max} , $\Delta\nu$, and T_{eff} (Corsaro et al. 2015).

To determine mass, radius, surface gravity, and mean density, we use the scaling relations after correcting $\Delta\nu$ for the red giant regime (Mosser et al. 2013).⁵ In essence, instead of directly plugging the observed $\Delta\nu_{\text{obs}}$ into Equations 2.2 and 2.3, we estimate the asymptotic large spacing via $\Delta\nu_{\text{as}} = \Delta\nu_{\text{obs}}(1 + \zeta)$, where $\zeta = 0.038$. With this correction of the large spacing, we obtain $M = 2.17 \pm 0.14 M_{\odot}$ and $R = 8.26 \pm 0.18 R_{\odot}$. In terms of mean density and surface gravity, which independently test the $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{max} relations, respectively, we find $\bar{\rho}/\bar{\rho}_{\odot} = (3.86 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-3}$ and $\log g = 2.942 \pm 0.008$. A comparison of key parameters determined from all our different modeling techniques is in Table 2.3.

2.6.1.2. Mixed Oscillation Modes Based on the distribution of mixed $\ell = 1$ modes, Gaulme et al. (2014) reported that the oscillation pattern period spacing was typical of that of a star from the secondary red clump, i.e., a core-He-burning star that has not experienced a helium flash. This was based on a dipole gravity mode period spacing of $\Delta\Pi_1 \simeq 150$ s. Red giant branch (RGB) stars have smaller period spacings than red clump stars, and ($\Delta\Pi_1 = 150$ s, $\Delta\nu = 8.31 \mu\text{Hz}$) puts the oscillating star on the very edge of the asteroseismic parameter space that defines the secondary red clump (Mosser et al. 2014). Due to noise and damped

⁵Other scaling relation applications, such as Chaplin et al. (2011) and Kallinger et al. (2010), assume the observed $\Delta\nu$ is equal to the asymptotic $\Delta\nu$. Mosser et al. (2013) uses a correction factor to account for the fact that oscillating red giants are not in the asymptotic regime, which we apply here.

Table 2.3. Physical parameter comparisons for KIC 9246715 with different modeling techniques

Model	Mass (M_{\odot})	Radius (R_{\odot})	$\log g$ (cgs)	$\bar{\rho}$ ($\bar{\rho}_{\odot} \times 10^{-3}$)	T_{eff} (K)
ELC (Light Curve + RV), Star 1	$2.171^{+0.006}_{-0.008}$	$8.37^{+0.03}_{-0.07}$	$2.929^{+0.007}_{-0.003}$	$3.70^{+0.10}_{-0.04}$	4930^{+140}_{-230}
ELC (Light Curve + RV), Star 2	$2.149^{+0.006}_{-0.008}$	$8.30^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	$2.932^{+0.003}_{-0.004}$	$3.76^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$	4930^{+140}_{-230}
MOOG Stellar Atmosphere, Star 1	3.21 ± 0.45	...	4990 ± 90
MOOG Stellar Atmosphere, Star 2	3.33 ± 0.37	...	5030 ± 80
Global Asteroseismology, Star 1 ^a	4.14 ± 0.02	...
Global Asteroseismology, Star 2 ^a	2.17 ± 0.14	8.26 ± 0.18	2.942 ± 0.008	3.86 ± 0.02	^b

^aAs discussed in Sections 2.6.1.3 and 2.6.2, we tentatively assign Star 2 to the main set of oscillations and Star 1 to the marginally detected oscillations.

^bA fixed temperature of 5000 ± 100 K was assumed to calculate the other asteroseismic parameters.

oscillations, it is difficult to unambiguously determine the mixed mode pattern described by Mosser et al. (2012). To more accurately assess the evolutionary stage of the oscillating star in KIC 9246715, we employ three different techniques to identify and characterize mixed modes.

First, we perform a Bayesian fit to the individual oscillation modes of the star using the DIAMONDS code (Corsaro & De Ridder 2014) and the methodology for the peak bagging analysis of a red giant star in Corsaro et al. (2015). We then compare the set of the obtained frequencies of mixed dipole modes with those from the asymptotic relation proposed by Mosser et al. (2012), which we compute using different values of $\Delta\Pi_1$. The result shows a significantly better match when values of $\Delta\Pi_1$ around 200 s are used. This confirms that the oscillating star is settled on the core-He-burning phase of stellar evolution. The results of the DIAMONDS fit are in Appendix C.

Second, we search for stars with a power density spectrum that resembles the oscillation spectrum of KIC 9246715. As shown in Figure 2.7, a good match is found with the star KIC 11725564, which exhibits very similar radial and quadrupole modes as well as the mixed mode pattern. To find this “twin,” we calculate the autocorrelation of the KIC 9246715 oscillation spectrum, pre-whiten its radial and quadrupole modes, and convert it into period. We find a weak, broad peak at about $\Delta P_{\text{obs}} = 80$ s. A similar result of $\Delta P_{\text{obs}} = 87$ s is found for KIC 11725564, with a notably cleaner signal thanks to higher mode amplitudes. This corresponds to the observed period spacing as defined by Bedding et al. (2011) and Mosser et al. (2011), and indicates that the star is indeed likely to be a secondary clump star.

Finally, we measure the asymptotic period spacing with the new method developed by Mosser et al. (2015). The signature $\Delta\Pi_1 = 150.4 \pm 1.4$ s is very clear, despite binarity. In fact, the presence of a second oscillation spectrum cannot mimic a mixed-mode pattern because its global amplitude is too small for us to observe a mode disturbance. Only one signature of an oscillating star is visible in a period spacing diagram.

We conclude that the mixed oscillation modes in KIC 9246715 are indicative of a secondary red clump star. This result is supported statistically by Miglio et al. (2014), who report it is more likely to find red clump stars than red giant branch stars in asteroseismic binaries in *Kepler* data. This is largely due to the fact that evolved stars spend more time on the horizontal branch than the red giant branch. Due to the large noise level of the mixed modes, we are unable to measure a core rotation rate in the manner of Beck et al. (2012) and Mosser et al. (2012). However, the mixed modes appear to be doublets which support an inclination near 90° .

2.6.1.3. Identifying the Oscillating Star The asteroseismic mass and radius are consistent with those from the ELC model for both stars. The surface gravity of the two stars from ELC are nearly identical, and both agree with the asteroseismic value. While neither star’s mean density agrees with the asteroseismic value, Star 2 is slightly closer than Star 1. Since one of the scaling equations gives mean density independent of temperature and ν_{\max} (Equation (2.2)), one might naïvely expect a better asteroseismic estimation of density compared to surface gravity. It is therefore important to consider the temperature dependence of Equation (2.3). From Gaulme et al. (2013, 2014), and the present work, as-

Fig. 2.7.— Power density spectrum of KIC 11725564 (gray), a seismic “twin” of KIC 9246715 (red). Both power spectra are smoothed with a boxcar of $1/50$ of the large separation. The modes in KIC 11725564, a secondary red clump star, have $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{\max} which very nearly match KIC 9246715. They are less noisy and have larger amplitudes than the modes in KIC 9246715, making this star a useful asteroseismic comparison. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

teroseismic masses and radii were reported to be $(1.7 \pm 0.3 M_{\odot}, 7.7 \pm 0.4 R_{\odot})$, $(2.06 \pm 0.13 M_{\odot}, 8.10 \pm 0.18 R_{\odot})$, and $(2.17 \pm 0.14 M_{\odot}, 8.26 \pm 0.18 R_{\odot})$, respectively. Among these, ν_{\max} does not vary much (102.2, 106.4, 106.4 μHz), and $\Delta\nu$ varies even less (8.3, 8.32, 8.31 μHz), while the assumed temperatures were 4699 K (from the KIC), 4857 K (from Huber et al. 2014), and 5000 K (this work). Even if temperature is the least influential parameter in the asteroseismic scalings, we are at a level of precision where errors on temperature dominate the global asteroseismic results. In this case, while Star 2 appears to be a better candidate for the main oscillator at a glance, scaling relations alone cannot be used to prefer one star over the other. However, in Section 2.6.3 we demonstrate that Star 2 is likely less active than Star 1. Based on this, we tentatively assign Star 2 as the main oscillator.

2.6.1.4. Surface Gravity Disagreement The asteroseismic $\log g$ measurement nearly agrees with those from ELC, yet all three are some 0.3 dex lower than the spectroscopic $\log g$ values, as can be seen in Table 2.3. This discrepancy is similar to the difference found for giant stars by Holtzman et al. (2015). They investigate a large sample of stars from the ASPCAP (APOGEE Stellar Parameters and Chemical Abundances Pipeline) which have $\log g$ measured via spectroscopy and asteroseismology. They find that spectroscopic surface gravity measurements are roughly 0.2–0.3 dex too high for core-He-burning (red clump) stars and roughly 0.1–0.2 dex too high for shell-H-burning (RGB) stars. Holtzman et al. (2015) speculate the difference may be partially due to a lack of treatment of stellar rotation, and derive an empirical calibration relation for a “correct” $\log g$ for RGB stars only. However, the stars in KIC 9246715 do not rotate particularly fast ($v_{\text{rot}} \sin i \lesssim 8 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, which includes a contribution from macroturbulence as discussed in Section 2.4.2), so we cannot dismiss this discrepancy so readily.

2.6.2. A Hint of a Second Set of Oscillations

Given that the giants in KIC 9246715 are nearly twins, we test whether it is possible that we see only one set of oscillation modes because both stars are oscillating with virtually identical frequencies. The predicted ν_{max} values for these not-quite-identical stars are $103.4_{-1.1}^{+1.6}$ and $104.1_{-1.2}^{+1.1} \mu\text{Hz}$ for Star 1 and Star 2, respectively (from an inversion of Equations (2.2) and (2.3)), and the predicted $\Delta\nu_{\text{obs}}$ are $8.14_{-0.03}^{+0.06}$ and $8.20_{-0.04}^{+0.03} \mu\text{Hz}$ for Star 1 and Star 2, respectively. As described in Section 2.6.1.1, the intrinsic observed mode linewidths is $0.4 \mu\text{Hz}$, which is about four times wider than expected. To quantify how likely it is for oscillation modes like this to overlap one another, we use the ELC model results

from Section 2.5.1 to calculate distributions of expected $\Delta\nu$ for each star. We find that in 89% of the cases, $|\Delta\nu_1 - \Delta\nu_2| < 0.4 \mu\text{Hz}$. This suggests that, if both stars do indeed exhibit solar-like oscillations, some degree of mode overlap is likely.

Searching for a second set of oscillations is motivated by the broad, mixed-mode-like appearance of the $\ell = 0$ modes in Figure 2.8, where mixed modes are not physically possible, and by the faint diagonal structure mostly present on the upper left side of the $\ell = 1$ mode ridge. Even though oscillation modes from the two stars should not perfectly overlap, modes of degree $\ell = 0, 1$ of one star can almost overlap modes of degree $\ell = 1, 0$ of the other star.

The universal red giant oscillation pattern (Mosser et al. 2011) yields $\Delta\nu = 8.31 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{Hz}$ for this system (Section 2.6.1.1). However, it appears that the asymptotic relations for pressure-modes and mixed modes from the main oscillating star alone may not reproduce the position of all the peaks in the power spectrum. We therefore test the hypothesis of a binary companion. The universal oscillation pattern allows us to tentatively allocate the extra peaks to a pressure-mode oscillation pattern based on $\Delta\nu = 8.60 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{Hz}$.⁶ This putative oscillation spectrum is globally interlaced with the main oscillations, with the dipole modes of one component close to the radial modes of the other component, and vice versa.

This value aligns the diagonal structure seen in the échelle diagram and satisfies the $(\ell = 0, 1 - \ell = 1, 0)$ near-overlap evident in Figure 2.8. However, because these peaks are only marginally detected, ν_{max} cannot be mea-

⁶The quoted uncertainty here is an “internal” error bar which assumes an underlying distribution of modes that corresponds to the red giant universal pattern.

sured. The asteroseismic scaling connecting $\Delta\nu$ with the mean density yields $\bar{\rho}/\bar{\rho}_{\odot} = (4.14 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-3}$. This density is larger than we expect; in fact, we expect Star 1 to be less dense than Star 2, the suspected main oscillator. This casts further doubt on the second set of oscillations, and it may be a spurious detection.

Finally, we investigate whether the modes show any frequency modulation as a function of orbital phase by examining portions of the power spectrum spanning less than the orbital period. However, the solar-like oscillations modes are short-lived (about 23 days from an average $0.5 \mu\text{Hz}$ width of $l = 0$ modes), so it is difficult to clearly resolve Doppler-shifted modes in a power spectrum of a light curve segment. At $\nu_{\text{max}} = 106 \mu\text{Hz}$, the maximum frequency shift expected from a 60 km s^{-1} difference in radial velocity is $0.02 \mu\text{Hz}$. This is less than the intrinsic mode line width, and therefore not observable.

2.6.3. Signatures of Stellar Activity

KIC 9246715 is an interesting pair of well-separated red giants that exhibit photometric variations from stellar activity, weak or absent solar-like oscillations, and a notably eccentric orbit. In this and the following section, we discuss how stellar activity and tidal forces have acted over the binary’s lifetime to arrive at the system we see today. The first confirmed case of activity and/or tides suppressing convection-driven oscillations was Derekas et al. (2011), and as Gaulme et al. (2014) showed, stellar activity and tides likely play an important role in many RG/EBs.

Fig. 2.8.— Échelle diagram of KIC 9246715’s power density spectrum. Darker regions correspond to larger peaks in power density. The power density spectrum is smoothed by a boxcar over seven bins and cut into 8.31- μ Hz chunks; each is then stacked on top of its lower-frequency neighbor. This representation allows for visual identification of the modes. Lines are plotted to guide the eye toward a theoretical mode distribution according to the red giant universal pattern (Mosser et al. 2011). It illustrates how we expect the modes to appear, but is not the result of a fit. Solid blue and dashed red lines are associated with the main (nominally Star 2) and marginally-detected (nominally Star 1) oscillations, respectively. The variable ℓ labels each mode by its spherical degree. Large spacing is $\Delta\nu = 8.31 \mu\text{Hz}$ for the main (blue) lines and $8.60 \mu\text{Hz}$ for the marginal (red) lines (see Section 2.6.2). Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

In this system, the light curve residuals discussed in Section 2.5.2 and Figure 2.6 show significant scatter during both eclipses, and especially primary eclipse (when Star 1 is in front). This means at least Star 1 is magnetically active, and activity in the system is further supported by photometric variability of up to 2% on a timescale approximately equal to half the orbital period (Gaulme et al. 2014). A magnetically active Star 1 is also consistent with Star 2 as the suspected main oscillator, because strong magnetic fields may be responsible for damping solar-like oscillations, as described in Fuller et al. (2015).

Figures 2.9 and 2.10 investigate whether magnetic activity has any appreciable effect on absorption lines in either star. Following the approach of Fröhlich et al. (2012), we plot each target spectrum (solid colored line) on top of a model (dotted line), and show the difference below (solid black line). The model spectrum is a PHOENIX BT-Settl stellar atmosphere like the one described in Section 2.3.1 (Allard et al. 2003; Asplund et al. 2009), with $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ and $\log g = 3.0$. It has been convolved to a lower resolution much closer to that of the ARCES and TRES spectrographs.

We examine a selection of the strongest Fe I lines which fall in the disentangled wavelength region and are either prone to Zeeman splitting in the presence of strong magnetic fields (Harvey 1973), or not (Sistla & Harvey 1970). The non-magnetic lines serve as a control. We find none of the six panels of Fe I absorption lines in either star show any significant deviation from the model spectrum. Thus, there is no apparent Zeeman broadening, which is unsurprising for evolved red giants. Magnetic fields must be quite strong to produce this effect. However, the $\text{H}\alpha$ and Ca II absorption lines, which can be indicators of chromospheric activity, are somewhat more interesting. The $\text{H}\alpha$ line appears significantly deeper and

broader than the model in both stars. While net emission is typically associated with activity, Robinson et al. (1990) show several examples of main sequence stars with increased $H\alpha$ absorption due to chromospheric heating, although they caution it is difficult to separate the photospheric and chromospheric contributions to the line. Still, the increased $H\alpha$ absorption equivalent width is slightly more pronounced in Star 1 than Star 2. While this may not be a significant difference on its own, taken together with the increased scatter in the primary eclipse residuals from Figure 2.6, it also suggests Star 1 is the more magnetically active of the pair. It is unclear whether the CaII doublet shows signs of excess broadening or increased equivalent width, but these lines certainly do not have *smaller* equivalent widths than the model.

The overall photometric variability from Figure 2.2 and increased scatter in the primary eclipse residual from Figure 2.6 indicate that both stars are moderately magnetically active, and Star 1 more so than Star 2. This is consistent with increased $H\alpha$ absorption in both stars (and especially Star 1), and supports our suspicion that Star 2 is the main oscillator, and that stellar activity is suppressing solar-like oscillations in Star 1.

2.6.4. *Stellar Evolution and Tidal Forces*

Over the course of KIC 9246715's life, both stars have evolved in tandem to reach the configuration we see today. We quantify this with simple stellar evolution models created using the Modules for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics (MESA) code (Paxton et al. 2011, 2013, 2015). Figure 2.11 presents a suite of models with various initial stellar masses. All the models include overshooting

Fig. 2.9.— *Top of each panel:* observed FDBinary-extracted spectrum of Star 1 (red) together with a stellar template (dotted black line). *Bottom of each panel:* difference between the observed and model spectra. Vertical lines show the position of each absorption line. Broadened magnetic-sensitive lines would indicate Zeeman splitting, but this is not observed. Net emission in the H α and CaII lines is a characteristic signature of chromospheric magnetic activity, but this is not observed either. Instead, the H α line is deeper and broader than the model. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

Fig. 2.10.— The same as in Figure 2.9, but for Star 2 (yellow). No signatures of Zeeman broadening or chromospheric emission are present. The H α absorption is slightly deeper and broader than expected, but not as much as that of Star 1. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

for all the convective zone boundaries with an efficiency of $f = 0.016$ (Herwig 2000), assume no mass loss, and set the mixing-length parameter $\alpha = 2.5$. The standard solar value of $\alpha = 2$ does not allow for sufficiently small stars beyond the RGB. The stage of each model star’s life as it ages in Figure 2.11 is color-coded, and curved lines of constant radii corresponding to $R_1 \pm \sigma_{R_1}$ (gray) and $R_2 \pm \sigma_{R_2}$ (white), within the ranges of $M_1 \pm \sigma_{M_1}$ and $M_2 \pm \sigma_{M_2}$, respectively, are shown. There are two instances in each pair of model stars’ lives when they have the same radii as the stars in KIC 9246715: once on the RGB, and again on the secondary red clump (horizontal branch).

In general, coeval stars on the RGB must have masses within 1% of each other, whereas masses can differ more on the horizontal branch due to its longer evolutionary lifetime. Both model stars in Figure 2.11 can be the same age on the horizontal branch, but not on the RGB. Stars 1 and 2 in Figure 2.11 have RGB ages of $8.13^{+0.08}_{-0.06} \times 10^8$ yr and $8.36^{+0.08}_{-0.06} \times 10^8$ yr, and horizontal branch ages of $9.17 \pm 0.17 \times 10^8$ yr and $9.42^{+0.20}_{-0.13} \times 10^8$ yr, respectively. Without $\alpha > 2$, the MESA model stars on the horizontal branch are always larger than those in KIC 9246715. We consider several ideas as to why the MESA models and the evolutionary stage determined from asteroseismic mixed-mode period spacing may differ:

1. Mass loss: Adding a prescription for RGB mass loss ($\eta = 0.4$, a commonly adopted value of the parameter describing mass-loss efficiency, see Miglio et al. 2012) to the MESA model does not appreciably change stellar radius as a function of evolutionary stage. Even a more extreme mass-loss rate ($\eta = 0.7$) does not significantly affect the radii, essentially because the star is too low-mass to lose much mass.

2. He abundance: Increasing the initial He fraction in the MESA model does not allow for smaller stars in the red clump phase, because shell-H burning is very efficient with additional He present. As a result, the star maintains a high luminosity and therefore a larger radius as it evolves from the tip of the RGB to the red clump.
3. Convective overshoot: The MESA models in this work assume a reasonable overshoot efficiency as described above ($f = 0.016$). We tried varying this from 0–0.03, and can barely make a red clump star as small as $8.3 R_{\odot}$ when $f = 0.01$. With less overshoot, the RGB phase as shown in Figure 2.11 increases in duration, which allows a higher probability for stars of M_1 and M_2 to both be on the RGB.
4. Period spacing: The period spacing $\Delta\Pi_1 = 150$ s may not be measuring what we expect due to rotational splitting of mixed oscillation modes. If the true period spacing is closer to $\Delta\Pi_1 \simeq 80$ s, this would put the oscillating star on the RGB. However, as demonstrated in Section 2.6.1.2, the mixed modes agree with a secondary red clump star. A detailed discussion of rotational splitting in slowly rotating red giants is explored in Goupil et al. (2013).
5. Mixing length: As discussed above, increasing the mixing-length parameter from the standard solar value of $\alpha = 2$ to $\alpha = 2.5$ in the MESA model, which effectively increases the efficiency of convection, produces a red clump star small enough to agree with both measured radii. This is because it reduces the temperature gradient in the near-surface layers, increasing the effective temperature while reducing the radius at constant luminosity. This is what we employ to make horizontal branch stars that agree with R_1 and R_2 .

Fig. 2.11.— Ages for a suite of MESA stellar evolution models for stars of different masses. Color indicates the evolutionary state of a star as it moves from the Main Sequence (MS) \rightarrow Red Giant Branch (RGB) \rightarrow Secondary Red Clump/Horizontal Branch (HB) \rightarrow Asymptotic Giant Branch and beyond (AGB+). Lines of constant radius equal to R_1 and R_2 that fall within the one-sigma errors in mass are shown (gray, $R_1 \pm \sigma_{R_1}$ corresponding to $M_1 \pm \sigma_{M_1}$; white, $R_2 \pm \sigma_{R_2}$ corresponding to $M_2 \pm \sigma_{M_2}$). All models assume a mixing-length parameter of $\alpha = 2.5$. It is possible for both stars in KIC 9246715 to be the same age on the HB, but not on the RGB. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

Beyond a stellar evolution model, it is important to consider how each star has affected the other over time. When the two stars in KIC 9246715 reach the tip of the RGB, they have radii of approximately $25 R_\odot$, which is still significantly smaller than the periastron separation ($r_{\text{peri}} = (1 - e) a = 137 R_\odot$). We never expect the stars to experience a common envelope phase, so this cannot be used to constrain the present evolutionary state.

To estimate how tidal forces change orbital eccentricity, we follow the approach of Verbunt & Phinney (1995). They use a theory of the equilibrium tide first proposed by Zahn (1977) to calculate a timescale for orbit circularization as a star evolves. It is important to note that Verbunt & Phinney (1995) assumed circularization would proceed by a small secondary star (main sequence or white dwarf) imposing an equilibrium tide on a large giant, while the situation with KIC 9246715 is more complicated. For a thorough review of tidal forces in stars, see Ogilvie (2014).

From Equation (2) in Verbunt & Phinney (1995), the timescale τ_c on which orbital circularization occurs is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\tau_c} &\equiv \frac{d \ln e}{dt} \\ &\simeq -1.7 \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{4500 \text{ K}} \right)^{4/3} \left(\frac{M_{\text{env}}}{M_\odot} \right)^{2/3} \\ &\times \frac{M_\odot}{M} \frac{M_2}{M} \frac{M + M_2}{M} \left(\frac{R}{a} \right)^8 \text{ yr}^{-1}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

where M , R , and T_{eff} are the mass, radius, and temperature of a giant star with dissipative tides, M_{env} is the mass of its convective envelope, M_2 is the mass of the companion star, and a is the semi-major axis of the binary orbit.

We integrate this expression over the lifetime of KIC 9246715 to estimate the total expected change in orbital eccentricity, $\Delta \ln e$. We assume a is constant and that there is no mass loss. Because KIC 9246715 is a detached binary, we can separate the integral into a part that is independent of the orbit and a part that must be integrated over time:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln e &= \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{\tau_c(t')} \\ &\simeq -1.7 \times 10^{-5} \left(\frac{M}{M_\odot} \right)^{-11/3} \\ &\times q(1+q)^{-5/3} I(t) \left(\frac{P_{\text{orb}}}{\text{day}} \right)^{-16/3}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

where q is the mass ratio and

$$I(t) \equiv \int_0^t \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}(t')}{4500 \text{ K}} \right)^{4/3} \left(\frac{M_{\text{env}}(t')}{M_\odot} \right)^{2/3} \left(\frac{R(t')}{R_\odot} \right)^8 dt'. \quad (2.6)$$

For the MESA model described above with $M = 2.15 M_\odot$, we compute $\Delta \ln e = -2.3 \times 10^{-5}$ up until $t = 8.3 \times 10^8$ years and $\Delta \ln e = -0.17$ up until $t = 9.4 \times 10^8$ years (the ages corresponding to $R \simeq 8.3 R_\odot$). Rewriting these as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = -4.6$ and $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = -0.77$, which are both less than zero, indicates that the binary has *not* had sufficient time to circularize its orbit, though it is possible the system's initial eccentricity was higher than the $e = 0.35$ we observe today.

The two stars in KIC 9246715 have very similar masses, radii, and temperatures, so this rough calculation is valid both for Star 1 acting on Star 2 and vice versa. Given more time to evolve past the tip of the RGB and well onto the red

clump (with $R \simeq 25 R_{\odot}$ for the second time), $\log[-\Delta \ln e]$ becomes greater than zero and the expectation is a circular orbit. Therefore, the observed eccentricity is consistent with both a RGB star aged approximately 8.3×10^8 years and with a secondary red clump star just past the tip of the RGB aged approximately 9.4×10^8 years.

Tidal forces also tend to synchronize a binary star’s orbit with the stellar rotation period, generally on shorter timescales than required for circularization (Ogilvie 2014). Hints of KIC 9246715’s stellar rotation behavior are present throughout this study: quasi-periodic light curve variability on the order of half the orbital period, residual scatter between light curve observations and the best-fit model during both eclipses, a constraint on $v_{\text{rot}} \sin i$ from spectra, and an asteroseismic period spacing consistent with a red clump star yet not clear enough to measure a robust core rotation rate.

While full tidal circularization has not occurred, it is clear that modest tidal forces have played a role in the evolution of KIC 9246715, and may be linked to the absence or weakness of solar-like oscillations. Future studies of RG/EBs with different evolutionary histories and orbital configurations will help explore this connection further.

2.7. Conclusions

We have characterized the double red giant eclipsing binary KIC 9246715 with a combination of dynamical modeling, stellar atmosphere modeling, and global asteroseismology, and have investigated the roles of magnetic activity, tidal forces, and stellar evolution in creating the system we observe today. KIC 9246715

represents a likely future state of similar-mass RG/EB systems and raises interesting questions about the interactions among stellar activity, tides, and solar-like oscillations.

The two stars in KIC 9246715 are nearly twins ($M_1 = 2.171^{+0.006}_{-0.008} M_\odot$, $M_2 = 2.149^{+0.006}_{-0.008} M_\odot$, $R_1 = 8.37^{+0.03}_{-0.07} R_\odot$, $R_2 = 8.30^{+0.04}_{-0.03} R_\odot$), yet we find only one set of solar-like oscillations strong enough to measure robustly ($M = 2.17 \pm 0.14 M_\odot$, $R = 8.26 \pm 0.18 R_\odot$). The asteroseismic mass and radius agree with both Star 1 and Star 2, as does the surface gravity derived from asteroseismology ($\log g = 2.942 \pm 0.008$; compare with $\log g_1 = 2.929^{+0.007}_{-0.003}$ and $\log g_2 = 2.932^{+0.003}_{-0.004}$). The asteroseismic density, which is not a function of effective temperature, is systematically larger than Star 1 and Star 2, but is a slightly closer match with Star 2 ($\bar{\rho}/\bar{\rho}_\odot = (3.86 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-3}$; compare with $\bar{\rho}_1/\bar{\rho}_\odot = (3.70^{+0.04}_{-0.09}) \times 10^{-3}$ and $\bar{\rho}_2/\bar{\rho}_\odot = (3.76^{+0.06}_{-0.04}) \times 10^{-3}$). As a result, we cannot conclude which star is the source of the main oscillations from asteroseismology alone. However, Star 2 appears to be less active than Star 1, and we therefore tentatively assign the main oscillations to Star 2. The modes are four times wider than expected with amplitudes only $\sim 60\%$ as high as those in red giants with similar global oscillation properties, likely due to a combination of overlapping adjacent modes and magnetic damping. We identify a second set of marginally detectable oscillations potentially attributable to Star 1, for which only $\Delta\nu$ can be estimated, yielding a higher average density than the main oscillation spectrum. This is not consistent with the expected density of Star 1, however, which is less than that of Star 2. These extra modes may represent a spurious detection.

Surface gravities from dynamical modeling and asteroseismology nearly agree, while surface gravities from stellar atmosphere modeling are higher ($\log g_1 =$

3.21 ± 0.45 , $\log g_2 = 3.33 \pm 0.37$). A similar discrepancy has been found between the asteroseismic and spectroscopic surface gravities of other giant stars, but the physical cause is unknown. Radii from stellar evolution models are consistent with a pair of nearly-coeval stars either on the RGB with an age of approximately 8.3×10^8 years, or coeval stars on the horizontal branch with an age of about 9.4×10^8 years. However, the period spacing of mixed oscillation modes clearly indicates that the main oscillator in KIC 9246715 is on the secondary red clump, and we conclude that KIC 9246715 is a pair of secondary red clump stars.

Red giants are ideal tools for probing the Milky Way Galaxy via asteroseismology, so it is crucial that we understand the accuracy and precision of asteroseismically-derived physical parameters. Along the same lines, more than half of cool stars should be in binary or multiple systems, so galactic studies must be done carefully due to external influences of binarity on solar-like oscillations. Detailed studies of the handful of known RG/EBs are crucial to ensure we understand these galactic beacons. Future work will characterize the other known oscillating RG/EBs as well as several non-oscillating RG/EBs. These have the potential to become some of the best-studied stars while simultaneously helping us better understand the structure of the Milky Way.

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3. DYNAMIC MODELING OF RED GIANTS IN ECLIPSING BINARIES WITH MAIN SEQUENCE COMPANIONS

3.1. Introduction

In this dissertation, we study a total of eight RG/EBs. One of these, the double red giant KIC 9246715, has already been extensively discussed in Chapter 2. The other seven systems are, in order from shortest to longest orbital period: KICs 8702921, 9291629, 3955867, 9291629, 10001167, 5786154, 7037405, and 9970396. The orbital periods range from 19 days to 235 days. Key observed properties are in Table 3.1, which includes updated asteroseismic and spectroscopic parameters from Gaulme et al. (2016).

These seven RG/EBs all have main sequence companions and have been selected as a representative and well-observed subset of the stars presented in Gaulme et al. (2013, 2014). More specifically, four of the systems have periods less than 35 days, and three longer than 100 days; two of the systems do not show solar-like oscillations at all, and the rest do; one of the systems is an SB1 and the rest are SB2; all of them have been observed in primary or secondary eclipse with *BVRI* photometry on at least one night (see Section 3.2.2); and all of them have at least 15 high-resolution spectra from ARCES with good orbital phase coverage.

In this Chapter, we present dynamic binary modeling results using the Eclipsing Light Curve routine (ELC, Orosz & Hauschildt 2000) for the seven RG/EBs described above, and we compare the derived masses, radii, densities, and surface gravities to the same from updated asteroseismology (Gaulme et al. 2016). Section 3.2 reviews how we acquire, reduce, and process photometric and spectroscopic data, including the new multi-band photometry. Section 3.3 describes

Table 3.1. RG/EB system overview

KIC	P_{orb} (day)	T_0 (day) ^a	K_p (mag)	ν_{max} (μHz)	$\Delta\nu$ (μHz)	$T_{\text{eff}}^{\text{b}}$ (K)	$\log g^{\text{b}}$ (cgs)	$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]^{\text{b}}$ (dex)
8702921	19.38446(2)	4970.2139(7)	11.980	195.6(5)	14.07(1)	5058(86)	3.26(22)	0.15(5)
9291629	20.686424(3)	4966.8914(1)	13.957	4809*	3.11*	0.08*
3955867	33.65685(2)	4960.8989(3)	13.547	4884(83)	3.23(19)	-0.55(4)
10001167	120.3903(9)	4957.682(9)	10.050	19.90(9)	2.745(5)	4700(66)	2.65(10)	-0.69(4)
9246715 ^c	171.27688(1)	5170.51644(5)	9.266	106.4(8)	8.31(2)	5030(80)	3.33(37)	-0.10(9)
5786154	197.9182(2)	5162.6140(9)	13.534	29.8(2)	3.205(5)	4747(100)	2.65(21)	-0.06(6)
7037405	207.1082(1)	5112.7655(5)	11.875	21.8(1)	2.775(5)	4516(36)	2.46(17)	-0.34(1)
9970396	235.29852(7)	5190.5400(2)	11.447	63.7(2)	6.32(1)	4916(68)	3.14(12)	-0.23(3)

^aThe zero point is set to time of deepest eclipse midpoint (BJD-2450000).

^bDerived from stellar atmosphere modeling of each system's RG (Gaulme et al. 2016), using a process similar to that in Section 2.4.2. Values marked with * are from the revised KIC (Huber et al. 2014) because the spectra were too noisy and/or rotationally broadened for a good result.

^cThe data for KIC 9246715 are from Chapter 2, and the spectroscopic values reported here are for the suspected oscillator (Star 2).

how ELC is used to create dynamic orbital solutions for each binary by combining light curves and radial velocities and presents results for each individual system. Finally, Section 3.4 uses the dynamic masses and radii to test the asteroseismic scaling relations, and Section 3.5 summarizes our results.

3.2. Observations

3.2.1. Kepler Light Curves

As in Chapter 2, the main light curves for analyzing these seven RG/EBs are from *Kepler*. The *Kepler* spacecraft provides light curve data in units of counts, which is then converted into magnitudes, every thirty minutes in long-cadence mode. Once every quarter, the spacecraft rotated by 90° on the sky and a new portion of the detector continued observing the same stars over a four-year period. As a result, discontinuities between quarters must be removed from the light curves, as well as any other instrumental effects. The *Kepler* science team provides two kinds of light curve data: simple aperture photometry (SAP), which adds up the flux in an aperture for each star, and pre-search data conditioning simple aperture photometry (PDCSAP), which is processed with a pipeline specifically tailored for exoplanet transit searches. We begin with the SAP flux and put observations from different quarters onto the same median level. Because all the systems in the RG/EB subset are well-detached binaries, the out-of-eclipse portions are then flattened to remove out-of-eclipse variability.

Overall, this *Kepler* light curve processing preserves the eclipses, removes instrumental effects, and maintains continuity between quarters and gaps. The majority of real (non-instrumental) out-of-eclipse variability in these stars comes

from stellar activity, and detailed star spot evolution modeling over time is beyond the scope of this work. The physical effects of stellar activity on these stars is explored more in Section 4.3. Figure 3.1 shows the full light curve of each RG/EB over four years before flattening, arranged from top to bottom by decreasing orbital period. Stellar variability is especially pronounced in the shorter-period systems. In contrast, the left portion of Figures 3.8, 3.10, 3.12, 3.14, 3.16, 3.18, and 3.20 show each system’s light curve after flattening. In most cases, only the portions of the light curve that lie within one eclipse duration of the start and end of each eclipse are used in dynamic modeling. This is the same method used for KIC 9246715 (see Section 2.2.1). However, in three systems (KICs 9291629, 5786154, and 9970396), the scatter in the light curve was sufficiently large to make a determination of the median out-of-eclipse flux challenging. In those binaries, dynamic modeling proceeded with the entire flattened *Kepler* light curve.

3.2.2. BVRI Photometry

While *Kepler* light curves are excellent in terms of precision, cadence, continuity, and overall length of observation, they are limited to one bandpass. In other words, *Kepler* sees in a single broad swath of reddish-white light. This limits the ability to measure an accurate flux ratio during eclipses to constrain stellar temperatures in an eclipsing binary. The broad *Kepler* bandpass also introduces uncertainty in limb darkening profiles. An illustration of the difference between the *Kepler* bandpass and the Johnson *V* bandpass is in Figure 3.2.

To help constrain stellar properties, we follow the approach of Frandsen et al. (2013) and image several of the RG/EBs over a two-year period in the Johnson

Fig. 3.1.— Unflattened *Kepler* light curves for the RG/EB subset spanning four years. The y -axis is in units of ppm, and star KIC numbers are indicated to the right. Those printed in red and left-aligned lack solar-like oscillations. Adapted from Figure 3 of Gaulme et al. (2014).

Fig. 3.2.— The *Kepler* bandpass (blue) covers a much wider range in wavelength than the Johnson V filter (red), which affects the utility of *Kepler* light curves for measuring eclipse flux ratios to constrain stellar effective temperatures. Figure 1 from Cannizzo et al. (2010).

BVRI filters with the 1 m robotically controlled telescope at Apache Point Observatory (APO).¹ The goal of this observing campaign was to observe as many of the RG/EBs identified in Gaulme et al. (2013) as possible during primary and secondary eclipse, and to obtain out-of-eclipse observations for each system as well in order to measure eclipse depths as a function of color. Most of the RG/EB eclipse durations are a few days. We used orbital periods, zeropoints, eclipse timings, and eclipse durations from the *Kepler* Eclipsing Binary Catalog (Prša et al. 2011; Slawson et al. 2011) to forecast eclipses and prioritize targets. A sample eclipse forecast plot for the full RG/EB sample for 2015 is in Figure 3.3. Exposure times ranged from five seconds to 240 seconds, depending on the brightness of the target.

In the end, we obtained over 3000 *BVRI* images for the RG/EB subset alone. These together with observations of other RG/EB systems are visualized in Figure 3.4, where red and blue circles indicate images taken during an eclipse and gray circles indicate images taken out of eclipse. To create light curves, standard reductions and differential aperture photometry was performed on the images using PyRAF.² First, the flat fields and target images were bias-subtracted using the overscan region. The flats were combined and the target images were each assigned a composite flat field image taken around the same time. Typically, flats were taken on the same night or within one week of a target image. In cases where such a flat wasn't available, the next closest composite flat in time was used. Each target image was then divided by its assigned composite flat field image in the appropriate filter.

¹<http://nmsu1m.apo.nmsu.edu/1m/>

²PyRAF is a product of the STScI, which is operated by AURA for NASA.

Fig. 3.3.— Forecast 2015 eclipses of *Kepler* RG/EBs. Black lines indicate primary eclipses and red lines are secondary eclipses. The vertical blue lines indicate nights in 2015 April and May when multiple eclipses happen simultaneously. Because nights like this are common, the control files for the 1 m telescope had to tell the telescope to prioritize more than one target at a time.

Next, because the 1 m telescope is pointed robotically, the reduced target images were compared to a finding chart. Erroneous pointings, out-of-focus frames, and images taken while the telescope was slewing were deleted. The reduced and visually verified target images were then spatially aligned. Finally, aperture photometry was done for the target star and six comparison stars. Comparison stars were chosen as well-isolated stars with similar brightness to the target that did

Fig. 3.4.— Timeline of RG/EB images taken with the APO 1 m telescope. Red circles indicate primary eclipses, blue circles are secondary eclipses, and gray circles were taken out of eclipse. Filter is not indicated because *BVRI* were continuously cycled from one image to the next.

not appear to be variable. The apparent magnitude of at least four of these were combined into a single reference value, and this was subtracted from the target star apparent magnitude to yield a differential magnitude. Formal rms errors were propagated throughout this process. The differential magnitudes were subsequently binned into one or two points each night, which are shown in Figure 3.5. KIC 7037405 is not shown because no *BVRI* images were taken during eclipse.

We can immediately see that the *BVRI* light curve points have significantly worse phase coverage and precision than their unflattened *Kepler* counterparts. Because these are differential magnitudes, the magnitude of a star in each filter is a function of the comparison stars chosen, and does not provide any information

Fig. 3.5.— Differential *BVRI* light curves for the RG/EB subset. Each panel is folded on its system’s orbital period, and points are color-coded with respect to filter. Blue is the *B* (blue) filter, green is the *V* (visual) filter, red is the *R* (red) filter, and purple is the *I* (near-infrared) filter. KIC 7037405 is excluded because no 1 m images were taken during eclipse. The gray points mark every 100 *Kepler* data points, offset to an arbitrary magnitude for easier comparison.

about its intrinsic color. (This is why some of the *BVRI* light curves are brightest in *I* and dimmest in *B*, and some are the opposite.) Instead, the useful information lies in comparing eclipse depths between filters.

KIC 8702921 is a rather poor target; it has the shallowest eclipses and enough stellar variability to completely drown them out (e.g., compare to the unfolded KIC 8702921 light curve in Figure 3.1). We can tell it experiences relatively consistent brightening across multiple filters prior to primary eclipse, however, which is consistent with tidally-induced phase effects. KIC 9291629 is more variable, but also has much deeper eclipses. As a result, the images taken shortly before secondary eclipse and then during secondary eclipse are useful constraints. KIC

3955867 is extremely variable with relatively shallow eclipses. While we cannot use the *BVRI* observations to robustly measure eclipse depths in this binary, we can tell that the near-resonance between orbital period and differential rotation period has persisted into 2014–2015, after *Kepler* observations ended in 2013. Gaulme et al. (2014) measured a variability period of 33.30 days, which is slightly shorter than the orbital period. This suggests that the system is synchronously rotating (tidally locked) and the delay is a signature of differential rotation. The same effect also appears in the *Kepler* light curve of KIC 9291629.

The three long-period systems with in- and out-of-eclipse *BVRI* observations are KICs 10001167, 5786154, and 9970396. Primary eclipse depths are well constrained for KIC 5786154 and KIC 9970396, both of which have minimal variability. KIC 10001167 has a well-constrained secondary eclipse depth and appears to ramp up in brightness immediately before its primary eclipse, especially in bluer wavelengths. A similar phase effect is also seen in the *Kepler* light curve (e.g., compare to the unfolded KIC 10001167 light curve in Figure 3.1, and see Figure 10 in Gaulme et al. 2014). The shape is consistent with both ellipsoidal brightening due to tidal distortions and the reflection effect.

Unfortunately, none of the stars have *BVRI* observations during both primary and secondary eclipse as well as out of eclipse, so we are unable to use multi-band photometry to quantify light ratios as a function of wavelength as was done for KIC 8410637 in Frandsen et al. (2013). However, the *BVRI* differential magnitudes can still be used to constrain dynamic models with ELC. We do this for KIC 9291629 and KIC 9970396, which are discussed in Sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.7, respectively.

3.2.3. Radial Velocities From Ground-based Spectroscopy

The majority of the spectra used to measure radial velocities are from the Astrophysical Research Consortium Echelle Spectrograph (ARCES) at Apache Point Observatory in Sunspot, New Mexico. They were taken between 2012 May and 2015 November. The wavelength range is 3200–10000 Å with no gaps and a nominal resolution of 31,000, although the best signal-to-noise ratio without excessive telluric absorption is achieved in the 4500–7000 Å window. The spectra are extremely noisy blueward of 4500 Å and there are numerous absorption features from molecules in the Earth’s atmosphere redward of 7000 Å. For each RG/EB, we obtained at minimum 15 spectra at different orbital phases. As in Section 2.2.2.2, the spectra were reduced using standard echelle reduction techniques guided by Karen Kinemuchi’s ARCES cookbook (private communication).³ We followed the same procedure in Section 2.2.2.4 to ensure the velocity zeropoint was consistent over the entire dataset, and used the broadening function (BF) technique in Appendix A to extract radial velocities, which are reported in Table A.1. Most spectra of SB2 binaries yield a velocity point for both the giant star and its main sequence companion, but in some cases there are fewer points for the main sequence star due to BF overlap or noise. The BF peak heights are directly proportional to the stellar light ratio, and the peak corresponding to a dwarf star only $\sim 5\%$ as bright as its neighbor can be difficult to distinguish from a noisy background. As a result, there are larger errors on the velocity location of a Gaussian fit to these peaks.

³<http://astronomy.nmsu.edu:8000/apo-wiki/wiki/ARCES> - ARCES Data Reduction Cookbook.

An additional 25 spectra of KIC 7037405 are from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey-III (SDSS-III) Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment (APOGEE) survey (Alam et al. 2015). The wavelength range is 1.5–1.7 μm , with a nominal resolution of 22,500. These were reduced with the standard APOGEE pipeline, but not combined. The radial velocities were extracted using a technique developed by Suvrath Mahadevan and collaborators (private communication) and are described in detail in McKeever et al. (in prep).

3.3. Physical Parameters From Light Curves and Radial Velocities

Chapter 2 (Rawls et al. 2016) used the Eclipsing Light Curve (ELC) program (Orosz & Hauschildt 2000) with differential evolution Monte Carlo Markov Chain optimizers (DE-MCMC, Ter Braak 2006) to simultaneously fit a combination of light curves and radial velocity observations for KIC 9246715. See Section 2.5.1 for a detailed description of how ELC fits a dynamic model to a set of observations. Here, we use the same method for the remaining seven stars in the RG/EB subset, and consider all the *Kepler* light curve points together with all the radial velocity points simultaneously. Five of the seven systems have red giants that exhibit solar-like oscillations, which are analyzed in Gaulme et al. (2014) and Gaulme et al. (2016) to derive global asteroseismic parameters. Two of the systems, KIC 9291629 and KIC 9970396, are modeled with *BVRI* light curve points taken during or near eclipse in addition to their *Kepler* light curves.

For RG/EBs that are SB2 and therefore have a radial velocity curve for both stars, ELC gives a full dynamic solution from fitting 16 parameters: orbital period P_{orb} , zeropoint T_{conj} , orbital inclination i , $e \cos \omega$, $e \sin \omega$, the temperature of one

star (T_1 or T_2), the mass of one star M_1 , the amplitude of one star’s radial velocity curve K_1 , the fractional radii of each star R_1/a and R_2/a , the temperature ratio T_2/T_1 , the *Kepler* contamination factor, and stellar limb darkening parameters for the triangular limb darkening law (Kipping 2013). This can be modified to a 14-parameter fit in the case of a circular orbit (omitting $e \cos \omega$ and $e \sin \omega$, which are both fixed to zero), but all the systems in the RG/EB subset have nonzero eccentricities. For eclipsing binaries that are SB1 with a radial velocity curve for one star only, we fit the same 16 parameters, but are unable to constrain the mass ratio or component masses (due to a lack of K_2), the scale of the system a , or, by extension, absolute radii. KIC 8702921 is the only SB1 here and it is discussed in more detail in Section 3.3.1.

Typical fit parameter distributions for an SB2 RG/EB are shown in Figure 3.6 for KIC 7037405. Most of the parameters have symmetric, broadly peaked distributions, which indicate the parameter space has been well-explored and is well-constrained by the input data sets. The exceptions are T_{eff} and the *Kepler* contamination. Temperature is poorly constrained by the broad *Kepler* bandpass so the ELC optimizer is unable to find temperature values that improve the fit. As a result, the distribution prefers the input value (6600 K for the companion star, in this case) and does not explore other options very thoroughly. In KIC 7037405, there is a bright star nearby, which means there is a non-negligible amount of contamination light, yet the fit was forced to choose a value of 5% or lower. With the exception of contamination, which is usually low and well-constrained, these fit parameter distributions are representative of most of the RG/EB subset. Error bars are computed from the cumulative distribution frequency of each fit parameter, excluding the first several thousand models, which allows for an appropriate

MCMC burn-in period. Each ELC optimization run is continued long enough to compute more than 400,000 models and achieve a robust global solution.

Fig. 3.6.— Distributions of the 16 parameters fit by ELC with the DE-MCMC optimization for KIC 7037405. More than 1,290,000 iterative models were generated for this system. Here, Star 1 is the main sequence companion and Star 2 is the red giant. Most of the distributions are symmetric and broadly peaked. The exceptions are $T_{\text{eff}, 1}$ and the *Kepler* contamination factor. As discussed in Section 2.5.2, the *Kepler* bandpass is broad and does not constrain absolute temperature well. Lacking other constraints, ELC’s optimizers tend to prefer retaining the input value of 6600 K. This star has a bright neighbor nearby, which may be increasing the contamination past the 5% level, but this is also challenging to model precisely with a wide bandpass.

Figure 3.7 shows the same ELC fit parameters for KIC 8702921 as in Figure 3.6. However, KIC 8702921 is an SB1 and only has a radial velocity curve for

the red giant star. At a glance, the fit is clearly less well-constrained than the case of KIC 7037405. Extremely “spiky” distributions, such as those for Period, zeropoint (T_0 conj), $e \cos \omega$, $e \sin \omega$, and K_1 are easily fit by ELC and no additional exploration of parameter space is required. Overall flat distributions, including M_1 , $T_{\text{eff}, 1}$, and limb darkening parameters for the main sequence companion, are not constrained at all. As a result, the best-fit global solution reported by ELC has large error bars for quantities which depend on these parameters. It is not possible to achieve a better solution without additional data about the main sequence star.

Fig. 3.7.— Distributions of the 16 parameters fit by ELC with the DE-MCMC optimization for KIC 8702921. More than 490,000 iterative models were generated for this system. Here, Star 1 is the red giant and Star 2 is the main sequence companion. The distributions look very different from those in Figure 3.6 because KIC 8702921 is an SB1. Parameters including inclination, component masses, and limb darkening for the extremely faint M dwarf companion are not constrained when only one radial velocity curve is available.

In the following subsections, we present flattened *Kepler* light curves and radial velocity curves for each RG/EB, discuss unique properties that arise from

dynamic modeling, and present each system’s best-fit ELC solution. Parameter error bars are given as 50% of the cumulative distribution function with the one-sigma upper error at 84.25% and one-sigma lower error at 15.75%. We note that the uncertainties reported for γ_{vel} are based on the internal consistency of each model using relative velocities, but the true systematic error is on the order of 0.2–0.3 km s⁻¹. As mentioned earlier, limb darkening coefficients are given according to the quadratic version of the triangular limb darkening law (Kipping 2013). This law imposes three physical boundary conditions that describe a triangular region in 2D parameter space. Uniformly sampling a pair of limb darkening coefficients in the interval [0, 1] therefore avoids unphysical solutions while retaining the star’s intensity profile as unknown. The result is a re-parameterized quadratic limb darkening law,

$$\frac{I(\mu)}{I(1)} = 1 - u_1(1 - \mu) - u_2(1 - \mu)^2. \quad (3.1)$$

Here, $I(\mu)/I(1)$ is the specific intensity of a star compared to that at the center of its projected disk, μ is the cosine of the angle between the line of sight and the emergent intensity, and u_1 and u_2 are the traditional quadratic limb darkening coefficients. The new coefficients fit by ELC are then defined as

$$q_1 \equiv (u_1 + u_2)^2 \quad (3.2)$$

$$q_2 \equiv 0.5u_1(u_1 + u_2)^{-1}. \quad (3.3)$$

For a full discussion and derivation, see Kipping (2013).

When evaluating how well any model fits a set of observations, it is important to consider how well the model reproduces reality. A global χ^2 minimum or “best fit” is achieved when the available observations most closely match a

computer model, but any χ^2 minimization algorithm proceeds under the assumption that this model is correct. The dynamic binary models created by ELC, while detailed and reasonably accurate, nonetheless differ from reality. Several physical unknowns widen the gap between model and reality, which include but are not limited to a consistent and accurate definition and measurement of stellar T_{eff} , poorly-constrained red giant limb darkening behavior regardless of the parametrization used, variable contamination from nearby stars in the *Kepler* aperture, and imperfect processing of *Kepler* light curve data. As a result, the final values reported for the adopted “all-eclipse” model for KIC 9246715 (see Table 2.2) likely have unrealistically small error bars. We encourage caution in interpreting the error bars for this and the other RG/EBs as reported from ELC modeling. They are only as accurate as the models are physically correct. The total eclipses in the rest of the RG/EB subset eliminate some of the degeneracies inherent to grazing eclipses, as discussed in Section 2.5.2, but the larger point stands: ELC models do not perfectly match reality.

3.3.1. KIC 8702921

An oscillating red giant and faint M-type main sequence star comprise this RG/EB with a 19 day orbital period. This system defies the trend in Gaulme et al. (2014), which suggests short-period RG/EBs are more likely to have weak or absent solar-like oscillations due to tidal effects. However, KIC 8702921 boasts the lowest-mass companion star of all the known *Kepler* RG/EBs, which likely explains this discrepancy. It is also the only system in the RG/EB subset for which we are unable to extract the radial velocity curve of the faint companion. Figure 3.8 shows the flattened *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this

system, and Figure 3.9 and Table 3.2 present the results from the ELC fit. The eclipses are very shallow and there is substantial in- and out-of-eclipse variability even once the light curve has been flattened in preparation for eclipse modeling, including phase effects on the order of 0.2% (Gaulme et al. 2014).

Even though KIC 8702921 is an SB1, if we adopt the asteroseismic mass value for the red giant, we can estimate the mass of the main sequence companion using the mass function. We combine Equations (1.3) and (1.4) to get

$$f(m) = \frac{K_1^3 P_{\text{orb}} (1 - e^2)^{3/2}}{2\pi G} = M_1 \frac{q^3}{(1 + q)^2} \sin^3 i, \quad (3.4)$$

where “1” refers to the giant star component and q is the mass ratio ($q = M_2/M_1$). When the best values and the largest errors on K_1 , P_{orb} , and e from Table 3.2 are combined, we find $f(m) = 0.00529 \pm 0.00005 M_\odot$. Together with the inclination $i = 86 \pm 2^\circ$ and asteroseismic mass $M_1 = 1.67 \pm 0.05 M_\odot$ (Gaulme et al. 2016), this yields a mass ratio of $q = 0.163 \pm 0.002$. Therefore, the estimated companion star mass is $M_2 = 0.272 \pm 0.008 M_\odot$. We include these values in Table 3.2 even though they rely on an asteroseismic mass and not dynamic modeling alone.

This is by far the lowest-mass companion of the RG/EB subset, which confirms it is an M dwarf and supports the SB1 nature of the system. These masses and the observed radial velocity curve imply $K_2 \sim 85 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, a very large amplitude. If it were present, this signal could not have been overlooked due to blending with the red giant BF peak, because the companion star’s velocity always differs greatly from the red giant star’s velocity. For more on this, see Appendix A and Figure A.2, which shows the strong red giant BF peak in KIC 8702921 and no apparent secondary BF peak.

Fig. 3.8.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 8702921. The light curve spans four years, and is shown unfolded (top), folded on the orbital period (middle), and with zoomed and offset views of each eclipse (bottom). The main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the deeper primary eclipse. Right: Radial velocity curve for the red giant in KIC 8702921. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye, and the bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curve over one orbit.

Fig. 3.9.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 8702921. The top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line shows the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2. Physical parameters of KIC 8702921 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	19.38446 ± 0.00002	
T_{conj} [day]	137.2139 ± 0.0007	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$86.2^{+2.0}_{-0.2}$	
e	$0.1002^{+0.0009}_{-0.0007}$	
ω [deg]	$162.3^{+1.4}_{-1.2}$	
$e \cos \omega$	-0.0954 ± 0.0004	
$e \sin \omega$	0.030 ± 0.003	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	0.66 ± 0.06	
contam	0.02 ± 0.02	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s $^{-1}$]	-10.23 ± 0.01	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	1.67 ± 0.05	asteroseismic (Gaulme et al. 2016)
R/a	$0.149^{+0.001}_{-0.008}$	
K [km s $^{-1}$]	13.88 ± 0.04	
q_1	$0.41^{+0.13}_{-0.03}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.48^{+0.05}_{-0.06}$	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	0.272 ± 0.008	estimate from M_{RG} and $f(m)$
R/a	$0.0080^{+0.0001}_{-0.0006}$	

3.3.2. KIC 9291629

This system has a similar orbital period to KIC 8702921, 21 days, but the giant star does not show any oscillations. The companion star is a F-type main sequence star (Gaulme et al. 2014), and the orbit is nearly circular. Figure 3.10 shows the *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this system, and Figure 3.11 and Table 3.3 present the results from the ELC fit.

In addition to the *Kepler* light curve, the ELC fit includes a total of eight binned points from the *BVRI* observations described in Section 3.2.2. KIC 9291629 shows significant quasi-periodic variability for which Gaulme et al. (2014) measured a period of 20.60 days, or 99.6% of the orbital period. This lag likely represents differential spot rotation within a tidally locked orbit. The secondary eclipse shows clear signs of star spots which evolve over several orbits. As a result, the secondary eclipse depth is likely underestimated in the ELC model. Because the main sequence star is in front of the red giant during secondary eclipse, the main sequence star radius may be overestimated. At $1.8 R_{\odot}$, it is somewhat larger than expected for a main sequence star with $1.1 M_{\odot}$; the star spots likely explain the disagreement. The consequences of this binary’s stellar activity and tidal resonance are explored in Section 4.2.2.

3.3.3. KIC 3955867

This system has a relatively short 34 day orbital period and is composed of a non-oscillating red giant and a main sequence star. The orbit is very close to circular. Figure 3.12 shows the *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this system, and Figure 3.13 and Table 3.4 present the results from the ELC fit.

Fig. 3.10.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 9291629, plotted the same way as in Figure 3.8. The main difference is that the main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the shallower secondary eclipse. Significant starspot activity which changes over time can be seen during both eclipses. Right: Radial velocity curves for KIC 9291629. Star 1 (red) is the RG and Star 2 (yellow) is the main sequence companion. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curves over one orbit.

Fig. 3.11.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 9291629. As before, the top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line is the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously, including the *BVRI* points, which are not plotted here. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3. Physical parameters of KIC 9291629 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	20.686424 ± 0.000003	
T_{conj} [day]	133.8914 ± 0.0001	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$84.122^{+0.0008}_{-0.0004}$	
e	$0.00063^{+0.00005}_{-0.00002}$	
ω [deg]	336.5 ± 16.0	
$e \cos \omega$	0.000610 ± 0.000009	
$e \sin \omega$	-0.0008 ± 0.0002	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	$0.79922^{+0.00012}_{-0.00008}$	
a [R_{\odot}]	$41.489^{+0.011}_{-0.005}$	
contam	0.0064 ± 0.0002	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s^{-1}]	$-30.662^{+0.002}_{-0.004}$	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$1.1274^{+0.0006}_{-0.0003}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	7.932 ± 0.002	
R/a	$0.19116^{+0.00002}_{-0.00003}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	$50.20^{+0.03}_{-0.01}$	
q_1	$0.296^{+0.0014}_{-0.0003}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.734^{+0.0005}_{-0.0003}$	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$1.1147^{+0.0012}_{-0.0005}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$1.8328^{+0.0005}_{-0.0004}$	
R/a	0.04417 ± 0.00001	
K [km s^{-1}]	$50.774^{+0.0007}_{-0.0003}$	
q_1	$0.2463^{+0.0008}_{-0.0006}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.6994^{+0.0003}_{-0.0002}$	triangular limb darkening

KIC 3955867 is the most strongly variable of the RG/EB subset, with a variability period of 33.30 days, or 98.9% of the orbital period (Gaulme et al. 2014). As in KIC 9291629, this lag is most likely a signature of differential spot rotation in a tidally locked binary.

The peak-to-peak variability amplitude is slightly larger here than in KIC 9291629, but overall the two systems are very similar short-period non-oscillators. The red giant in KIC 3955867 ($1.10 M_{\odot}$, $8.24 R_{\odot}$) is slightly larger than in KIC 9291629 ($1.13 M_{\odot}$, $7.93 R_{\odot}$), and the main sequence companion in KIC 3955867 ($0.92 M_{\odot}$, $0.97 R_{\odot}$) is notably smaller than that of KIC 9291629 ($1.11 M_{\odot}$, $1.83 R_{\odot}$). It is more likely a G-type star and not an F-type star as reported in Gaulme et al. (2014). Like KIC 9291629, KIC 3955867 is prone to an over-estimated main sequence star radius due to significant star spot activity in both eclipses, and particularly secondary eclipse. The connections between this system’s stellar activity and tidal resonances are explored more fully in Section 4.2.3.

3.3.4. KIC 10001167

An oscillating red giant and a main sequence star comprise this binary with a relatively long orbital period, 120 days. Gaulme et al. (2014) report the companion as F-type, implying it should have a mass and radius larger than the Sun; however, its mass and radius are sub-solar and more accurately classified as G. As in KICs 9291629 and 3955867, the secondary eclipse depth is variable and may be causing the secondary star’s radius to be overestimated. Figure 3.14 shows the *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this system, and Figure 3.15 and Table 3.5 present the results from the ELC fit.

Fig. 3.12.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 3955867. Only points in and near each eclipse were used to model this system, which is why more gaps appear than in, e.g., Figure 3.10. The main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the shallower secondary eclipse. Significant starspot activity which changes over time can be seen during both eclipses. Right: Radial velocity curves for KIC 3955867. Star 1 (red) is the RG and Star 2 (yellow) is the main sequence companion. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curves over one orbit.

Fig. 3.13.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 3955867. The top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line shows the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4. Physical parameters of KIC 3955867 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	33.65685 ± 0.00002	
T_{conj} [day]	127.8989 ± 0.0003	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$86.7455^{+0.0002}_{-0.02}$	
e	$0.0122^{+0.0005}_{-0.0006}$	
ω [deg]	$63.9^{+1.1}_{-1.4}$	
$e \cos \omega$	$0.00536^{+0.00004}_{-0.00002}$	
$e \sin \omega$	$0.0109^{+0.0005}_{-0.0006}$	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	1.328 ± 0.004	
a [R_{\odot}]	$55.451^{+0.008}_{-0.243}$	
contam	$0.0392^{+0.004}_{-0.0004}$	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s^{-1}]	14.814 ± 0.007	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$1.103^{+0.001}_{-0.002}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$8.238^{+0.004}_{-0.028}$	
R/a	$0.14859^{+0.00008}_{-0.00006}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	$37.83^{+0.01}_{-0.34}$	
q_1	$0.2358^{+0.0005}_{-0.0003}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.9369^{+0.0237}_{-0.0001}$	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$0.9187^{+0.0005}_{-0.0165}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$0.9692^{+0.0009}_{-0.0016}$	
R/a	$0.01748^{+0.00005}_{-0.05875}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	$45.4321^{+0.0002}_{-0.0263}$	
q_1	$0.2358^{+0.0005}_{-0.0588}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.7268^{+0.0029}_{-0.0003}$	triangular limb darkening

KIC 10001167 is one of four longer-period binaries in the RG/EB subset, and is the only one of these which shows significant phase effects. (The flattened *Kepler* light curve in Figure 3.14 has removed phase effects and omitted most of the points between eclipses.) As discussed in Section 3.2.2, the phase effects appear more strongly in bluer wavelengths than red. The stars are well-separated in a moderately eccentric orbit ($R_1 + R_2 = 13.7 R_\odot$, $a = 122 R_\odot$, $e = 0.16$), which implies any tidal distortions are small, and reflected light from the main sequence star should be minimal too, since it contributes only about 5% of the total light. Gaulme et al. (2014) measured the peak-to-peak amplitude of the phase modulation to be about 0.4%.

If the physical cause is due to tides, it is possible that such a low-level “heart-beat star” phase effect (Thompson et al. 2012) only appears because the star has the lowest density and surface gravity of the sample, making it more susceptible to tidal distortions. It is also the most metal-poor giant and is enriched in alpha elements (see Section 4.2.4). KIC 10001167 contains two of the lowest-mass stars of the sample, at $0.857 M_\odot$ for the giant and $0.805 M_\odot$ for the main sequence companion, which means it must be relatively old to have such an evolved low-mass star. The giant shows some signs of stellar variability, which is likely due to strong solar-like oscillations rather than magnetic activity. This can be seen as wiggles in the bottom eclipse zoom panels of Figure 3.15 and overall scatter in a more “zoomed-out” view of the light curve. This is the brightest RG/EB, second only to the double red giant KIC 9246715, so these variations are real and not due to noise. All of these effects are discussed further in Sections 4.3 and 4.4.

Fig. 3.14.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 10001167, plotted the same way as in Figure 3.12. The main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the shallower secondary eclipse. The notable level of in- and out-of-eclipse variability is real and not due to noise; this is one of the brightest targets in the RG/EB subset. Right: Radial velocity curves for KIC 10001167. Star 1 (red) is the RG and Star 2 (yellow) is the main sequence companion. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curves over one orbit.

Fig. 3.15.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 10001167. The top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line shows the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5. Physical parameters of KIC 10001167 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	120.3903 ± 0.0009	
T_{conj} [day]	124.682 ± 0.009	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$87.60^{+0.29}_{-0.40}$	
e	$0.1553^{+0.0016}_{-0.0009}$	
ω [deg]	$30.89^{+0.86}_{-0.66}$	
$e \cos \omega$	$0.1332^{+0.0001}_{-0.0004}$	
$e \sin \omega$	0.080 ± 0.002	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	1.29 ± 0.02	
a [R_{\odot}]	121.5 ± 2.2	
contam	0.024 ± 0.02	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s^{-1}]	$-103.51^{+0.04}_{-0.02}$	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$0.857^{+0.055}_{-0.060}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$12.73^{+0.51}_{-0.41}$	
R/a	0.105 ± 0.002	
K [km s^{-1}]	25.07 ± 0.10	
q_1	$0.47^{+0.26}_{-0.22}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.48^{+0.36}_{-0.28}$	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$0.805^{+0.034}_{-0.029}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$0.97^{+0.05}_{-0.04}$	
R/a	0.0080 ± 0.0003	
K [km s^{-1}]	$26.64^{+0.77}_{-0.98}$	
q_1	$0.01^{+0.03}_{-0.01}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.93^{+0.06}_{-0.07}$	triangular limb darkening

3.3.5. KIC 5786154

This RG/EB has a 198 day orbital period and is composed of a large oscillating red giant ($R = 11.0 R_{\odot}$) and an F–G type main sequence companion. The companion star radius ($1.56 R_{\odot}$) is larger than expected for a main sequence star of its mass ($1.02 M_{\odot}$), and unlike KICs 9291629 and 3955867, this result cannot be explained as a result of star spot contamination. The activity level is only 0.2% (Gaulme et al. 2014) and there is very little scatter in the light curve residuals either in or out of eclipse. No phase effects are observed, and it is the most eccentric of the RG/EB subset with $e = 0.378$. Figure 3.16 shows the *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this system, and Figure 3.17 and Table 3.6 present the results from the ELC fit.

3.3.6. KIC 7037405

KIC 7037405 is similar to KIC 5786154 with a slightly lower eccentricity, $e = 0.228$, and slightly longer orbital period, 207 days. It is composed of a large oscillating red giant ($R = 13.7 R_{\odot}$) and an F-type main sequence star. Like KIC 7037405, this companion is also a bit larger than expected for a star of its mass ($R = 1.74 R_{\odot}$, $M = 1.15 M_{\odot}$). Figure 3.18 shows the *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this system, which includes points from both ARCES and APOGEE. Figure 3.19 and Table 3.7 present the results from the ELC fit. A detailed study of this star appears in McKeever et al. (in prep).

Fig. 3.16.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 5786154, plotted the same way as in Figure 3.10. The main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the shallower secondary eclipse. Right: Radial velocity curves for KIC 5786154. Star 1 (red) is the RG and Star 2 (yellow) is the main sequence companion. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curves over one orbit.

Fig. 3.17.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 5786154. The top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line shows the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.6.

Table 3.6. Physical parameters of KIC 5786154 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	197.9182 ± 0.0002	
T_{conj} [day]	329.6140 ± 0.0009	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$89.15^{+0.03}_{-0.10}$	
e	0.3777 ± 0.0002	
ω [deg]	$205.17^{+0.09}_{-0.07}$	
$e \cos \omega$	0.34185 ± 0.00004	
$e \sin \omega$	$-0.1606^{+0.0005}_{-0.0006}$	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	1.318 ± 0.003	
a [R_{\odot}]	$182.4^{+0.1}_{-0.4}$	
contam	$0.045^{+0.004}_{-0.006}$	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s^{-1}]	-6.151 ± 0.003	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$1.062^{+0.002}_{-0.011}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$11.01^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	
R/a	$0.0603^{+0.0004}_{-0.0001}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	$24.67^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	
q_1	0.33 ± 0.04	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.71^{+0.07}_{-0.06}$	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	$1.019^{+0.001}_{-0.004}$	
R [R_{\odot}]	$1.557^{+0.007}_{-0.006}$	
R/a	$0.00855^{+0.00003}_{-0.00004}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	$25.71^{+0.02}_{-0.14}$	
q_1	0.020 ± 0.009	triangular limb darkening
q_2	0.67 ± 0.03	triangular limb darkening

Fig. 3.18.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 7037405, plotted the same way as in Figure 3.12. The main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the shallower secondary eclipse. Right: Radial velocity curves for KIC 7037405. Star 1 (red) is the RG and Star 2 (yellow) is the main sequence companion. Square points are from APOGEE. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curves over one orbit.

Fig. 3.19.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 7037405. The top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line shows the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7. Physical parameters of KIC 7037405 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	207.1082 ± 0.0001	
T_{conj} [day]	279.7655 ± 0.0005	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$89.12^{+0.09}_{-0.08}$	
e	0.2284 ± 0.0003	
ω [deg]	133.23 ± 0.07	
$e \cos \omega$	-0.15646 ± 0.00002	
$e \sin \omega$	0.1664 ± 0.0004	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	1.341 ± 0.009	
a [R_{\odot}]	197.5 ± 1.0	
contam	$0.044^{+0.005}_{-0.009}$	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s^{-1}]	-39.238 ± 0.002	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	1.267 ± 0.025	
R [R_{\odot}]	13.72 ± 0.08	
R/a	0.0695 ± 0.0002	
K [km s^{-1}]	23.56 ± 0.01	
q_1	0.56 ± 0.06	triangular limb darkening
q_2	0.50 ± 0.04	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	1.15 ± 0.01	
R [R_{\odot}]	1.74 ± 0.02	
R/a	0.00880 ± 0.00008	
K [km s^{-1}]	26.02 ± 0.25	
q_1	$0.06^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	$0.68^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	triangular limb darkening

3.3.7. KIC 9970396

KIC 9970396 has the longest orbital period of the sample at 235 days. It is composed of an oscillating red giant and an F-type main sequence companion star (Gaulme et al. 2014). Figure 3.20 shows the *Kepler* light curve and radial velocity curves for this system, and Figure 3.21 and Table 3.8 present the results from the ELC fit.

By chance, this star falls in a portion of the *Kepler* field of view which was not observed once every four quarters due to a broken detector. There are three gaps in the time series that can be seen in Figure 3.1. Between this and the long orbital period, only six primary eclipses and four secondary eclipses were observed during the entire *Kepler* mission. To improve the modeling and better constrain the eclipse depths, we add twelve additional *BVRI* light curve points to the ELC model. These are binned into one or two points per day from the observations described in Section 3.2.2.

The KIC 9970396 system has a smaller eccentricity of $e = 0.182$ and a smaller red giant ($R = 7.70 R_{\odot}$) than both KICs 5786154 and 7037405. As in those systems, there are no phase effects, and there are only very minimal fluctuations attributable to stellar activity in the light curve. However, the companion star's radius is still larger than expected for a main sequence star given its mass ($R = 1.08 R_{\odot}$, $M = 0.998 M_{\odot}$). In addition, the average stellar density of the red giant derived from dynamic modeling is significantly higher than the asteroseismic value computed from the $\Delta\nu$ scaling. This and other comparisons with the asteroseismic scaling relations are explored further in Section 3.4.

Fig. 3.20.— Left: Flattened *Kepler* light curve of KIC 9970306, plotted the same way as in Figure 3.12. The main sequence star passes in front of the red giant during the shallower secondary eclipse. Right: Radial velocity curves for KIC 9970396. Star 1 (red) is the RG and Star 2 (yellow) is the main sequence companion. The top panel shows the velocities as a function of time with a light dotted line to guide the eye. The bottom panel shows the folded radial velocity curves over one orbit.

Fig. 3.21.— Best-fit ELC model for KIC 9970396. As before, the top panels show radial velocity with residuals above, the middle panels show the folded light curve over one orbit with residuals below, and the bottom panels show a zoomed view of each eclipse with residuals below (red is the eclipse when the giant is in front, and yellow is the eclipse when the main sequence companion is in front). The black line is the best-fit ELC model for all data considered simultaneously, including the *BVRI* points, which are not plotted here. The full set of derived parameters are in Table 3.8.

Table 3.8. Physical parameters of KIC 9970396 from ELC modeling

Parameter	Value	Comment
P_{orb} [day]	235.29852 ± 0.00007	
T_{conj} [day]	357.5401 ± 0.0002	0 d \equiv 2454833 BJD
i [deg]	$89.971^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$	
e	0.1821 ± 0.0002	
ω [deg]	138.27 ± 0.06	
$e \cos \omega$	-0.135907 ± 0.000007	
$e \sin \omega$	0.1212 ± 0.0003	
$T_{\text{MS}}/T_{\text{RG}}$	0.799 ± 0.002	
a [R_{\odot}]	207.45 ± 0.63	
contam	$0.0047^{+0.0062}_{-0.0037}$	<i>Kepler</i> contamination
γ_{vel} [km s^{-1}]	-16.5427 ± 0.0005	systemic velocity
Red Giant Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	1.168 ± 0.014	
R [R_{\odot}]	7.70 ± 0.02	
R/a	$0.03712^{+0.00002}_{-0.00001}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	20.914 ± 0.007	
q_1	0.25 ± 0.01	triangular limb darkening
q_2	0.66 ± 0.02	triangular limb darkening
Main Sequence Star		
M [M_{\odot}]	0.998 ± 0.006	
R [R_{\odot}]	$1.082^{+0.005}_{-0.004}$	
R/a	$0.00521^{+0.00002}_{-0.00001}$	
K [km s^{-1}]	24.47 ± 0.14	
q_1	$0.042^{+0.016}_{-0.014}$	triangular limb darkening
q_2	0.685 ± 0.006	triangular limb darkening

3.4. Testing the Asteroseismic Scaling Relations

The RG/EB subsample includes four oscillating SB2 binaries with main sequence companions as well as the double red giant system which can be used to test the asteroseismic scaling relations (Equations (1.12) and (1.13)). Because $\Delta\nu$ and ν_{\max} depend directly on density and surface gravity, respectively, we compare these quantities as well as mass and radius. The results are plotted in Figure 3.22, and the results from Section 3.3 are summarized together with updated asteroseismic stellar parameters from Gaulme et al. (2016) in Table 3.9. The asteroseismic values are derived using the same second-order asymptotic correction described in Section 2.6.1.1 for KIC 9246715 (Mosser et al. 2013).

The scaling relations appear to work in a general sense, but are not accurate for this sample of RG/EBs. We find they fail most strongly for RGB stars least like the Sun; in other words, they are not accurate for RGB stars with very low density and surface gravity. In every case, where a discrepancy arises between the dynamic mass or radius and the asteroseismic mass or radius, both quantities are overestimated by asteroseismology. The overestimates worsen if only a first-order asymptotic correction is used (Kjeldsen & Bedding 1995) in lieu of the second-order correction from Mosser et al. (2013). Because mass and radius are deduced from asteroseismology by combining measures of mean density and surface gravity ($\Delta\nu$ and ν_{\max} , respectively), it is possible to have good agreement with dynamic modeling for density and surface gravity yet have masses and radii which are both systematically offset—too high, in this case. The scaling relations may work better for red clump stars (e.g., KIC 9246715 agrees well in both mass and radius), but we have only a single data point, so it is impossible to say for sure.

Fig. 3.22.— Comparing results from dynamic modeling and asteroseismology. The upper left panel compares masses, the upper right, radii, the lower left, density, and the lower right, surface gravity. The values plotted are in Table 3.9. Spectroscopically-derived surface gravities from Table 3.1 are plotted in gray to illustrate the strong discrepancy. Overall, agreement between dynamic modeling and the asteroseismic scalings is not very good.

Table 3.9. Red giant parameters from different modeling techniques

KIC	Dynamic Binary Modeling with ELC				Asteroseismology ^a			
	M (M_{\odot})	R (R_{\odot})	$\log g$ (cgs)	$\bar{\rho}$ ($\bar{\rho}_{\odot} \times 10^{-3}$)	M (M_{\odot})	R (R_{\odot})	$\log g$ (cgs)	$\bar{\rho}$ ($\bar{\rho}_{\odot} \times 10^{-3}$)
8702921 ^b	$3.22^{+0.07}_{-0.13}$...	1.67 ± 0.05	5.32 ± 0.05	3.209 ± 0.004	11.07 ± 0.02
9291629 ^c	$1.1274^{+0.0006}_{-0.0002}$	7.932 ± 0.002	2.691 ± 0.001	2.259 ± 0.002
3955867 ^c	$1.103^{+0.001}_{-0.002}$	$8.238^{+0.004}_{-0.028}$	2.649 ± 0.001	1.973 ± 0.005
10001167	$0.857^{+0.055}_{-0.060}$	$12.73^{+0.51}_{-0.41}$	$2.16^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	0.415 ± 0.058	1.09 ± 0.03	13.7 ± 0.1	2.200 ± 0.004	0.421 ± 0.002
5786154	$1.062^{+0.002}_{-0.011}$	$11.01^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	$2.381^{+0.002}_{-0.007}$	0.796 ± 0.012	1.39 ± 0.06	12.6 ± 0.2	2.377 ± 0.005	0.687 ± 0.002
7037405	1.267 ± 0.025	13.72 ± 0.08	2.266 ± 0.005	0.491 ± 0.013	1.28 ± 0.03	14.4 ± 0.1	2.230 ± 0.003	0.431 ± 0.002
9970396	1.168 ± 0.014	7.70 ± 0.02	$2.732^{+0.003}_{-0.002}$	2.56 ± 0.04	1.36 ± 0.04	8.47 ± 0.07	2.716 ± 0.003	2.234 ± 0.007

^aValues from Gaulme et al. (2016) measured using the asymptotic correction described in Section 2.6.1.1 (Mosser et al. 2013).

^bThis system is an SBI.

^cThese RG/EBs lack solar-like oscillations.

Precision is better for radius than mass in the dynamic modeling because of high-quality *Kepler* light curves, which make radii more precise, and systematic scatter in the secondary star radial velocity curves, which makes masses less precise. The precision of asteroseismic radius is also higher than mass due to the functional form of the scaling laws and a large contribution from effective temperature to the asteroseismic error budget. However, we note that even if the temperatures were off by more than 100 K, which is characteristic of the largest spectroscopic T_{eff} 1σ error bars, the result would be the same.

Past studies which compared asteroseismic radii with interferometric radii (e.g., Huber et al. 2012; Baines et al. 2014) typically found scatter for red giants similar to these results, but we additionally find that the radii are systematically overestimated by the asteroseismic scaling relations. Of course, interferometry cannot be used to measure stellar masses. The implications of overestimated masses are particularly profound. When isochrones and asteroseismic masses are combined to estimate stellar ages, the result from masses which are slightly too large will yield ages that are far too young. This is discussed further in Gaulme et al. (2016). In addition, any attempt to use asteroseismic masses to constrain red giant mass loss or the initial mass function of stellar populations will be incorrect.

In the future, careful studies of more RG/EBs might enable us to determine whether the $\Delta\nu$ or ν_{max} scaling is responsible for the majority of the discrepancy, or a combination of both. It would be particularly useful to compare a population of RGB stars and red clump stars. A sufficiently large sample could propose empirical corrections for use in ensemble asteroseismology. Gaulme et al. (2016) test the scaling relations for the full *Kepler* RG/EB sample of ten oscillating SB2s, which includes the five studied here. More still would be necessary to

suggest statistically robust correction factors, and we are continuing to search *Kepler* data and propose new *K2* targets to increase the sample size.

Another important finding illustrated in the lower right panel of Figure 3.22 is evidence for a large systematic spectroscopic $\log g$ offset. The discrepancy is on the order of 0.2–0.4 dex higher than both the dynamic and asteroseismic $\log g$. This was also reported in Section 2.6.1.4 for KIC 9246715, and has been consistently seen for APOGEE targets (see, e.g., Holtzman et al. 2015). The physical cause remains unknown, and is almost certainly not a rotation effect. Holtzman et al. (2015) note that the offset is worse for red clump stars than RGB stars. While it is possible to derive an empirical correction given a sufficiently large sample of stars, it is clear that traditional stellar atmosphere modeling with MOOG (Snedden 1973), ASPCAP (García Pérez et al. 2015), and similar spectroscopic grid-search methods are not measuring the physical stellar surface gravity. In fact, several estimates of both T_{eff} and $\log g$ exist for these stars, and these differences are discussed more in Section 5.2.

3.5. Conclusions

We have characterized an additional seven RG/EBs observed by *Kepler* with dynamic binary modeling that combines *Kepler* light curves and radial velocity curves from ground-based spectra. We include *BVRI* photometry points for two of the binaries to help constrain eclipse depths. Together with the double red giant binary KIC 9246715 in Chapter 2, this brings the RG/EB subset sample size to eight. All but one of the systems are SB2, which means we are able to measure the masses and radii of component stars to high precision. The sole SB1 has

precise relative radii (R_1/a and R_2/a) measurements and good component mass estimates derived by combining the binary mass function with the asteroseismic mass. All but two of the RG/EBs in this sample exhibit solar-like oscillations, and now that all the stars' global physical properties are well-constrained, we are in a good position to study the physical processes that may inhibit solar-like oscillations. This is the goal of Chapter 4.

For the five SB2 binaries which do oscillate, including the oscillating component of KIC 9246715, we use the masses, radii, surface gravities, and average densities to directly test the asteroseismic scaling relations. We find they are correct in a general sense, but not highly accurate for stars with very low densities and/or surface gravities. In particular, the scaling laws consistently overestimate both mass and radius when compared with results from dynamic binary modeling. This has profound implications for ensemble asteroseismology which generally assumes that asteroseismically-derived properties are correct and uses the results to study the composition and kinematics of our galaxy.

3.6. Acknowledgements

The asteroseismic results used in this Chapter all derive from measurements by Patrick Gaulme, and appear in Gaulme et al. (2013, 2014, 2016). Patrick also processed the *Kepler* light curves for both asteroseismology and eclipse modeling purposes. The stellar atmosphere modeling with MOOG was performed by Jean McKeever on co-added composite spectra for each system, and these results appear in Gaulme et al. (2016). Jean also took the majority of the ARCES observations and reduced and continuum-normalized all the ARCES spectra.

4. MECHANISMS OF SUPPRESSING SOLAR-LIKE OSCILLATIONS IN RED GIANTS

4.1. Introduction

Approximately one fifth of the known RG/EBs do not show any solar-like oscillation activity at all (Gaulme et al. 2014). The fraction of single evolved stars without confirmed binary companions that lack oscillations is unknown. Among the subset of eight RG/EBs considered here, we have the unique double red giant KIC 9246715, which appears to have one oscillating red clump star and a nearly-identical twin which does not oscillate. There are two additional non-oscillating red giants in the sample as well: KIC 9291629 and KIC 3955867.

In the absence of external influences, all evolved giant stars with a convective outer layer should theoretically exhibit stochastically-driven solar-like oscillations. However, that is clearly not the case. Gaulme et al. (2014) proposed that stronger tidal interactions from short-period binaries and increased magnetic activity on spotty giants are linked to absent or damped solar-like oscillations. Now that the oscillating and non-oscillating binaries alike have been well-characterized globally via dynamic modeling in Chapter 3, we can use the available observations with new modeling techniques to study them in greater detail. We therefore use this information to explore how magnetically active each system is, how stellar evolution likely proceeded, and what role tidal forces have played over time.

In this Chapter, we present disentangled high-resolution spectroscopy for each of the seven RG/EBs with main sequence companions and use spectral line diagnostics to estimate magnetic activity in Section 4.2. Alongside this, we present stellar evolution models for each red giant based on mass and metallicity. In Sec-

tion 4.3, we compare each system’s magnetic features and describe how this could be responsible for suppressing solar-like oscillations. Section 4.4 quantifies the tidal forces each giant star has experienced as it evolved to reach its present-day observed radius and investigates whether this could be the culprit for suppressed or missing oscillation modes. Finally, Section 4.5 summarizes the results.

4.2. Magnetic Diagnostics and Stellar Evolution Histories

To examine each giant star’s spectrum, we consider spectra from ARCES, introduced in Section 3.2.3, and use the FDBinary (fd3) technique described in Appendix B. We follow the same procedure as in Section 2.4.2 and use Fourier decomposition to combine a set of observed binary spectra into one spectrum per star at zero velocity. These RG/EBs differ from KIC 9246715, however, because the faint star only contributes about 5% of the total light to each system. While it is mathematically possible to create disentangled spectra for both stellar components in these binaries, the main sequence star spectrum is prohibitively faint and noisy, so we keep only the red giant spectrum. We do not have enough information to disentangle spectra for the SB1 KIC 8702921, so we instead consider a co-added composite spectrum which contains trace amounts of light from the faint main sequence companion. High-resolution stellar spectra contain many features which can serve as magnetic line diagnostics and can also help constrain the projected rotational velocity, $v_{\text{rot}} \sin i$, because absorption lines are broadened (but equivalent width is unchanged) as rotation speed increases.

For consistency, we examine the same spectral regions used in Section 2.6.3 for KIC 9246715. These are some of the strongest FeI lines in the disentangled

region which are either particularly prone to Zeeman splitting (Harvey 1973) or not (Sistla & Harvey 1970), the H α absorption feature, which may exhibit extra absorption or emission depending on the physical conditions, and a pair of CaII absorption lines around 8500 Å, which may exhibit net emission in the presence of a highly active chromosphere. Results are presented in the subsections below for each star. We follow the approach of Fröhlich et al. (2012) and plot each target spectrum on top of an appropriate model with the difference below. Model spectra are drawn from Coelho (2014) and selected to closely match the target’s spectroscopic parameters in Table 3.1 (T_{eff} , $\log g$, [Fe/H]). We set $[\alpha/\text{H}] = 0$ for all systems except KIC 10001167, which was shown to be alpha-enhanced by the APOGEE pipeline.

Alongside the spectra, we use Models for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics (MESA, Paxton et al. 2011, 2013, 2015) to create 1D stellar evolution models for the evolved star in each RG/EB. MESA creates two types of output files: global stellar properties as a function of time and radial profiles of the stellar interior at various timesteps. We use the former together with each red giant’s present radius to estimate ages, and we explore how each system’s past may affect its present oscillation situation.

MESA takes three critical input parameters: initial stellar mass, initial metallicity Z , and initial helium mass fraction Y (defined such that $X + Y + Z = 1$, where X is the hydrogen mass fraction). We model each red giant assuming dynamical mass from ELC modeling and composition based on spectroscopic [Fe/H] (see Tables 3.1 and 3.9). The two measures of metallicity are related by

$$[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = \log \left[\frac{f_{\text{Fe}}(\alpha)}{f_{\text{Fe}}(0)} \times \frac{m_Z(0)}{m_Z(\alpha)} \times \frac{Z}{1 - Y - Z} \times \left(\frac{Z}{X} \right)_{\odot}^{-1} \right], \quad (4.1)$$

where f_{Fe} is the number fraction of iron with respect to all elements heavier than helium and m_Z is the average atomic mass of heavy elements weighted by the number of atoms. The reference values denoted with (0) are for the Sun and the values for the star in question denoted with (α) are a function of the fraction of alpha-elements (Valcarce et al. 2013). An online calculator¹ which applies this relation was used to convert the spectroscopic [Fe/H] metallicities into a set of (X, Y, Z) based on standard abundances from Asplund et al. (2004).

With a stellar evolution model in hand, we estimate how the star’s radius and tidal circularization function evolves with time. The circularization function $I(t)$, which is a function of radius $R(t)$, convective envelope mass $M_{\text{env}}(t)$, and effective temperature $T_{\text{eff}}(t)$, was first introduced in Equation (2.6) in Section 2.6.4. This is the portion of the detached binary equilibrium tide circularization timescale which depends only on the red giant’s evolution (Verbunt & Phinney 1995). We can add in the effects of the companion star (via the mass ratio q and orbital period P_{orb}) once $I(t)$ is evaluated to get a complete picture of how a system’s orbit is expected to change eccentricity over time. To review, the full function first presented in Equation (2.5) is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln e &= \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{\tau_c(t')} \\ &\simeq -1.7 \times 10^{-5} \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)^{-11/3} \\ &\times q(1+q)^{-5/3} I(t) \left(\frac{P_{\text{orb}}}{\text{day}} \right)^{-16/3}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

For each system, $I(t)$ is plotted as a function of radius from the end of the main sequence, to the star’s present-day radius (horizontal line), and a bit beyond.

¹<http://astro.wsu.edu/cgi-bin/XYZ.pl>

The most notable feature on the plot is the RGB luminosity bump, which appears as a “blip” in both $I(t)$ and $R(t)$. This bump occurs as the hydrogen-burning shell encounters a discontinuity in hydrogen abundance left behind from the first dredge-up. The first dredge-up happens when a star begins ascending the RGB and its convective envelope first extends into regions affected by hydrogen fusion during its main-sequence life (Christensen-Dalsgaard 2015). The exact shape and location of the RGB bump varies with stellar mass.

As stellar evolution continues, the star will eventually reach the tip of the RGB and ignite helium. We let each MESA model run well past this point to check if there is more than one age at which an evolved star could have its present-day radius. This was the case with KIC 9246715, a red clump star; see Section 2.6.4 and Figure 2.11 for a full discussion. From the rest of the RG/EB subset, only KICs 10001167, 5786154, and 7037405 have a point during their future evolution when the radius matches for a second time. However, Gaulme et al. (2014) reports that all three of these oscillating systems have a mixed-mode period spacing consistent with the RGB and not the red clump, so we proceed under the well-founded assumption that all are RGB stars.

In the following subsections, we discuss each system’s spectroscopic features that differ from an appropriate stellar atmosphere model (Coelho 2014) and present age estimates from MESA to test whether straightforward coevolution is realistic. Finally, we use Equation (4.2) with the results from MESA to calculate whether the cumulative tidal forces over each red giant’s life are expected to have circularized its orbit.

4.2.1. KIC 8702921

As the only SB1 in the sample, KIC 8702921 is a difficult target for spectral disentangling because the amplitudes of each star’s radial velocity curve are not known. However, this means the spectra contain only trace amounts of light from the main sequence companion, so we simply shift them all to zero velocity and co-add them. KIC 8702921 does not appear to have any significant rotational line broadening, and given its short 19-day orbital period, it must not be tidally locked. This agrees with Gaulme et al. (2014) which found a variability period of 97.8 days, or five times longer than the orbital period. This also agrees with the system’s non-zero eccentricity, because the timescale required for tidal synchronization is generally shorter than that for circularization.

Figure 4.1 presents regions of spectra sensitive to magnetic activity compared to an appropriate HIGHRES model spectrum from Coelho (2014). There is no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic FeI lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. The CaII lines do not show any signs of emission. The only interesting feature is H α , which is notably deeper than the model predicts. This may be indicative of chromospheric activity, which is discussed further in Section 4.3.

In Figure 4.2, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius (bottom). The vertical line indicates the current radius of the star, which is the point up to which we evaluate an expected change in eccentricity. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -401$ up until $t = 2.47 \times 10^9$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 5.24 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = 2.6$, which is greater than zero, meaning

Fig. 4.1.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 8702921. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ K, $\log g = 3.0$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.2$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014). The only feature which deviates notably from the model is $\text{H}\alpha$.

the binary should have had enough time to circularize its orbit. The fact that it has not actually been circularized is considered in Section 4.4.

4.2.2. KIC 9291629

This binary is the faintest RG/EB in the sample, which makes its disentangled spectrum in Figure 4.3 relatively noisy. The lines are also clearly rotationally broadened. To investigate spectral regions that may be sensitive to magnetic activity, we select an appropriate HIGHRES spectrum (Coelho 2014) and use the PyAstronomy² `rotBroad` function to apply a $v \sin i$ consistent with synchronous rotation ($v = 2\pi R/P_{\text{orb}}$). The result is in Figure 4.4.

²<https://github.com/sczesla/PyAstronomy>

Fig. 4.2.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 8702921. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. The star is a relatively small giant early in its evolution and has not yet evolved past the RGB luminosity bump, which appears as the bump in the upper right of both panels.

There is no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic Fe I lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. Occasional positive spikes in the spectrum are due to noise compounded with the inherent continuum normalization difficulties of FDBinary (see Section B.1), but they occur well away from features of interest. $H\alpha$ is unremarkable, and its slight asymmetry is likely due to noise. The Ca II lines, however, show strong signs of net emission. These results are discussed further in Section 4.3. We note that the flat part on the red edge of the Ca II window is an edge effect from disentangling which begins well after the line at 8542 Å. This artifact also appears in all subsequent spectra.

In Figure 4.5, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius. The vertical line indicates the current radius of the star, which is the point up to which we evaluate an expected change in eccentricity. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -104$ up until $t = 7.91 \times 10^9$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 7.93 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = 2.02$, which is greater than zero, and indicates the binary should have had enough time to circularize its orbit. This generally agrees with KIC 9291629’s near-circular orbit and is considered further in Section 4.4.

4.2.3. KIC 3955867

The red giant disentangled spectrum for KIC 3955867 is in Figure 4.6. KIC 3955867 is only slightly brighter than KIC 9291629 and suffers from the same occasional positive spikes in the spectrum, but they occur well away from features of interest. The absorption lines are clearly rotationally broadened. To investigate spectral regions that may be sensitive to magnetic activity, we select an

Fig. 4.3.— A portion of disentangled spectrum for the RG in KIC 9291629 from the FDBinary technique (red). A single ARCES observation is shown in black for comparison. The *Kepler* magnitude of this system is 13.957 and it is the faintest RG/EB in the sample. As a result, all 15 of the observed spectra and the final disentangled spectrum are quite noisy.

Fig. 4.4.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 9291629. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 4750$ K, $\log g = 3.0$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014), and has been rotationally broadened with $v \sin i = 19.39$ km s $^{-1}$. The only features which deviate notably from the model are the CaII lines.

Fig. 4.5.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 9291629. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. The star has not quite reached the RGB luminosity bump.

appropriate HIGHRES spectrum (Coelho 2014). Using the same method that was used for KIC 9291629, we apply a $v \sin i$ consistent with synchronous rotation ($v = 2\pi R/P_{\text{orb}}$) to the model spectrum before comparing it with the disentangled spectrum. The result is in Figure 4.7.

When taking a closer look at magnetically sensitive lines, we find no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic Fe I lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. $\text{H}\alpha$ displays a slight asymmetry which causes it to appear shallower than the model; it is unclear whether the total line width differs or not. The Ca II lines, however, show strong signs of net emission, particularly the one at 8542 Å. These results are discussed more in Section 4.3.

In Figure 4.8, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius. The vertical line indicates the current radius of the star, which is the point up to which we evaluate an expected change in eccentricity. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -17.6$ up until $t = 5.07 \times 10^9$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 8.24 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = 1.25$, which is greater than zero, meaning the binary should have had enough time to circularize its orbit. This agrees with the near-circular orbit and is considered further in Section 4.4.

4.2.4. KIC 10001167

As one of the brightest stars in the RG/EB subset, KIC 10001167 has a very high signal-to-noise ratio in its spectra. The disentangled red giant spectrum is in Figure 4.9. The large systemic velocity of -104 km s^{-1} is apparent in the offset between the single ARCES spectrum shown in black and the disentangled result in

Fig. 4.6.— A portion of disentangled spectrum for the RG in KIC 3955867 from the FDBinary technique (red). As in Figure 4.3, a single ARCES observation is shown in black for comparison. There are 15 spectra used here.

Fig. 4.7.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 3955867. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ K, $\log g = 3.0$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.5$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014), and has been rotationally broadened with $v \sin i = 12.36$ km s $^{-1}$. The only features which deviate notably from the model are the CaII lines and possibly H α .

Fig. 4.8.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 3955867. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. The star has not yet reached the RGB luminosity bump.

red. KIC 10001167 is not a fast rotator, but it is slightly enhanced in α elements according to APOGEE ($[\alpha/\text{H}] = 0.22$). A zoomed view of regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity is in Figure 4.10. There is no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic FeI lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. The CaII lines do not show any signs of emission. The only interesting feature is $\text{H}\alpha$, which is significantly deeper than the model predicts. These results are discussed in context in Section 4.3.

In Figure 4.11, as before, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -0.65$ up until $t = 1.17 \times 10^{10}$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 12.73 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = -0.18$, which is slightly less than zero, and very close to the cutoff for an expected circularized orbit. This just barely agrees with the observed $e = 0.16$, and is discussed further in Section 4.4.

4.2.5. KIC 5786154

The red giant disentangled spectrum for the long-period binary KIC 5786154 is in Figure 4.12, and a zoom of magnetically sensitive regions compared to an appropriate model from Coelho (2014) is in Figure 4.13. KIC 5786154 is not a fast rotator. There is no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic FeI lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. The CaII lines do not show any signs of emission. As in KIC 10001167, the only interesting feature is $\text{H}\alpha$, which is significantly deeper than the model predicts. These results are discussed further in Section 4.3.

Fig. 4.9.— A portion of disentangled spectrum for the RG in KIC 10001167 from the FDBinary technique (red). As before, a single ARCES observation is shown in black for comparison. There are 21 spectra used here.

Fig. 4.10.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 10001167. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 4750$ K, $\log g = 2.5$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.8$, and $[\alpha/\text{H}] = 0.4$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014). The only feature which deviates notably from the model is the deep $\text{H}\alpha$ absorption line.

Fig. 4.11.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 10001167. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. This star has evolved past the RGB luminosity bump.

In Figure 4.14, as before, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -0.009$ up until $t = 8.55 \times 10^9$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 11.01 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = -2.04$, which is less than zero, meaning the binary has not had enough time to circularize its orbit. This agrees with KIC 5786154’s eccentric orbit (the most eccentric of the subset with $e = 0.38$) and is discussed more in Section 4.4.

4.2.6. KIC 7037405

As mentioned in Chapter 3, KIC 7037405 is similar to KIC 5786154, and this holds true in their red giant spectra. The disentangled spectrum of KIC 7037405 is in Figure 4.15, and a zoom of magnetically sensitive regions compared to an appropriate model from Coelho (2014) is in Figure 4.16. KIC 7037405 is a long-period binary and not a fast rotator. We find no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic FeI lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. The CaII lines do not show any signs of emission. The only interesting feature is a deep H α line. These results are discussed further in Section 4.3. A detailed study of this star is underway in McKeever et al. (in prep).

In Figure 4.17, as before, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -0.022$ up until $t = 3.62 \times 10^9$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 13.72 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = -1.65$, which is less than zero, and indicates the binary has not had enough time to circularize its orbit. This agrees well with $e = 0.23$ and is considered further in Section 4.4.

Fig. 4.12.— A portion of disentangled spectrum for the RG in KIC 5786154 from the FDBinary technique (red). As before, a single ARCES observation is shown in black for comparison. There are 23 spectra used here.

Fig. 4.13.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 5786154. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 4750$ K, $\log g = 2.5$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014). The only feature which deviates notably from the model is the deep $\text{H}\alpha$ absorption line.

Fig. 4.14.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 5786154. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. This star has evolved past the RGB luminosity bump.

Fig. 4.15.— A portion of disentangled spectrum for the RG in KIC 7037405 from the FDBinary technique (red). As before, a single ARCES observation is shown in black for comparison. There are 20 spectra used here.

Fig. 4.16.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 7037405. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 4500$ K, $\log g = 2.5$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.5$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014). The only feature which deviates notably from the model is the deep $\text{H}\alpha$ absorption line.

Fig. 4.17.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 7037405. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. This star has evolved past the RGB luminosity bump.

4.2.7. KIC 9970396

This red giant’s disentangled spectrum is in Figure 4.18, and a zoom of magnetically sensitive regions compared to an appropriate stellar atmosphere model from Coelho (2014) is in Figure 4.19. Like the other long-period RG/EBs, KIC 9970396 does not exhibit rotational broadening. There is no difference in how well the magnetic and non-magnetic FeI lines fit the model, and no Zeeman splitting or broadening appears. The CaII lines do not show any signs of emission. Yet again, the most interesting feature is $H\alpha$, which is significantly deeper than the model. These results are discussed further in Section 4.3.

In Figure 4.20, as before, we present the red giant’s age as a function of radius and the circularization function $I(t)$ also as a function of radius. We calculate $\Delta \ln e = -0.0002$ up until $t = 5.05 \times 10^9$ years, the theoretical age of the star when it reaches $R = 7.70 R_{\odot}$. This can be rewritten as $\log[-\Delta \ln e] = -3.54$, which is less than zero, meaning the binary has not had enough time to circularize its orbit. This agrees with KIC 9970396’s eccentric orbit ($e = 0.18$) and is explored further in Section 4.4.

4.3. Magnetically Suppressed Solar-like Oscillations in Red Giants

In Chapter 2, we found that both stars in KIC 9246715 are moderately magnetically active, but that one appears to be more active than the other. Given a single main set of solar-like oscillations and two nearly-identical stars, it was impossible to determine which star was the oscillator solely by comparing dynamical modeling and asteroseismology. We concluded that the less magnetically active star was more likely to be the source of the main solar-like oscillations. Three

Fig. 4.18.— A portion of disentangled spectrum for the RG in KIC 9970396 from the FDBinary technique (red). As before, a single ARCES observation is shown in black for comparison. There are 23 spectra used here.

Fig. 4.19.— Spectral regions potentially sensitive to magnetic activity in KIC 9970396. The model spectrum has $T_{\text{eff}} = 5000$ K, $\log g = 3.0$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0$ (HIGHRES, Coelho 2014). The only feature which deviates notably from the model is the deep $\text{H}\alpha$ absorption line.

Fig. 4.20.— Radius evolution over time (top) and the circularization function $I(t)$ (bottom) for the red giant in KIC 9970396. The vertical line is the present radius of the star from ELC modeling. This star has not yet reached the RGB luminosity bump.

observable features support this conclusion: overall variability in the *Kepler* light curve with a maximum peak-to-peak amplitude of 2% (Gaulme et al. 2014), increased stellar variability during one eclipse compared to the other, and a larger degree of H α absorption in excess of what a model stellar atmosphere predicted.

Now that we have an additional seven RG/EBs characterized with the same kinds of observations, and no ambiguity as to which star in each binary is a potentially oscillating red giant, we can examine how they enhance the picture linking magnetic activity to suppressed solar-like oscillations. In all but KIC 8702921, the primary eclipse happens when the red giant fully covers the light from the main sequence companion, and the secondary eclipse happens when the companion star is in front of the red giant but is not able to block a large portion of its light. (The primary and secondary eclipse designations are reversed for KIC 8702921, but the physics is the same.) As a result, comparing the magnitude of the *Kepler* light curve residuals during each eclipse is not as instructive as it was for KIC 9246715, where both stars are nearly the same size. Instead, residuals in both eclipses are primarily a function of the activity level of the red giant. In general, the primary eclipse residuals are more randomly distributed while the secondary eclipse residuals show more structure as the main sequence star passes in front of discrete spots on the giant. This is most apparent in the short-period systems with the most stellar activity, KICs 9291629 and 3955867 (see the lower left corner of the left panel in Figures 3.10 and 3.12). Gaulme et al. (2014) measured the maximum peak-to-peak variability amplitude and found 16.4% and 22.7% for KICs 9291629 and 3955867, respectively. All the long-period systems with main sequence companions only vary at the 0.2–0.4% level. The short-period RG/EB with the M dwarf companion, KIC 8702921, comes in at 1.4%.

However, as shown in Section 4.2, light curve variability is not the only tool available to measure magnetism in these RG/EBs. Lines potentially sensitive to magnetic activity are another excellent indicator. Across the entire RG/EB subset, we examine a set of FeI lines which are in a high signal-to-noise region of the disentangled giant spectra. Three of them are prone to Zeeman broadening or splitting in the presence of strong magnetic fields, and the other three are not magnetically sensitive and serve as controls. We find no measurable difference in the behavior of one set of lines compared to the other in any of the RG/EBs when an appropriate model spectrum is subtracted. This is not a surprising result; magnetic fields must be incredibly strong and preferentially aligned for Zeeman effects to appear, and red giants are not among the most highly magnetic stars. Aurière et al. (2015) found that typical red giants have magnetic field strengths on the order of a few Gauss. Even if such a star had spotty regions with magnetic field strengths thousands of times as strong, much like the Sun, the Zeeman splitting would still be impossible to detect with ARCES. Aurière et al. (2015) were only able to detect low levels of red giant magnetic activity via high-resolution spectropolarimetry. We conclude that the lack of detection of Zeeman broadening or splitting in the disentangled spectra both here and in Section 2.6.3 is not able to constrain anything about the activity level of the red giants.

We attempted to examine the well-known CaII H & K features, which are a reliable measure of chromospheric activity. Unfortunately they are in a relatively blue region which is inherently noisy in ARCES and has significantly lower flux in redder stars like these, rendering this region of the spectrum a jumbled mess. Instead, we examine both H α λ 6563 and CaII λ 8498, 8542, which may serve as proxies and yield interesting results.

We find that only the non-oscillating RG/EBs have signatures of net CaII emission, which we interpret as an unambiguous signature of chromospheric magnetic activity. KIC 9291629 does not have any abnormal H α absorption, but it is unclear whether KIC 3955867 does or not, as its line profile is asymmetric. If anything, it is shallower than the model. KIC 3955867 is the more magnetically active of the two RG/EBs. In contrast, we find that only the oscillating systems have excess H α absorption. This trend is least pronounced in KIC 8702921 and most pronounced in KIC 7037405, yet present in all of the oscillating systems.

The strong H α absorption is most likely not due to instrumental effects, because it appears consistently in some stars and not others. We verify it is not a strong function of the stellar atmosphere model spectrum used by testing adjacent Coelho (2014) HIGHRES spectra in T_{eff} and $\log g$ grids. It is not a result of a resolution mismatch, which would manifest itself across all the spectral lines and not just H α . There are some narrow telluric water molecule absorption features in the vicinity of H α , but if these were strong contributors to the line profile there would be a corresponding disagreement between the disentangled spectrum and the model spectrum immediately blueward of H α as well (e.g., see Figure 2 in Eaton 1995), and this is not observed. It cannot be due to interstellar reddening because that would weaken the line rather than strengthen it. We further checked to see if the H α line varies significantly over time and has been poorly averaged in some way via the disentangling process. This is difficult to test because the original spectra are SB2, but it does not appear to be the case. The excess H α absorption is almost certainly real and only present in the long-period oscillators.

Generally speaking, red giant stars have remarkably consistent H α line profiles (Eaton 1995), so any deviation from expectations is interesting. The line

is usually strong, indicating the chromosphere is continuous over the whole star, and may indicate excessive chromospheric activity. We note that because H I lines are formed throughout the atmosphere of a star, their profiles are more complicated to model accurately than, for instance, Fe I. The HIGHRES model spectra from Coelho (2014) also assume local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE), and this type of model is known to produce cores of strong lines that are too shallow (Gray 2008). That being said, Robinson et al. (1990) finds that some cool main sequence stars have excess H α absorption which can be related to Ca II H & K emission, but there is not a one-to-one correlation. This was briefly discussed in Section 2.6.3. Such a relationship is illustrated in Figure 4.21, which shows two pairs of main sequence stars with similar effective temperatures (4100 K and 3300 K). In both cases, the star with Ca II H & K emission has a correspondingly deeper and stronger H α absorption feature. This leads us to tentatively conclude that the oscillating RG/EBs with strong H α have some level of chromospheric activity, but not enough to cause emission in the Ca II $\lambda\lambda$ 8498, 8542 lines, increase *Kepler* photometric variability above about 1%, or suppress solar-like oscillations entirely.

At face value, this conclusion weakens our claim in Chapter 2, which stated that the oscillating star in KIC 9246715 is more likely “Star 2” due to its weaker H α absorption. This star’s H α profile agrees better with a model spectrum than does “Star 1.” However, KIC 9246715 has the highest level of *Kepler* photometric variability among the oscillating systems, so this argument may still be valid. Among the other systems with oscillating giants, only KIC 8702921 has oscillations with damped amplitudes (Patrick Gaulme, private communication). The nature of the suppressed modes in that giant, those in KIC 9246715, and the nonexistent modes in KIC 9291629 and KIC 3955867 appear to be from a physical

Fig. 4.21.— Strong $H\alpha$ absorption may be linked to Ca II H \& K emission, and therefore chromospheric activity. The faint dotted profiles belong to main sequence stars with Ca II H \& K absorption while the solid line profiles belong to main sequence stars with Ca II H \& K emission. Left: two dwarf stars with temps around 4100 K and Ca II flux differing by more than a factor of five. Right: two dwarf stars with temps around 3300 K and Ca II flux differing by a factor of 2.5. The top panels show the difference of the spectra below. Figure 10 from Robinson et al. (1990).

process which affects all modes equally. This differs from the magnetically-linked mode suppression mechanism presented in Fuller et al. (2015), which preferentially affects dipole oscillation modes ($\ell = 1$). Instead, the upper convection region of the stars is being deformed or disrupted in a way that does not allow the star to continue “ringing” over all frequencies.

Overall, we conclude that net emission in Ca II together with a high level of photometric variability above 15% correlates with absent oscillations, and that a

combination of enhanced H α absorption with photometric variability above about 1% may predict damped oscillations. But what causes such visible effects of stellar activity in the first place? The underlying cause of photometric variability coupled with either CaII emission or enhanced H α absorption may be linked to the tidal forces associated with being in a binary.

4.4. The Effect of Tidal Forces on Solar-like Oscillations in Red Giants in Binary Systems

In our discussion of magnetic activity, we have implicitly treated each red giant like a single star, when in fact they are all binaries. In two cases, we see a high level of magnetic activity associated with short orbital periods and no solar-like oscillations. In four cases, we see a moderate level of magnetic activity associated with long orbital periods and strong solar-like oscillations. The remaining two RG/EBs are damped oscillators with what appears to be an intermediate level of magnetic activity; one has a short orbital period (KIC 8702921) and one a long period (KIC 9246715).

To investigate how the red giants in each binary have been tidally affected by their companion over the course of stellar evolution, we analyze the MESA models described in Section 4.2. In Figure 4.22, we use results from MESA to evaluate Equation (4.2) and follow the approach of Verbunt & Phinney (1995) to present each system’s observed eccentricity versus the expected expected lifetime change in eccentricity. Binaries with $\log[-(\Delta \ln e)] > 0$, to the left of the dotted line, are predicted to have circular orbits. Those with $\log[-(\Delta \ln e)] < 0$, on the other hand, to the right of the dotted line, have not had sufficient time to theoretically circularize their orbits.

Fig. 4.22.— Expected change in eccentricity over RG/EB lifetimes (x -axis) compared to the observed eccentricity. Each system is color-coded by its orbital period; darker (redder) systems have longer orbital periods than lighter (yellow) ones. Those which fall to the left of the dotted line are predicted to have circularized their orbits ($e \sim 0$) due to tidal effects, while those to the right are not. This plot follows the same form as Figure 4 in Verbut & Phinney (1995).

Of course, this estimation of tidal effects is not exact. It assumes straightforward coevolution, which is consistent with all the RG/EBs but not guaranteed; it assumes the 1D stellar evolution model made with MESA is correct; and it oversimplifies a full physical treatment of tidal forces via the equilibrium tide. It further assumes each binary is well-separated at all times. For a thorough review of these and other assumptions as they pertain to tidal dissipation, see Ogilvie (2014). Still, Figure 4.22 shows many interesting trends. The two non-oscillating systems with nearly-circular orbits and high magnetic activity, KICs 9291629 and 3955867, both appear in the lower left. They are behaving as predicted, with nearly-circularized orbits. The four longest-period systems, which appear as darker (redder) points, are more toward the upper right of the plot. They consistently have higher eccentricities and are not predicted to have circularized.

The exceptions which fall between these two regimes are particularly interesting: KICs 8702921 and 10001167. Interestingly, these two RG/EBs are the only ones in the subset which show subtle phase effects. In the former case, photometric variability is observed at the 1.4% level, and the companion star is a small M dwarf, which may help explain why its orbit is not circularized even though we expect it to be. Yet the quantity on the x -axis in Figure 4.22 explicitly includes the binary mass ratio, so this should be accounted for. This disagreement could be indicating that the scaling relations are inaccurate for KIC 8702921, since we used the asteroseismic mass together with the SB1 dynamic solution to estimate both component masses. Or perhaps, as the smallest and least-evolved giant star in the sample, KIC 8702921 simply needs more time to shift its 5:1 ratio of variability period to orbital period toward 1:1 synchronization before its orbit can circularize, potentially suppressing solar-like oscillations even further.

The other ambiguous case is KIC 10001167, the 120-day orbital period binary with very strong oscillation modes and photometric variability of 0.4%, the most of the long-period systems. However, this variability is more likely due to the strong solar-like oscillations than magnetic activity (Patrick Gaulme, private communication). KIC 10001167 boasts one of the largest giant stars of the subset at $12.73 R_{\odot}$, the lowest mass at $0.857 M_{\odot}$, and therefore the lowest density and surface gravity. It lands right on the cusp of whether or not it is expected to have a circularized orbit. This star appears to represent a case which bridges the regimes of short-period, highly magnetic, tidally disrupted, non-oscillating giants with long-period, less magnetic, non-tidally disrupted, oscillating ones. Its orbit is most likely synchronized with rotation given the phase effects seen in both the *Kepler* and *BVRI* light curves; this would yield a modest rotation speed of about 5.4 km s^{-1} that would not noticeably broaden its spectrum. This together with its highly evolved position on the RGB suggest that KIC 10001167 is in a stable state and not transitioning from one regime to the other.

One may almost draw a line of decreasing magnetic activity from the lower left toward the upper right of Figure 4.22. This is highly suggestive of many short-period, circularized systems having some sort of tidally-exacerbated magnetic surface features which long-period eccentric systems lack. It is unclear whether there is a causal link here, however, and more RG/EBs are needed to determine whether this is a real trend. We can definitively say there are no trends with system age, which is unsurprising given the range of red giant masses. All the RG/EBs must have different ages to have different masses yet all be RGBs simultaneously. There does not appear to be any trend between tidal evolution or magnetic activity and whether the giant star has passed through the RGB luminosity bump. According

to the MESA models, the three short-period systems and the longest-period system are all early in the RGB phase of life (pre-bump) while the rest are relatively more evolved (post-bump), but not necessarily older. There are also no trends found between oscillation behavior and metallicity.

The picture emerging from a look at tidal evolution together with magnetic activity is intriguing but incomplete. To learn which trends persist among giant stars in general and which do not, it is necessary to observe a larger set of both RGB and red clump stars in binaries and as single stars. The fact that both stars in KIC 9246715 have evolved through the tip of the RGB and onto the red clump may explain some of this system’s oddities, and we have only begun to fill in the continuum of oscillating RG/EB behavior. In the most extreme cases, tidally-induced pulsations in so-called “heartbeat stars” drown out solar-like oscillations entirely as tidal forces rhythmically stretch the star’s convection zone over highly eccentric orbits (Thompson et al. 2012). A step down from this appears to be non-oscillating binaries with circularized orbits and magnetic activity. At the opposite end of the spectrum lie long-period binaries containing solar-like oscillators with minimal activity. These stars appear much as they would without a binary companion.

4.5. Conclusions

We have used a combination of high-resolution disentangled spectra and stellar evolution models based on dynamic masses to investigate trends among stellar activity, tidal forces, and solar-like oscillation behavior in eight RG/EBs. Broadly speaking, we find two types of systems: those with short orbital periods, syn-

chronous rotation, high levels of magnetic activity, and no solar-like oscillations, and those with long orbital periods, non-synchronous rotation, low levels of magnetic activity, and strong solar-like oscillations. For various reasons, three systems do not fit perfectly in one category or the other. All of the systems are consistent with coevolution, and all except the double red giant KIC 9246715 (see Chapter 2) have an RGB star as the giant component.

Magnetic activity is measured in two ways: with photometric variability in *Kepler* light curves from Gaulme et al. (2014), and by examining how the H α absorption line and the CaII $\lambda\lambda$ 8498, 8542 lines compare with stellar atmosphere models. We find that high photometric variability tends to occur in tandem with CaII $\lambda\lambda$ 8498, 8542 emission and predict a lack of solar-like oscillations. We further find that photometric variability around the 1–2% level together with a slight excess of H α absorption may predict damped solar-like oscillations, and that minimal photometric variability paired with extreme H α absorption correlates with strong solar-like oscillations.

These trends roughly follow the expected tidal evolution of each RG/EB, which is modeled using the 1D stellar evolution program MESA and a simplified equilibrium tide calculation that considers the stellar mass ratio and orbital period together with the red giant star’s evolution. Short-period binaries tend to have tidally circularized orbits, be more magnetically active, and have suppressed oscillation amplitudes while long-period binaries tend to have eccentric orbits, be less magnetically active, and have strong solar-like oscillations.

5. GALACTIC CONTEXT AND SUMMARY

5.1. Introduction

Throughout this dissertation, we have focused on detailed modeling and analysis of eight RG/EBs in order to better understand what physical processes can inhibit solar-like oscillations in stars. In this final Chapter, we use what we have discovered to place these RG/EBs in a greater context within the Milky Way Galaxy. They are useful benchmarks that enable more than just studying stellar interiors and testing asteroseismic scaling relations. As some of the best-studied stars, they have the potential to serve as reference points for present and future surveys, and they are the first known members of a useful population that can only grow in number with time.

5.2. Red Giant Binaries in the Milky Way Galaxy

Given that each of the SB2 binaries in the RG/EB subset has a known sky position and stellar components with well-defined radii and effective temperatures, it is possible to compute distances. We use the JKTABSDIM¹ program (Southworth et al. 2005) to calculate distances, which uses orbital parameters of each binary, theoretical bolometric corrections from Girardi et al. (2002), updated extinction estimates from the KIC (Brown et al. 2011; Huber et al. 2014), and *JHK* magnitudes from the Two Micron All Sky Survey (2MASS, Skrutskie et al. 2006). The results are shown in Figure 5.1, which plots galactic height versus radius, and Figure 5.2, which is a still frame of a 3D rendering with contours defining the Milky Way plane for reference. The point colors correspond to metallicity. No

¹<http://www.astro.keele.ac.uk/jkt/codes/jktabsdim.html>

clear galactic metallicity gradient is observed, though we note the small number of stars in the sample makes this unsurprising. The derived distances are 2.97 ± 0.14 kpc for KIC 9291629, 2.69 ± 0.08 kpc for KIC 3955867, 0.83 ± 0.04 kpc for KIC 10001167, 3.58 ± 0.11 kpc for KIC 5786154, 1.96 ± 0.06 kpc for KIC 7037405, 0.59 ± 0.02 kpc for KIC 9246715, and 1.15 ± 0.07 kpc for KIC 9970396. All the stars are clearly along similar lines of sight as viewed from our Solar System because they all fall in the *Kepler* field of view.

In addition to the observations presented so far, several other sources have measured parameters for some of the RG/EBs in our subset. The revised KIC (Huber et al. 2014) is one source of stellar parameters for all *Kepler* targets. Six of the eight RG/EBs were observed at least once by APOGEE (Alam et al. 2015), and we used 25 APOGEE spectra of KIC 7037405 for giant star radial velocity measurements in Section 3.2.3. Since just a few points were available for the other four APOGEE targets and we can only extract velocities for the giant component in the near-infrared, they were not used. However, the APOGEE pipeline estimates parameters for the stars it observes whenever possible. The APOGEE DR12 (Holtzman et al. 2015) includes measurements for KICs 3955867, 7037405, 8702921, 9970396, and 10001167, but not KIC 9246715, because it was too strongly double-lined for the ASPCAP pipeline (García Pérez et al. 2015). Distances based on APOGEE parameters which use isochrone fits from Bressan et al. (2012) are also available for these stars (Hayden et al. 2014). Another recent study used a data-driven approach to measure stellar parameters of APOGEE targets, which include KICs 3955867, 9970396, and 10001167 (*The Cannon*, Ness et al. 2015). Finally, the MESA models from Section 4.2 predict T_{eff} and $\log g$ for each system. We compare T_{eff} , $\log g$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$, and distance values in Figure 5.3.

Fig. 5.1.— Galactic height vs. radius for the RG/EB subset. The black star indicates the location of the Sun, and the points are color-coded by metallicity.

Fig. 5.2.— 3D projection of the RG/EB subset in the Milky Way. This figure is an alternate way of presenting Figure 5.1. Gray contours are concentric circles around the galactic center (black dot) with radii of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 kpc.

Fig. 5.3.— Comparison among T_{eff} , $\log g$, metallicity, and distance. All of the red points are directly used in this work, with values from MOOG (Gaulme et al. 2016) as diamonds and values derived from binary modeling (Section 3.3) as stars. Recall from Section 3.4 that the asteroseismic $\log g$ values are nearly identical to those from binary modeling. Blue circles are from the APOGEE DR12 (Holtzman et al. 2015), green squares are from *The Cannon* (Ness et al. 2015), purple triangles are from the revised KIC (Huber et al. 2014), and orange hexagons are what MESA calculates in the stellar evolution models (Section 4.2).

Overall, T_{eff} measurements have the largest scatter while $\log g$ has more consistent systematic disagreements, as discussed earlier in Sections 2.6.1.4 and 3.4. The distances show good agreement within the reported 20% error bars for APOGEE (Hayden et al. 2014). Our adopted values are all in red: stellar atmosphere modeling with MOOG from Gaulme et al. (2016) in the top three panels (diamonds), ELC-derived from Chapter 3 in the second panel from the top (stars), and distances measured as described above (stars) in the bottom panel.

Using well-characterized RG/EBs to test pipelines that measure stellar parameters demonstrates their ability to calibrate surveys. As more RG/EBs are discovered in archival *Kepler* data, new *K2* data, and by future missions like *TESS* (Ricker et al. 2014), we will be able to use them as references for fundamental stellar parameters across incredibly large datasets. Given sufficient short-cadence observations, we may be able to combine dynamic binary modeling and asteroseismology for oscillating main sequence stars and greatly expand the reach of eclipsing binaries as asteroseismic benchmarks.

In the meantime, it is important to note that samples of evolved stars selected via ensemble asteroseismology will be biased. They will miss magnetically active stars and many close binaries. Depending on the goals of the study, this may or may not be a desirable selection effect. More importantly, populations of giant stars selected asteroseismically will have overestimated masses and radii. This directly affects studies which aim to measure mass-loss rates, the initial mass function, stellar ages, and anything that is a function of stellar evolution.

5.3. Summary and Conclusions

In this dissertation, we have thoroughly characterized a subset of eight RG/EBs observed by *Kepler*. Eclipsing binaries allow us to directly measure stellar properties independently of asteroseismology, which we use to investigate why some red giants don't oscillate and test asteroseismic scaling relations for those that do. We present full dynamic solutions for each system that simultaneously fit a model to a set of light curves and radial velocity curves. By combining orbital solutions, high-resolution spectroscopy, and stellar evolution models, we find short-period binaries tend to have active red giants and strong tidal forces which act to suppress solar-like oscillations. Longer-period binaries tend to have less active red giants and weaker tidal forces which do not affect oscillation modes.

Specifically, all but one of the RG/EBs contain an RGB star with a main sequence companion. Two of these exhibit high magnetic activity coupled with significant tidal forces which have circularized their short (< 35 day) orbits. The magnetic activity is characterized by photometric variations $> 15\%$ and net emission in the CaII $\lambda\lambda 8498, 8542$ lines. These systems lack solar-like oscillations entirely. Four other binaries have low levels of magnetic activity and insufficient tidal forces to circularize their long (> 100 day) orbits, and their solar-like oscillations appear as expected. They tend to exhibit stronger H α absorption in their spectra than predicted from a stellar atmosphere model.

Between these two extremes lie two RG/EBs with different levels of suppressed oscillations. One is a pair of nearly-identical red clump stars with an intermediate level of magnetic activity and tidal forces in a 171 day orbit which has resulted in one star exhibiting damped oscillations and the other apparently

not oscillating at all. The other is a relatively small oscillating red giant with an intermediate level of magnetic activity and insufficient tidal forces from an M dwarf companion to circularize its short 19 day orbit. The companion is so small and dim that its signal cannot be seen to create a radial velocity curve.

Taken together, this subset of RG/EBs demonstrates a link between binaries with tidal forces and magnetic activity and those with missing or damped solar-like oscillations. The five oscillating stars with complete dynamic solutions from binary modeling have been used to test the mass and radius asteroseismic scaling relations, which appear to work in a general sense but fail the most for stars least like the Sun (lower average stellar densities and surface gravities). While density and surface gravity agree reasonably well between the two techniques, the asteroseismic scaling relations systematically overestimate both mass and radius. We predict that future RG/EB classifications will fall along a spectrum: heartbeat stars with tidally-induced pulsations—no oscillations due to strong tidal and/or magnetic effects—stars with tidally and/or magnetically damped solar-like oscillations—and strong solar-like oscillations much like a single star.

Alongside the main science results of this dissertation, we present two suites of python programs in Appendices A and B. One is designed to assist with implementing the broadening function technique to extract radial velocities from spectra, and the other handles input and output for spectral disentangling via Fourier decomposition.

Our findings suggest that future asteroseismic surveys should be aware they are excluding magnetically active stars and close binaries, and that studies relying on properties of stars from asteroseismology should use extreme care when inter-

preting masses and radii due to systematic overestimates of both. These binaries can serve as benchmarks for calibrating stellar parameters from large-scale photometric, asteroseismic, and spectroscopic surveys, and they are quickly becoming some of the best-studied stars.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX A. EXTRACTING RADIAL VELOCITIES WITH THE BROADENING FUNCTION

This appendix reviews the mathematics behind the broadening function (BF) technique for extracting radial velocities from spectra, describes how the BF is applied in this dissertation, and presents a new suite of programs written in python that implement the BF technique and plot the results. Sample plots showing Gaussian fits to BF peaks for both an SB1 and an SB2 are presented, and all the final radial velocities for the RG/EB subset are listed in Table A.1. The BF technique is also briefly discussed in Section 2.3.1 as applied to KIC 9246715.

A.1. Derivation of the BF

The BF technique was originally presented by Rucinski (1992) for the study of AW UMa, and later improved (a detailed discussion appears in Rucinski 2002, with practical details online¹). Stellar spectra are characterized by absorption lines as a function of wavelength, but the shape, width, and location of the lines can change for numerous physical reasons. Consider an observed stellar spectrum S as a convolution of two pieces: an idealized sharp-lined spectrum template T and a function that broadens it in a consistent way, B :

$$S(\lambda) = \int B(\lambda') T(\lambda - \lambda') d\lambda'. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

In essence, the BF technique solves for B by using the observed S , a template T , and a singular value decomposition (SVD) method.

¹<http://www.astro.utoronto.ca/~rucinski/SVDcookbook.html>

The BF is similar to the cross-correlation function (CCF), a common technique used to measure stellar velocities. However, the CCF is nonlinear, which is less than ideal. Linearity means that the relative luminosities of components is directly related to the relative area under each BF peak, the BF has a true baseline of zero, and the BF does not exhibit the same level of peak distortions as the CCF, which is especially important when the goal is to identify a signal from two stars. This is illustrated in Figure A.1. In addition, the BF is well-suited for binaries in which the two stars show extremely different amounts of rotational broadening.

Fig. A.1.— The BF is a better tool for measuring binary star radial velocities than the CCF. Left: spectra of a sharp-line template star, HD 89449, and of a close binary star, KR Com. Right: BF and CCF obtained from the same spectra at left (thick lines). The thin lines show the three fit components for the system in the top right panel, and the thin line replots the BF on top of the CCF for direct comparison in the bottom right panel. Figure 1 from Rucinski (2002).

To solve Equation A.1 for the BF, we consider the problem as an array operation, $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{B}$, in which the rectangular array \mathbf{D} is created from the template vector \mathbf{T} (Rucinski 1992). The spectra must be re-binned into equal steps in velocity. First, both \mathbf{S} and $\mathbf{D}\mathbf{B}$ are multiplied by the transpose \mathbf{D}^T . The new array $\mathbf{D}^T\mathbf{D}$ is then decomposed into $\mathbf{U} \times \mathbf{W} \times \mathbf{V}^T$, where \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V}^T are orthogonal and \mathbf{W} has only diagonal elements. The solution can then be computed for several observed spectra through the relation

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{W}^{-1} (\mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{S}). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The resulting BFs are always noisy, because each element of the solution B_j has been treated as independent. However, spectral resolution is controlled by the spectrograph slit, which means that neighboring BF points are coupled in reality. To reintroduce this to the BFs, we smooth them by convolving them with a Gaussian of $\sigma = 1.5$ pixels (for the ARCÉS echelle). In practice, Rucinski (2002) reports this smoothing has the same effect as rejecting higher-order singular values during SVD, but has the advantage of only acting locally whereas removing some singular values may introduce nonlocal effects.

Finally, to measure velocity differences between the template and target, we use a least-squares method to fit Gaussians to each BF peak. Each Gaussian has three free parameters: height, position (velocity), and width.

A.2. Applying the BF to RG/EB Systems

In the case of eclipsing binary stars, the BF transforms a sharp-lined model atmosphere (or standard star template) into a broadened spectrum of a binary, though it can in principle measure any geometrical line broadening effect. This

determines not only the shape of the BF, but also relates the absolute radial velocities of target spectra to templates at zero velocity.

BFs are computed in a geocentric frame and barycentric velocity corrections are then applied. We experimented with many different spectral templates, including radial velocity standard stars and PHOENIX BT-Settl model atmospheres (Allard et al. 2003) convolved to a resolution similar to ARCES (see Section 2.3.1). Arguments can be made for either approach. Real stellar templates can eliminate systematic velocity errors because they are observed with the same instrument near the same time; however, they include telluric absorption features which introduce a spurious BF peak near zero and pose a problem for binaries with small orbital velocities. They also require additional telescope time to obtain. On the other hand, model stellar atmosphere templates can be created for any desired T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$; however, they do not perfectly reproduce the instrument response function and therefore cannot minimize systematic errors. In the end, we choose to use model stellar atmosphere templates because so many of the RG/EBs have an extremely faint secondary BF peak for the main sequence star; this component is typically $\sim 5\%$ as bright as the red giant. The ability to fine-tune template stellar parameters to make this peak as strong as possible is crucial.

Figures A.2 and A.3 are two examples of typical BFs for KIC 8702921 and KIC 3955867, respectively. Each panel represents a single observation. The template used for KIC 8702921 is a PHOENIX BT-Settl model atmosphere of a main sequence star with $T_{\text{eff}} = 4200$ K. Even with cooler templates, it was not possible to isolate any BF peaks for the extremely faint main sequence component. Thus, KIC 8702921 is a single-lined binary (SB1). KIC 3955867, on the other hand, has a moderately brighter main sequence star. The BF peaks appear most strongly

with a main sequence model atmosphere template that has $T_{\text{eff}} = 5500$ K, making it a double-lined binary (SB2). In comparing these BF fits to those for KIC 9246715 in Figure 2.3, it is clear to see how the light ratio of the components influences the ability to measure radial velocities. In all cases, we use the spectral range 5400–6726 Å, which has a high signal-to-noise ratio and minimal telluric features. Final barycentric-corrected radial velocities for the full RG/EB subset in Chapter 3 are given in Table A.1.

Fig. A.2.— Broadening function fits for KIC 8702921. Each panel represents one spectral observation, ordered chronologically, for which the BF is shown in black. To identify the location of each BF in radial velocity space, we fit a Gaussian, which is plotted in red. The date of observation and orbital phase are printed in the upper corner of each panel. Barycentric corrections have not yet been applied to these velocities.

Fig. A.3.— Broadening function fits as in Figure A.2, but for KIC 3955867. Each panel represents one spectral observation, ordered chronologically, for which the BF is shown in black. To identify the location of each BF in radial velocity space, we fit a Gaussian, which is plotted in red. The date of observation and orbital phase are printed in the upper corner of each panel. Barycentric corrections have not yet been applied to these velocities.

A.3. BF-rvplotter: The BF Technique in Python

In order to apply the BF technique to our observed RG/EB spectra, we wrote a suite of python programs based on the IDL routines by Rucinski.² They are publicly available and documented at <https://github.com/mrawls/BF-rvplotter>, and a top-level description is provided here.

²<http://www.astro.utoronto.ca/~rucinski/BFdescription.html>

The main program is `BF_python.py`, and its dependent functions are in `BF_functions.py`. Additional programs in the repository are useful for plotting spectra, using telluric absorption lines in lieu of radial velocity standard stars, creating a radial velocity curve, and convolving spectra to different resolutions, among other things. `BF_python.py` uses the SVD class from PyAstronomy³ as well as tools from the packages `numpy`, `matplotlib`, `scipy`, `pandas`, `astropy` (Robitaille et al. 2013), and `gaussfitter`.⁴

To begin, `BF_python.py` takes three text infiles. One lists the full file paths to input spectra, which may be either FITS or text files (the first line must be the template), one contains the time of observation (we recommend using BJD observation midpoints) and barycentric velocity (in km s^{-1}) for each input spectrum, and one has a set of guesses for each BF's Gaussian fit parameters (amplitude, location, and width for up to three peaks per observation). The program also requires the binary's orbital period and zeropoint to calculate orbital phases (if set incorrectly, the program will still work; the orbital phase values written out and printed on the multi-pane BF plot will simply be wrong).

The program outputs a series of intermediate plots, which may be toggled on/off, and an output text file containing the final radial velocities. In practice, the user must run `BF_python.py` several times: first to adjust the length and resolution of the BF, next to customize reasonable plot parameters, and finally to iterate on appropriate initial guesses for each Gaussian fit.

³<https://github.com/sczesla/PyAstronomy>

⁴<https://github.com/keflavich/gaussfitter>

Table A.1. Radial velocities measured for the RG/EB subset

UTC Date	Midpoint ^a	Phase	v_1 (km s ⁻¹)	v_2 (km s ⁻¹)
KIC 8702921 ^b				
2012 May 25	6072.858652	0.883	-1.48(7)	...
2012 May 25	6072.930101	0.887	-1.21(7)	...
2012 Jun 12	6090.856560	0.811	1.54(8)	...
2012 Jun 27	6105.713648	0.578	-1.28(7)	...
2012 Aug 26	6165.918776	0.684	1.07(8)	...
2012 Aug 27	6166.923172	0.735	1.62(8)	...
2012 Sep 03	6173.859859	0.093	-19.91(8)	...
2013 Apr 20	6402.902536	0.909	-3.72(8)	...
2013 May 12	6424.879134	0.043	-15.99(8)	...
2013 Jun 01	6444.942672	0.078	-18.60(7)	...
2013 Aug 12	6516.671786	0.778	1.95(8)	...
2013 Oct 05	6570.605874	0.561	-2.25(7)	...
2013 Oct 09	6574.656364	0.770	2.21(8)	...
2014 Apr 25	6772.960301	1.000	-12.52(8)	...
2014 May 14	6791.967642	0.980	-10.18(8)	...
2014 Jun 05	6813.962418	0.115	-21.36(7)	...
2014 Jun 15	6823.946494	0.630	0.95(8)	...
2014 Oct 14	6944.736670	0.861	-1.58(7)	...
2014 Oct 16	6946.694266	0.962	-8.52(7)	...
2014 Oct 24	6954.636842	0.372	-17.51(7)	...
2014 Oct 28	6958.733051	0.583	-1.82(8)	...
2014 Oct 29	6959.780492	0.637	-0.17(8)	...
KIC 9291629				
2013 Sep 02	6537.722016	0.935	-50.07(19)	-9.79(30)
2013 Sep 09	6544.786084	0.277	20.94(20)	-80.22(39)
2013 Oct 09	6574.756502	0.726	-80.44(19)	18.71(31)
2014 Apr 22	6769.944171	0.161	12.57(19)	-73.22(34)
2014 May 14	6791.857844	0.220	17.64(19)	-79.06(53)
2014 Jun 05	6813.899006	0.286	18.67(18)	-80.08(39)
2014 Jul 27	6865.661220	0.788	-79.46(18)	19.40(43)
2014 Sep 02	6902.666721	0.577	-53.73(19)	-6.87(34)
2014 Oct 14	6944.636871	0.606	-61.50(18)	0.85(39)
2014 Oct 16	6946.626580	0.702	-78.80(18)	18.11(36)
2014 Oct 24	6954.566738	0.086	-3.43(19)	-56.03(33)

Table A.1 (continued)

UTC Date	Midpoint ^a	Phase	v_1 (km s ⁻¹)	v_2 (km s ⁻¹)
2014 Oct 24	6954.772716	0.096	-3.64(19)	-61.76(32)
2014 Oct 28	6958.716742	0.287	17.67(18)	-80.91(39)
2014 Oct 29	6959.764249	0.337	10.47(18)	-76.19(37)
2015 May 06	7148.921210	0.481	-20.18(97)	-35.61(59)
KIC 3955867				
2013 Sep 02	6537.744095	0.851	-16.05(12)	51.68(79)
2013 Oct 09	6574.775382	0.951	1.31(12)	30.09(88)
2013 Nov 03	6599.552699	0.687	-19.30(11)	57.66(11)
2014 Apr 22	6769.966889	0.750	-22.76(11)	61.69(08)
2014 May 14	6791.940043	0.403	37.08(14)	-8.54(11)
2014 Jun 15	6823.879356	0.352	45.79(12)	-19.88(36)
2014 Jul 27	6865.642585	0.593	-5.58(12)	40.72(90)
2014 Oct 14	6944.718961	0.943	0.54(11)	31.50(41)
2014 Oct 16	6946.559237	0.997	14.64(12)	...
2014 Oct 24	6954.601273	0.236	52.59(11)	-30.14(89)
2014 Oct 28	6958.753222	0.360	43.56(12)	...
2014 Oct 29	6959.744627	0.389	37.91(12)	-14.87(56)
2015 Apr 07	7119.977524	0.150	45.36(11)	-21.38(57)
2015 May 06	7148.825113	0.007	16.14(11)	...
2015 May 06	7148.850024	0.008	16.59(11)	...
KIC 10001167				
2013 Apr 20	6402.811072	0.004	-107.69(4)	...
2013 May 12	6424.817710	0.186	-83.37(4)	-122.58(37)
2013 Jun 01	6444.813717	0.353	-84.12(4)	-122.81(20)
2013 Jun 13	6456.850012	0.453	-90.57(4)	-118.36(35)
2013 Jul 08	6481.816657	0.660	-116.94(4)	-86.33(50)
2013 Aug 26	6530.728436	0.066	-95.45(4)	-112.07(50)
2013 Sep 09	6544.602074	0.181	-83.78(4)	-122.81(44)
2013 Oct 05	6570.567252	0.397	-86.68(4)	-121.76(38)
2013 Oct 09	6574.609915	0.431	-89.60(4)	-121.05(04)
2013 Nov 02	6598.599819	0.630	-114.07(4)	-93.45(87)
2014 May 14	6791.750162	0.234	-81.64(8)	...
2014 May 23	6800.951358	0.311	-82.19(4)	-122.35(78)
2014 Jun 05	6813.916188	0.418	-87.64(4)	-120.89(60)
2014 Jun 15	6823.820991	0.501	-95.87(4)	...

Table A.1 (continued)

UTC Date	Midpoint ^a	Phase	v_1 (km s ⁻¹)	v_2 (km s ⁻¹)
2014 Jul 27	6865.695046	0.849	-130.26(4)	-72.23(61)
2014 Oct 14	6944.663256	0.504	-97.56(4)	-112.59(50)
2014 Oct 16	6946.663321	0.521	-100.04(4)	...
2014 Oct 24	6954.549986	0.587	-106.63(4)	...
2014 Oct 28	6958.542440	0.620	-111.28(5)	-92.71(06)
2014 Nov 01	6962.639875	0.654	-116.86(5)	-92.21(84)
2015 Apr 07	7119.995840	0.961	-113.91(4)	-92.06(20)
KIC 5786154				
2012 Jun 27	6105.787040	0.765	-17.16(2)	...
2012 Sep 03	6173.830910	0.109	19.10(2)	...
2013 Apr 20	6402.887380	0.267	6.49(2)	-17.13(42)
2013 May 12	6424.935620	0.378	-15.03(2)	2.05(05)
2013 Jun 01	6444.880450	0.479	-21.27(2)	8.48(46)
2013 Jun 13	6456.898550	0.539	-22.68(2)	11.69(26)
2013 Sep 02	6537.624070	0.947	-4.94(2)	...
2013 Sep 09	6544.625520	0.983	1.25(2)	-12.35(24)
2013 Oct 09	6574.595030	0.134	26.26(2)	-38.24(32)
2013 Nov 02	6598.645520	0.256	9.62(2)	...
2014 Apr 25	6772.877390	0.136	25.15(2)	-40.56(27)
2014 Jun 05	6813.931650	0.343	-9.30(2)	...
2014 Jul 27	6865.729550	0.605	-22.03(2)	10.87(12)
2014 Sep 02	6902.775870	0.792	-16.79(2)	...
2014 Oct 14	6944.571080	0.004	4.26(2)	...
2014 Oct 16	6946.578900	0.014	5.45(2)	-18.11(23)
2014 Oct 24	6954.708110	0.055	9.31(2)	-22.49(11)
2014 Oct 28	6958.675460	0.075	13.28(2)	-27.53(28)
2014 Oct 29	6959.724760	0.080	13.64(2)	-29.43(32)
2014 Nov 01	6962.594460	0.095	18.22(2)	-32.63(15)
2015 Oct 25	7320.732980	0.904	-8.26(2)	...
2015 Nov 13	7339.540340	0.999	3.05(3)	...
KIC 7037405				
2013 Jun 13	6456.916350	0.490	-44.44(4)	-31.55(89)
2013 Sep 22	6557.733352	0.977	-40.61(10) ^c	...
2013 Sep 24	6559.723285	0.987	-38.44(11) ^c	...
2013 Sep 25	6560.721014	0.991	-37.36(11) ^c	...

Table A.1 (continued)

UTC Date	Midpoint ^a	Phase	v_1 (km s ⁻¹)	v_2 (km s ⁻¹)
2013 Oct 19	6584.632204	0.107	-14.31(11) ^c	...
2013 Oct 20	6585.630708	0.112	-13.69(11) ^c	...
2014 Apr 10	6757.892997	0.943	-46.42(10) ^c	...
2014 Apr 11	6758.902344	0.948	-45.57(12) ^c	...
2014 Apr 13	6760.905764	0.958	-43.88(10) ^c	...
2014 Apr 14	6761.872858	0.963	-42.92(11) ^c	...
2014 Apr 15	6762.868652	0.967	-42.08(10) ^c	...
2014 Apr 16	6763.881170	0.972	-41.13(10) ^c	...
2014 Apr 22	6769.912040	0.001	-35.26(3)	...
2014 May 06	6783.835690	0.069	-20.50(10) ^c	...
2014 May 07	6784.821974	0.073	-19.69(10) ^c	...
2014 May 08	6785.825446	0.078	-18.76(10) ^c	...
2014 May 09	6786.798470	0.083	-17.98(10) ^c	...
2014 May 10	6787.809358	0.088	-17.28(10) ^c	...
2014 May 11	6788.843091	0.093	-16.47(10) ^c	...
2014 May 14	6791.767270	0.107	-15.22(4)	-67.58(53)
2014 May 23	6800.940870	0.151	-11.77(3)	-67.95(82)
2014 Jun 04	6812.745069	0.208	-13.74(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 05	6813.813580	0.213	-14.84(3)	-64.99(79)
2014 Jun 06	6814.755451	0.218	-14.61(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 07	6815.785503	0.223	-14.95(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 08	6816.766252	0.228	-15.52(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 09	6817.761959	0.232	-15.87(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 10	6818.764558	0.237	-16.31(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 11	6819.762190	0.242	-17.01(11) ^c	...
2014 Jun 12	6820.755988	0.247	-17.43(10) ^c	...
2014 Jun 15	6823.809960	0.262	-19.47(3)	-59.06(81)
2014 Jul 27	6865.624120	0.464	-42.64(3)	...
2014 Sep 02	6902.634520	0.642	-55.72(3)	-21.12(88)
2014 Oct 14	6944.554730	0.845	-56.78(3)	...
2014 Oct 16	6946.597250	0.854	-56.50(3)	-20.49(79)
2014 Oct 24	6954.585730	0.893	-53.13(3)	-23.05(83)
2014 Oct 28	6958.608290	0.913	-51.09(3)	-24.19(82)
2014 Oct 29	6959.625870	0.917	-50.67(3)	-26.36(94)
2014 Nov 01	6962.563310	0.932	-48.59(3)	-27.50(65)
2015 Apr 07	7119.959980	0.692	-58.05(3)	-19.31(96)
2015 May 06	7148.957990	0.832	-57.50(3)	-19.28(91)
2015 Sep 30	7295.562020	0.539	-50.71(5)	...
2015 Oct 13	7308.780730	0.603	-53.66(3)	-23.34(69)

Table A.1 (continued)

UTC Date	Midpoint ^a	Phase	v_1 (km s ⁻¹)	v_2 (km s ⁻¹)
2015 Oct 25	7320.631430	0.661	-55.83(3)	-19.43(75)
2015 Nov 13	7339.608540	0.752	-59.54(3)	-18.82(80)
KIC 9970396				
2013 Apr 20	6402.951560	0.153	6.63(2)	-43.86(39)
2013 May 12	6424.962840	0.246	4.21(2)	...
2013 Jun 01	6444.954710	0.331	-3.76(2)	-29.90(62)
2013 Jun 13	6456.838920	0.382	-10.27(2)	-23.48(20)
2013 Aug 26	6530.791870	0.696	-33.74(2)	3.16(58)
2013 Sep 09	6544.672160	0.755	-34.64(2)	4.11(47)
2013 Oct 05	6570.578500	0.865	-30.52(2)	1.43(51)
2013 Oct 09	6574.578920	0.882	-29.26(2)	0.00(44)
2014 Apr 25	6772.857650	0.725	-35.19(2)	4.41(30)
2014 May 14	6791.783290	0.805	-33.76(3)	6.52(53)
2014 Jun 05	6813.881230	0.899	-27.58(2)	-0.27(62)
2014 Jun 15	6823.910840	0.942	-22.65(2)	...
2014 Jul 27	6865.748570	0.120	6.01(2)	...
2014 Sep 02	6902.791940	0.277	0.45(2)	-35.80(32)
2014 Oct 14	6944.588530	0.455	-17.17(2)	...
2014 Oct 16	6946.745550	0.464	-20.41(2)	...
2014 Oct 24	6954.692870	0.498	-22.55(2)	-8.87(32)
2014 Oct 28	6958.594850	0.514	-22.54(2)	-6.43(36)
2014 Oct 28	6958.782810	0.515	-25.14(2)	-10.14(28)
2014 Oct 29	6959.573040	0.518	-22.75(2)	-7.95(22)
2014 Nov 01	6962.578730	0.531	-24.04(2)	-7.02(17)
2015 Oct 13	7308.763190	0.002	-14.59(2)	...
2015 Oct 25	7320.749410	0.053	-5.29(2)	-32.74(58)

^aExposure midpoint timestamp, (BJD-2450000).

^bThis system is an SB1.

^cThese velocities are from APOGEE.

APPENDIX B. SPECTRAL DECOMPOSITION WITH FDBINARY (FD3)

Spectroscopy is one of an observational astronomer’s greatest tools. Encoded into stellar absorption lines is information about everything from motion to temperature to magnetic activity. Spectra of eclipsing binaries can tell us about the physical properties of both stars, as shown in Appendix A for orbital motion. In order to measure properties of each star’s atmosphere, however, it is necessary to isolate which pieces of overlapping observed spectra correspond to which star. An elegant solution to spectral disentangling is presented in Ilijić et al. (2004) with the code FDBinary (later renamed fd3), which we review here. We then describe how this method is applied to our subset of RG/EBs to create the spectra presented in Chapter 4 and Section 2.4.1, and conclude with an overview of a suite of python tools to assist with running FDBinary (fd3) and interpreting the results.

B.1. The Method of Fourier Decomposition

The goal of spectral disentangling is to use the known orbital parameters of a spectroscopic binary to reconstruct the individual spectra of each component star. We begin by considering a set of observed spectra greater than the number of components in the system (i.e., for a binary, we require at minimum three spectra taken at different times; for best results, they should be taken at a range of orbital phases and include an observation taken during eclipse). The spectra must be continuum-normalized on a grid of N points that are re-binned into equal steps in $\ln \lambda$. We then write the separation problem in Fourier space, following the approach of Ilijić et al. (2004). For $j = 1, \dots, M$ observed composite spectra,

Y_{ji} sampled at $i = 1 \dots N$, the goal is to combine them to arrive at the unknown component spectra X_1 and X_2 . These each have discrete Fourier transforms with amplitudes of y_{jn} , x_{1n} , and x_{2n} , respectively, with $n = 0, \dots, N/2$.

For each n , we can then write a system of M linear equations that relate the input spectra amplitudes to that of each component star:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma_j} \sum_{k=1,2} \ell_{kj} e^{-i\frac{2\pi n}{N}\beta_{kj}} x_{kn} = \frac{y_{jn}}{\sigma_j} \quad j = 1, \dots, M. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Here, ℓ_{kj} is the light factor of component k of the composite spectrum j and β_{kj} is the radial velocity shift of component k relative to the composite spectrum j . The noise in spectrum j is characterized by an rms of σ_j . Equation B.1 can be rewritten as $\mathbf{Y}_n = \mathbf{F}_n \mathbf{X}_n$, where the vector \mathbf{Y} contains each y_{jn}/σ_j , the components of the vector \mathbf{X} are unknown, and the design matrix \mathbf{F} contains information about radial velocities and light factors. This can be solved via singular value decomposition (SVD), as in Section A.1. A comprehensive mathematical description of the disentangling process is in Hensberge et al. (2008).

The main drawbacks to this technique are that it treats the model spectrum of each component as periodic functions, assumes the continuum has been perfectly normalized across the entire wavelength interval, and requires a set of observations that are well-sampled in orbital phase. Edge effects can distort disentangled line profiles if they fall closer than about two times the largest radial velocity amplitude from the end of a wavelength region (Hensberge et al. 2008), so it is important to have sufficiently long wavelength intervals. On the other hand, imperfect normalization and poor phase coverage can introduce undulations in the continuum of the disentangled spectra. For this reason, it is important to use wavelength intervals that are not too long. We typically process the input

composite spectra in smaller “chunks” on order 10–50 Å in length, which is a compromise that serves to minimize both undesirable edge effects and undulating continua in practice. It is also important that the continuum be at the same level at both ends of each chunk to avoid erroneous spikes.

B.2. Applying FDBinary (fd3) to RG/EB Systems

To use the FDBinary (fd3) technique on eclipsing binary spectra, it is necessary to provide an orbital solution parameterized by the orbital period, zeropoint, eccentricity, argument of periastron, and radial velocity semi-amplitude of each star. FDBinary includes the capability to fit for any combination of these; the fitting algorithm is not very robust, however, and in practice we find that it often prefers local minima. We therefore input fixed values for each parameter from a dynamic binary model (from, e.g., ELC; see Section 2.5) and only use the built-in iterative fitting capability in select cases to refine the zeropoint. It is important to note that the zeropoint input must be the time of periastron rather than the time of deepest eclipse.

FDBinary is able to handle binaries of type SB1, SB2, and SB2 with a third light source. In this work, we use FDBinary only for SB2 systems, because it is straightforward to manually co-add SB1 spectra when an orbital solution is known. The final input value required by FDBinary is the light ratio of the stars in each observed composite spectrum. This can be determined in several ways: by comparing the broadening function peak heights or areas, by combining a star’s radius and temperature, provided both are well-constrained ($L \propto R^2 T_{\text{eff}}^4$), or by measuring eclipse depths in different bandpasses. For the RG/EB subset, we

assume a light ratio of 95% to 5% for all the SB2 systems with main sequence companions, and a light ratio of unity for the double red giant KIC 9246715.

Disentangled spectra created with FDBinary are presented in Sections 2.4.1 and 4.2, and a portion of each disentangled spectrum used in this dissertation are in Figures 2.5, 4.3, 4.6, 4.9, 4.12, 4.15, and 4.18. For the double red giant KIC 9246715, which has a light ratio near unity, the disentangled spectra were used for stellar atmosphere modeling (see Section 2.4.2). For KIC 9246715 as well as the rest of the RG/EB subset, disentangled spectra are further used to investigate lines that may be sensitive to magnetic activity. The results are available in Sections 2.6.3 and 4.2.

B.3. FDBinary-tools: Programs to Assist With FDBinary (fd3)

In practice, using FDBinary to process spectra and analyze the results requires some intermediate steps. With this in mind, we present a suite of python programs to prepare input for the main FDBinary program and process the output. They are publicly available at <https://github.com/mrawls/FDBinary-tools>, and an overview is provided here. These programs use tools from the python packages `numpy`, `matplotlib`, and `astropy` (Robitaille et al. 2013).

Essentially, the user begins with several reduced 1D FITS spectra of a binary target and ends with a pair of spectra, one for each star, as both FITS files and plain text files. However, it is important to understand what the main FDBinary program requires to yield a good result. The first program, `spectra2txt.py`, takes a list of FITS files and turns them into the necessary format for FDBinary. This includes correcting for barycentric velocities, subtracting any systemic velocity,

resampling the wavelength grid so it is evenly spaced in $\ln \lambda$, and writing this all to a single text file.

Next, the program `make_fdbinary_infile.py` helps the user create one control file for each time they plan to run `FDBinary`. In cases where a long spectrum is broken into several smaller “chunks” to avoid the undulating continuum problem mentioned in Section B.1, creating a set of control files simultaneously may be useful. Finally, the program `fdbinary_plot.py` processes the files created by `FDBinary` and plots the freshly disentangled spectra. An additional program in the repository, `fdbinary_rvs.py`, creates a plot to compare the true radial velocity points to those from the model `FDBinary` generates from the orbital parameters provided. It is a good idea for the user to check that these velocity curves roughly agree and ensure the binary orbital parameters have been entered correctly.

APPENDIX C. FIT OSCILLATION MODES FOR KIC 9246715

In this Appendix, which originally appears in Rawls et al. (2016), we present the frequencies fit by DIAMONDS (Corsaro & De Ridder 2014), as described in Section 2.6.1.2. We follow the methodology for the peak bagging analysis of a red giant star in Corsaro et al. (2015). Each fit mode’s frequency together with its angular degree ℓ , azimuthal order m , amplitude or height, linewidth (when applicable), and probability of detection is listed in Table C.1. Figure C.1 shows these modes superimposed on the power density spectrum of KIC 9246715, which is split up like an échelle diagram for clarity. For comparison, we also plot the locations of where modes should fall according to the asymptotic relation (Mosser et al. 2012) for the main set of oscillations ($\Delta\nu = 8.31 \mu\text{Hz}$) and the marginally detected second set of oscillations ($\Delta\nu = 8.60 \mu\text{Hz}$). The power spectrum is quite noisy overall, exhibits wide modes with low amplitudes, and is challenging to interpret unambiguously. For a full discussion, see Section 2.6.

Fig. C.1.— Power spectral density (PSD) of KIC 9246715 as function of frequency, in the form of an échelle diagram (compare to Figure 2.8). The PSD has been whitened, or divided by the background fitting, which casts the y -axis in terms of sigma. Solid blue lines indicate the universal pattern for an oscillator with $\Delta\nu = 8.31 \mu\text{Hz}$ (main oscillator), while red lines indicate the same for $\Delta\nu = 8.60 \mu\text{Hz}$ (marginal detection). Dark green triangles correspond to the location of fit peaks from DIAMONDS (Table C.1). The width of each triangle’s base is the mode linewidth from the fit, and taller triangles represent higher detection confidence. Figure from Rawls et al. (2016).

Table C.1. Oscillation modes in KIC 9246715 fit with DIAMONDS

Frequency (μHz)	(ℓ, m)	Amplitude or Height ^a (ppm) or ($\text{ppm}^2 \mu\text{Hz}^{-1}$)	Linewidth (μHz)	Detection Probability ^b
76.50 ± 0.01	(0, 0)	5.2 ± 0.4	0.61 ± 0.05	0.91
84.43 ± 0.02	(0, 0)	10.9 ± 0.4	0.60 ± 0.05	1.00
92.54 ± 0.01	(0, 0)	13.2 ± 0.3	0.36 ± 0.02	1.00
100.75 ± 0.02	(0, 0)	15.7 ± 0.6	0.60 ± 0.07	1.00
109.06 ± 0.01	(0, 0)	14.6 ± 0.4	0.46 ± 0.03	1.00
117.37 ± 0.01	(0, 0)	12.6 ± 0.4	0.30 ± 0.02	1.00
125.92 ± 0.04	(0, 0)	9.8 ± 0.7	0.48 ± 0.07	1.00
134.53 ± 0.02	(0, 0)	9.1 ± 0.7	0.91 ± 0.07	1.00
87.714 ± 0.001	(1, ?)	402 $\begin{smallmatrix} +11 \\ -12 \end{smallmatrix}$...	0.97
88.40 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	1.6 ± 0.1	0.088 ± 0.006	0.75
88.70 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	5.0 ± 0.2	0.26 ± 0.02	0.99
89.19 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	1.7 ± 0.1	0.17 ± 0.01	0.585
89.422 ± 0.001	(1, 1)	461 $\begin{smallmatrix} +11 \\ -12 \end{smallmatrix}$...	0.99
96.12 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	2.8 ± 0.5	0.10 ± 0.01	0.90
96.62 ± 0.02	(1, -1)	7.6 ± 1.0	0.35 ± 0.06	0.56
97.00 ± 0.03	(1, 1)	7.9 ± 1.0	0.34 ± 0.05	0.80
103.26 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	3.7 ± 0.2	0.23 ± 0.02	0.19
103.66 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	6.3 ± 0.4	0.33 ± 0.03	0.10
104.67 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	6.1 ± 0.3	0.17 ± 0.01	1.00
105.04 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	8.7 ± 0.4	0.18 ± 0.02	1.00
105.50 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	5.9 ± 0.3	0.14 ± 0.01	0.99
105.89 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	8.4 ± 0.5	0.33 ± 0.03	1.00
111.940 ± 0.001	(1, -1)	435 $\begin{smallmatrix} +16 \\ -33 \end{smallmatrix}$...	0.99
112.28 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	3.5 ± 0.3	0.19 ± 0.02	0.79
113.13 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	7.7 ± 0.4	0.14 ± 0.01	1.00
113.39 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	12.3 ± 0.5	0.25 ± 0.02	1.00
114.74 ± 0.01	(1, ?)	2.9 ± 0.2	0.01 ± 0.01	0.93
120.59 ± 0.03	(1, 1)	5.4 ± 0.7	0.39 ± 0.10	0.99
121.60 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	6.8 ± 0.6	0.12 ± 0.02	0.99
121.88 ± 0.02	(1, 1)	9.6 ± 0.6	0.28 ± 0.04	1.00
122.74 ± 0.02	(1, -1)	4.3 ± 0.4	0.16 ± 0.03	0.99
123.101 ± 0.003	(1, 1)	347 $\begin{smallmatrix} +36 \\ -29 \end{smallmatrix}$...	1.00
128.53 ± 0.01	(1, ?)	3.2 ± 0.3	0.10 ± 0.01	0.98
129.23 ± 0.01	(1, -1)	3.7 ± 0.4	0.11 ± 0.01	0.98
129.52 ± 0.02	(1, 1)	1.3 ± 0.1	0.07 ± 0.01	0.62
129.95 ± 0.02	(1, -1)	6.0 ± 0.3	0.32 ± 0.05	0.56
130.20 ± 0.01	(1, 1)	4.8 ± 0.3	0.16 ± 0.02	0.15
130.47 ± 0.02	(1, -1)	3.9 ± 0.3	0.19 ± 0.03	0.72

Table C.1 (continued)

Frequency (μHz)	(ℓ, m)	Amplitude or Height ^a (ppm) or ($\text{ppm}^2 \mu\text{Hz}^{-1}$)	Linewidth (μHz)	Detection Probability ^b
130.74 ± 0.02	(1, 1)	6.1 ± 0.5	0.29 ± 0.05	0.99
131.14 ± 0.02	(1, -1)	1.7 ± 0.1	0.08 ± 0.01	0.13
137.30 ± 0.03	(1, -1)	5.0 ± 0.7	0.41 ± 0.13	0.97
137.74 ± 0.07	(1, 1)	3.3 ± 0.8	0.53 ± 0.18	0.31
138.65 ± 0.04	(1, -1)	7.7 ± 0.9	1.10 ± 0.26	1.00
139.06 ± 0.02	(1, 1)	4.2 ± 0.5	0.13 ± 0.03	0.99
91.84 ± 0.01	(2, 0)	1.7 ± 0.1	0.25 ± 0.02	0.63
99.63 ± 0.04	(2, 0)	11.1 ± 1.0	0.82 ± 0.11	1.00
108.24 ± 0.02	(2, 0)	11.6 ± 1.2	0.78 ± 0.11	1.00
116.54 ± 0.01	(2, 0)	13.3 ± 0.5	1.00 ± 0.08	1.00
125.06 ± 0.03	(2, 0)	10.8 ± 0.8	0.84 ± 0.15	1.00
133.35 ± 0.02	(2, 0)	9.3 ± 0.6	0.85 ± 0.09	1.00
86.01 ± 0.01	(3, 0)	3.1 ± 0.1	0.27 ± 0.02	0.68

^aAn amplitude is measured when the peak is a resolved Lorentzian, while height is measured instead when the peak is an unresolved Sinc² function. Linewidth is not defined in the latter case.

^bValues of 0.99 and above are ensured to be significant.

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